

Supplementary Table 1

Cluster Number	# of Genes in the Cluster	Gene Set Name [# Genes (K)]	Description	# Genes in Overlap (k)	p-value	FDRq-value
1	49					
		REACTOME_GPCR_LIGAND_BINDING [463]	GPCR ligand binding	6	1.86 e ⁻⁵	2.93 e ⁻²
		REACTOME_SIGNALING_BY_GPCR [702]	Signaling by GPCR	7	1.92 e ⁻⁵	2.93 e ⁻²
		REACTOME_CLASS_A_1_RHODOPSIN_LIKE_RECEECEPTORS [331]	Class A/1 (Rhodopsin-like receptors)	5	4.73 e ⁻⁵	4.81 e ⁻²
		REACTOME_GPCR_LIGAND_BINDING [463]	GPCR ligand binding	6	1.86 e ⁻⁵	2.93 e ⁻²
		REACTOME_SIGNALING_BY_GPCR [702]	Signaling by GPCR	7	1.92 e ⁻⁵	2.93 e ⁻²
		REACTOME_CLASS_A_1_RHODOPSIN_LIKE_RECEECEPTORS [331]	Class A/1 (Rhodopsin-like receptors)	5	4.73 e ⁻⁵	4.81 e ⁻²
		GOBP_ION_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORT [1169]	A process in which an ion is transported across a membrane. [GOC:mah]	10	1.02 e ⁻⁶	4.1 e ⁻³
		GOBP_CATION_TRANSPORT [1221]	The directed movement of cations, atoms or small molecules with a net positive charge, into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore. [GOC:ai]	10	1.51 e ⁻⁶	4.1 e ⁻³
		GOBP_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORT [1577]	The process in which a solute is transported across a lipid bilayer, from one side of a membrane to the other. [GOC:dph, GOC:jid]	11	1.99 e ⁻⁶	4.1 e ⁻³

GOBP_ION_TRANSPORT [1587]	The directed movement of charged atoms or small charged molecules into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore. [GOC:ai]	11	2.11×10^{-6}	4.1×10^{-3}
GOBP_ANATOMICAL_STRUCTURE_MATURATION [249]	A developmental process, independent of morphogenetic (shape) change, that is required for an anatomical structure to attain its fully functional state. [GOC:mah]	5	1.21×10^{-5}	1.89×10^{-2}
GOBP_CATION_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORT [949]	The process in which a cation is transported across a membrane. [GOC:dos, GOC:vw]	8	1.55×10^{-5}	2.01×10^{-2}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_ION_TRANSPORT [720]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the directed movement of charged atoms or small charged molecules into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore. [GOC:jl]	7	2.26×10^{-5}	2.2×10^{-2}

GOBP_AUTOCRINE_SIGNALING [7]	Signaling between cells of the same type. The signal produced by the signaling cell binds to a receptor on, and affects a cell of the same type. [GOC:bf, ISBN:3527303782]	2	2.93×10^{-5}	2.2×10^{-2}
GOBP_HIPPOCAMPAL_NEURON_APOPTOTIC_PROCROCESS [7]	Any apoptotic process that occurs in a hippocampal neuron. [GOC:sl, PMID:18940801]	2	2.93×10^{-5}	2.2×10^{-2}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_I_KAPPAB_PB_PHOSPHORYLATION [7]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of I-kappaB phosphorylation. [GO_REF:0000058, GOC:TermGenie, PMID:23675531]	2	2.93×10^{-5}	2.2×10^{-2}
GOBP_DEVELOPMENTAL_MATURATION [303]	A developmental process, independent of morphogenetic (shape) change, that is required for an anatomical structure, cell or cellular component to attain its fully functional state. [GO_REF:0000021, GOC:cls, GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:jid]	5	3.11×10^{-5}	2.2×10^{-2}

GOBP_REGULATION_OF_ION_TRANSMEMBRANE_TE_TRANS PORT [520]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the directed movement of ions from one side of a membrane to the other. [GOC:mah]	6	3.55 e ⁻⁵	2.3 e ⁻²
GOBP_MICROGLIAL_CELL_MIGRATION [8]	The orderly movement of a microglial cell from one site to another. [GO_REF:0000091, GOC:BHF, GOC:nc, GOC:TermGenie, PMID:19100238]	2	3.9 e ⁻⁵	2.33 e ⁻²
GOBP_GENERATION_OF_NEURONS [1453]	The process in which nerve cells are generated. This includes the production of neuroblasts and their differentiation into neurons. [GOC:nln]	9	4.9 e ⁻⁵	2.59 e ⁻²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_I_KAPPAB_PHOSPHORYLRYLATION [9]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of I-kappaB phosphorylation. [GO_REF:0000058, GOC:TermGenie, PMID:23675531]	2	5.01 e ⁻⁵	2.59 e ⁻²

GOBP_SYNAPSE_PRUNING [11]	<p>A cellular process that results in the controlled breakdown of synapse. After it starts the process is continuous until the synapse has disappeared.</p> <p>[GOC:dos, PMID:12062020, PMID:18083105, PMID:22632716, PMID:29844190]</p>	2	7.64×10^{-5}	3.71×10^{-2}
GOBP_CELLULAR_RESPONSE_TO_LIPID [608]	<p>Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a lipid stimulus.</p> <p>[GOC:mah]</p>	6	8.43×10^{-5}	3.76×10^{-2}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_GLIAL_CELLELL_MIGRATION [12]	<p>Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of glial cell migration.</p> <p>[GO_REF:0000058, GOC:BHF, GOC:nc, GOC:TermGenie, PMID:19100238]</p>	2	9.16×10^{-5}	3.76×10^{-2}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORT [618]	<p>Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the directed movement of a solute from one side of a membrane to the other.</p> <p>[GOC:mah]</p>	6	9.21×10^{-5}	3.76×10^{-2}

GOBP_METAL_ION_TRANSPORT [909]	The directed movement of metal ions, any metal ion with an electric charge, into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore. [GOC:ai]	7	9.8×10^{-5}	3.8×10^{-2}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CATION_TRANSMEMBRANRANE_TRANSPORT [394]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of cation transmembrane transport. [GO_REF:0000058, GOC:TermGenie, PMID:15304482]	5	1.07×10^{-4}	3.86×10^{-2}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_SYNAPTIC_PLASTICITY [207]	A process that modulates synaptic plasticity, the ability of synapses to change as circumstances require. They may alter function, such as increasing or decreasing their sensitivity, or they may increase or decrease in actual numbers. [GOC:dph, GOC:jid, GOC:tb, PMID:11891290]	4	1.12×10^{-4}	3.86×10^{-2}
GOBP_INORGANIC_ION_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORT [932]	The process in which an inorganic ion is transported across a membrane. [GOC:mah]	7	1.14×10^{-4}	3.86×10^{-2}

				Generation of cells within the nervous system. [GO_REF:0000021, GOC:cls, GOC:curators, GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:jid]	9	1.41 e ⁻⁴	4.57 e ⁻²
2	52			Primary active transporter of a solute across a membrane, via the reaction: ATP + H ₂ O = ADP + phosphate, to directly drive the transport of a substance across a membrane. The transport protein may be transiently phosphorylated (P-type transporters), or not (ABC-type transporters and other families of transporters). Primary active transport occurs up the solute's concentration gradient and is driven by a primary energy source.			
				GOMF_ATPASE_COUPLED_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORTER_ACTIVITY [98] [GOC:mtg_transport, ISBN:0815340729]	4	7.6 e ⁻⁶	1.34 e ⁻²

GOMF_ABC_TYPE_TRANSPORTER_ACTIVITY [49]	<p>Primary active transporter characterized by two nucleotide-binding domains and two transmembrane domains. Uses the energy generated from ATP hydrolysis to drive the transport of a substance across a membrane.</p>	3	3.4×10^{-5}	3×10^{-2}
GOMF_PRIMARY_ACTIVE_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORTER_ACTIVITY [169]	<p>Enables the transfer of a solute from one side of a membrane to the other, up the solute's concentration gradient, by binding the solute and undergoing a series of conformational changes. Transport works equally well in either direction and is powered by a primary energy source, directly using ATP. Primary energy sources known to be coupled to transport are chemical, electrical and solar sources.</p> <p>[GOC:mtg_transport, ISBN:0815340729, TC:3.-.-.-.]</p>	4	6.45×10^{-5}	3.16×10^{-2}

GOMF_ATP_DEPENDENT_ACTIVITY [555]	<p>A molecular function characterized by the coupling of ATP hydrolysis to other steps of a reaction mechanism to make the reaction energetically favorable, for example to catalyze a reaction or drive transport against a concentration gradient. [PMID:24878343, PMID:25750732, PMID:32933017, PMID:33818025, PMID:33873056, PMID:33988324]</p>	6	7.18 e^{-5}	3.16 e^{-2}
GOMF_SIGNALING_RECEPTOR_BINDING [1544]	<p>Binding to one or more specific sites on a receptor molecule, a macromolecule that undergoes combination with a hormone, neurotransmitter, drug or intracellular messenger to initiate a change in cell function. [GOC:bf, GOC:ceb, ISBN:0198506732]</p>	9	1.27 e^{-4}	4.17 e^{-2}

		GOMF_ABC_TYPE_XENOBIOTIC_TRANSPORTER_AR_ACTIVITY [14]	Catalysis of the reaction: ATP + H2O + xenobiotic(in) = ADP + phosphate + xenobiotic(out). [EC:7.6.2.2]	2	1.42 e ⁻⁴	4.17 e ⁻²
3	88	REACTOME_NEUROTRANSMITTER_RELEASE_CYCLE [51]	Neurotransmitter release cycle Dopamine	4	4.58 e ⁻⁶	1.4 e ⁻²
		REACTOME_DOPAMINE_NEUROTRANSMITTER_RELEASE_CYCLE [23]	Neurotransmitter Release Cycle	3	1.64 e ⁻⁵	2.5 e ⁻²
		REACTOME_NEURONAL_SYSTEM [411]	Neuronal System	7	3.05 e ⁻⁵	3.1 e ⁻²
4	60	none				
5	90	KEGG_ABC_TRANSPORTERS [44]	ABC transporters	5	4.61 e ⁻⁸	9.88 e ⁻⁵
		REACTOME_ABC_TRANSPORTERS_IN_LIPID_HOMEOSTASIS [18]	ABC transporters in lipid homeostasis	4	6.48 e ⁻⁸	9.88 e ⁻⁵
		REACTOME_ABC_FAMILY_PROTEINS_MEDIATED_EXPORT [103]	ABC-family proteins mediated transport	5	3.36 e ⁻⁶	3.41 e ⁻³
		REACTOME_TERMINATION_OF_O_GLYCAN_BIOSYNTHESIS [23]	Termination of O-glycan biosynthesis	3	1.75 e ⁻⁵	1.34 e ⁻²
		REACTOME_KERATAN_SULFATE_BIOSYNTHESIS [28]	Keratan sulfate biosynthesis	3	3.22 e ⁻⁵	1.96 e ⁻²
		PID_NEPHRIN_NEPH1_PATHWAY [31]	Nephrin/Neph1 signaling in the kidney podocyte	3	4.39 e ⁻⁵	2.22 e ⁻²
		WP_MAMMARY_GLAND_DEVELOPMENT_PATHWAY_P	Mammary gland development pathway - Pregnancy and lactation			
		Y_PREGNANCY_AND_LACTATION_STAGE_3_OF_4 [33]	(Stage 3 of 4)	3	5.32 e ⁻⁵	2.22 e ⁻²
		REACTOME_KERATAN_SULFATE_KERATIN_METABOLISM [34]	Keratan sulfate/keratin metabolism	3	5.82 e ⁻⁵	2.22 e ⁻²

GOBP_REGULATION_OF_TRANSPORT [1793]	<p>Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the directed movement of substances (such as macromolecules, small molecules, ions) into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore.</p> <p>[GOC:ai]</p>	15	7.99 e^{-6}	3.01 e^{-2}
GOBP_KERATAN_SULFATE_METABOLIC_PROCESS [18]	<p>The chemical reactions and pathways involving keratan sulfate, a glycosaminoglycan with repeat units consisting of beta-1,4-linked D-galactopyranosyl-beta-(1,4)-N-acetyl-D-glucosamine 6-sulfate and with variable amounts of fucose, sialic acid and mannose units; keratan sulfate chains are covalently linked by a glycosidic attachment through the trisaccharide galactosyl-galactosyl-xylose to peptidyl-threonine or serine residues.</p> <p>[GOC:go_curators]</p>	3	8.14 e^{-6}	3.01 e^{-2}

GOBP_LIPID_LOCALIZATION [483]	Any process in which a lipid is transported to, or maintained in, a specific location. [GOC:BHF, GOC:dph, GOC:tb]	8	1.16 e ⁻⁵	3.01 e ⁻²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_LIPID_TRANSPORT [155]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the directed movement of lipids into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore. [GOC:mah]	5	2.45 e ⁻⁵	4.76 e ⁻²

GOMF_ATPASE_COUPLED_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORTER_ACTIVITY [98]	<p>Primary active transporter of a solute across a membrane, via the reaction: $\text{ATP} + \text{H}_2\text{O} = \text{ADP} + \text{phosphate}$, to directly drive the transport of a substance across a membrane. The transport protein may be transiently phosphorylated (P-type transporters), or not (ABC-type transporters and other families of transporters). Primary active transport occurs up the solute's concentration gradient and is driven by a primary energy source.</p>	7	2.27×10^{-9}	4.01×10^{-6}
GOMF_ABC_TYPE_TRANSPORTER_ACTIVITY [49]	<p>Primary active transporter characterized by two nucleotide-binding domains and two transmembrane domains. Uses the energy generated from ATP hydrolysis to drive the transport of a substance across a membrane.</p>	5	8.03×10^{-8}	5.86×10^{-5}

GOMF_PRIMARY_ACTIVE_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORTER_ACTIVITY [169]	<p>Enables the transfer of a solute from one side of a membrane to the other, up the solute's concentration gradient, by binding the solute and undergoing a series of conformational changes. Transport works equally well in either direction and is powered by a primary energy source, directly using ATP. Primary energy sources known to be coupled to transport are chemical, electrical and solar sources.</p>	[GOC:mtg_transport, ISBN:0815340729, TC:3.-.-.-.-.]	7	9.98 e ⁻⁸	5.86 e ⁻⁵
GOMF_LIPID_TRANSPORTER_ACTIVITY [161]	<p>Enables the directed movement of lipids into, out of or within a cell, or between cells. [GOC:ai]</p>		5	2.94 e ⁻⁵	1.11 e ⁻²

GOMF_ATP_DEPENDENT_ACTIVITY [555]	<p>A molecular function characterized by the coupling of ATP hydrolysis to other steps of a reaction mechanism to make the reaction energetically favorable, for example to catalyze a reaction or drive transport against a concentration gradient.</p> <p>[PMID:24878343, PMID:25750732, PMID:32933017, PMID:33818025, PMID:33873056, PMID:33988324]</p>	8	3.13 e^{-5}	1.11 e^{-2}
GOMF_ACTIVE_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORTER_ER_ACTIV ITY [418]	<p>Enables the transfer of a specific substance or related group of substances from one side of a membrane to the other, up the solute's concentration gradient. The transporter binds the solute and undergoes a series of conformational changes. Transport works equally well in either direction.</p> <p>[GOC:mtg_transport, ISBN:0815340729]</p>	7	3.92 e^{-5}	1.15 e^{-2}

GOMF_STEROID_BINDING [101]	Binding to a steroid, any of a large group of substances that have in common a ring system based on 1,2-cyclopentanoperhydrophenanthrene. [GOC:jl, ISBN:0198506732]	4	7.52×10^{-5}	1.79×10^{-2}
GOMF_TRANSPORTER_ACTIVITY [1231]	Enables the directed movement of substances (such as macromolecules, small molecules, ions) into, out of or within a cell, or between cells. [GOC:ai, GOC:dgf]	11	8.12×10^{-5}	1.79×10^{-2}
GOMF_BETA_GALACTOSIDE_CMP_ALPHA_2_3_SI_SIALYLTRANSFERASE_ACTIVITY [7]	Catalysis of the reaction: CMP-N-acetylneuraminate + beta-D-galactosyl-(1->3)-N-acetyl-alpha-D-galactosaminyl-R = CMP + alpha-N-acetylneuraminyl-(2->3)-beta-D-galactosyl-(1->3)-N-acetyl-alpha-D-galactosaminyl-R. [EC:2.4.99.4]	2	9.93×10^{-5}	1.94×10^{-2}

GOMF_PHOSPHATIDYLCHOLINE_FLOPPASE_ACTIVITY [8]	Catalysis of the movement of phosphatidylcholine from the cytosolic to the exoplasmic leaflet of a membrane, using energy from the hydrolysis of ATP. [GOC:ab, PMID:16452632, RHEA:38583]	2	1.32 e ⁻⁴	2.33 e ⁻²
GOMF_ADENYL_NUCLEOTIDE_BINDING [1552]	Binding to an adenyly nucleotide, an adenosine esterified with (ortho)phosphate. [ISBN:0198506732]	12	1.48 e ⁻⁴	2.37 e ⁻²
GOMF_CHOLESTEROL_BINDING [51]	Binding to cholesterol (cholest-5-en-3-beta-ol); the principal sterol of vertebrates and the precursor of many steroids, including bile acids and steroid hormones. [GOC:jl, ISBN:0198506732]	3	1.97 e ⁻⁴	2.9 e ⁻²
GOMF_STEROL_BINDING [61]	Binding to a sterol, a steroid containing a hydroxy group in the 3 position, closely related to cholestan-3-ol. [GOC:mah]	3	3.35 e ⁻⁴	4.55 e ⁻²

6	258		Binding to a microtubule, a filament composed of tubulin monomers.			
		GOMF_MICROTUBULE_BINDING [273]	[GOC:krc]	9	6.46 e ⁻⁵	4.51 e ⁻²
			Enables the transfer of a polyol from one side of a membrane to the other. A polyol is any polyhydric alcohol.			
		GOMF_POLYOL_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORTER_ACTIVITY [13]	[ISBN:0198506732]	3	6.72 e ⁻⁵	4.51 e ⁻²
			A motor activity that generates movement along a microtubule, driven by ATP hydrolysis.			
			[PMID:19686686, PMID:32684327, PMID:32842864]			
		GOMF_MICROTUBULE_MOTOR_ACTIVITY [69]		5	7.67 e ⁻⁵	4.51 e ⁻²
			A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of a prolongation or process extending from a cell, e.g. a flagellum or axon. [GOC:jl, GOC:mah, http://www.cogsci.princeton.edu/~wn/]			
		GOBP_CELL_PROJECTION_ORGANIZATION [1576]		33	1.72 e ⁻⁹	1.34 e ⁻⁵

GOBP_CYTOSKELETON_ORGANIZATION [1519]	A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of cytoskeletal structures. [GOC:dph, GOC:jl, GOC:mah]	30	3.68×10^{-8}	1.43×10^{-4}
GOBP_CELL_PROJECTION_ASSEMBLY [607]	Formation of a prolongation or process extending from a cell, e.g. a flagellum or axon. [GOC:jl, GOC:mah, http://www.cogsci.princeton.edu/~wn/]	17	3.82×10^{-7}	9.89×10^{-4}
GOBP_MICROTUBULE_BASED_PROTEIN_TRANSPORT [13]	A microtubule-based process that results in the transport of proteins. [GOC:vw]	4	1.05×10^{-6}	2.03×10^{-3}
GOBP_AXONEME_ASSEMBLY [93]	The assembly and organization of an axoneme, the bundle of microtubules and associated proteins that forms the core of cilia (also called flagella) in eukaryotic cells and is responsible for their movements. [GOC:bf, GOC:cilia, GOC:jl, ISBN:0815316194]	7	2.15×10^{-6}	2.56×10^{-3}

GOBP_ANTEROGRADE_DENDRITIC_TRANSPORT_OT_OF_NEUROTRANSMITTER_RECEPTOR_COMPLEX [5]	The directed movement of a neurotransmitter receptor complex along microtubules in nerve cell dendrites towards the postsynapse. [GOC:dos]	3	2.44 e ⁻⁶	2.56 e ⁻³
GOBP_CILIUM_ORGANIZATION [416]	A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of a cilium, a specialized eukaryotic organelle that consists of a filiform extrusion of the cell surface. Each cilium is bounded by an extrusion of the cytoplasmic membrane, and contains a regular longitudinal array of microtubules, anchored basally in a centriole. [GOC:cilia, GOC:jl]	13	2.82 e ⁻⁶	2.56 e ⁻³
GOBP_MICROTUBULE_BASED_PROCESS [946]	Any cellular process that depends upon or alters the microtubule cytoskeleton, that part of the cytoskeleton comprising microtubules and their associated proteins. [GOC:mah]	20	2.84 e ⁻⁶	2.56 e ⁻³

GOBP_MICROTUBULE_BASED_MOVEMENT [418]	A microtubule-based process that results in the movement of organelles, other microtubules, or other cellular components. Examples include motor-driven movement along microtubules and movement driven by polymerization or depolymerization of microtubules. [GOC:cjm, ISBN:0815316194]	13	2.97×10^{-6}	2.56×10^{-3}
GOBP_AXO_DENDRITIC_PROTEIN_TRANSPORT [8]	The directed movement of proteins along microtubules in neuron projections. [ISBN:0815316194]	3	1.35×10^{-5}	1.04×10^{-2}
GOBP_MICROTUBULE_BUNDLE_FORMATION [125]	A process that results in a parallel arrangement of microtubules. [GOC:dph]	7	1.52×10^{-5}	1.08×10^{-2}
GOBP_ANTEROGRADE_DENDRITIC_TRANSPORT [9]	The directed movement of organelles or molecules along microtubules from the cell body toward the postsynapse in dendrites. [ISBN:0815316194]	3	2.01×10^{-5}	1.3×10^{-2}

GOBP_CELL_MOTILITY [1794]	Any process involved in the controlled self-propelled movement of a cell that results in translocation of the cell from one place to another. [GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:isa_complete, GOC:mlg]	27	2.83 e ⁻⁵	1.58 e ⁻²
GOBP_PROTEIN_LOCALIZATION_TO_PRESYNAPSAPSE [10]	A process in which a protein is transported to, or maintained in, a location within a presynapse. [GO_REF:0000087, GOC:TermGenie, PMID:24449494]	3	2.86 e ⁻⁵	1.58 e ⁻²
GOBP_EPITHELIUM_DEVELOPMENT [1211]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of an epithelium over time, from its formation to the mature structure. An epithelium is a tissue that covers the internal or external surfaces of an anatomical structure. [GOC:dph, GOC:mtg_lung]	21	3.15 e ⁻⁵	1.63 e ⁻²

GOBP_MICROTUBULE_BASED_TRANSPORT [210]	<p>A microtubule-based process that results in the transport of organelles, other microtubules, or other cellular components. Examples include motor-driven movement along microtubules and movement driven by polymerization or depolymerization of microtubules. [GOC:cjm, ISBN:0815316194]</p>	8	6.05×10^{-5}	2.83×10^{-2}
GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_RETINOIC_ACID [108]	<p>Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a retinoic acid stimulus. [GOC:sl]</p>	6	6.54×10^{-5}	2.83×10^{-2}
GOBP_DENDRITIC_TRANSPORT [13]	<p>The directed movement of organelles or molecules along microtubules in dendrites. [ISBN:0815316194]</p>	3	6.72×10^{-5}	2.83×10^{-2}

GOBP_TISSUE_DEVELOPMENT [1998]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a tissue over time, from its formation to the mature structure.	28	6.91×10^{-5}	2.83×10^{-2}
GOBP_MICROTUBULE_CYTOSKELETON_ORGANIZAIZATION [663]	[ISBN:0471245208] A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of cytoskeletal structures comprising microtubules and their associated proteins. [GOC:mah]	14	9.14×10^{-5}	3.55×10^{-2}
GOBP_AXONEMAL_DYNEIN_COMPLEX_ASSEMBLY [39]	The aggregation, arrangement and bonding together of a set of components to form an axonemal dynein complex, a dynein complex found in eukaryotic cilia and flagella, in which the motor domain heads interact with adjacent microtubules to generate a sliding force which is converted to a bending motion. [GOC:cilia, GOC:mah, PMID:19052621]	4	1.06×10^{-4}	3.91×10^{-2}

				The process whose specific outcome is the progression of an embryo over time, from zygote formation until the end of the embryonic life stage. The end of the embryonic life stage is organism-specific and may be somewhat arbitrary; for mammals it is usually considered to be birth, for insects the hatching of the first instar larva from the eggshell. [GOC:go_curators, GOC:isa_complete, GOC:mtg_sensu]			
		GOBP_EMBRYO_DEVELOPMENT_ENDING_IN_BIRTIRTH_OR_EGG_HATCHING [679]			14	1.17 e ⁻⁴	4.13 e ⁻²
7	44	none					
				Binding to one or more specific sites on a receptor molecule, a macromolecule that undergoes combination with a hormone, neurotransmitter, drug or intracellular messenger to initiate a change in cell function. [GOC:bf, GOC:ceb, ISBN:0198506732]			
8	88				15	9.68 e ⁻⁷	1.71 e ⁻³
		GOMF_SIGNALING_RECEPTOR_BINDING [1544]					

GOBP_REGULATION_OF_TRANSPORT [1793]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the directed movement of substances (such as macromolecules, small molecules, ions) into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore. [GOC:ai]	17	2.31 e ⁻⁷	1.8 e ⁻³
GOBP_HOMEOSTATIC_PROCESS [1708]	Any biological process involved in the maintenance of an internal steady state. [GOC:j], ISBN:0395825172	16	6.48 e ⁻⁷	2.51 e ⁻³
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_MULTICELLULAR_ORGANISMAL_PROCESS [1556]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of an organismal process, any of the processes pertinent to the function of an organism above the cellular level; includes the integrated processes of tissues and organs. [GOC:ai]	15	1.07 e ⁻⁶	2.76 e ⁻³
GOBP_INORGANIC_ION_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORT [932]	The process in which an inorganic ion is transported across a membrane. [GOC:mah]	11	5.12 e ⁻⁶	9.84 e ⁻³

GOBP_ION_TRANSPORT [1587]	The directed movement of charged atoms or small charged molecules into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore. [GOC:ai]	14	7.02×10^{-6}	9.84×10^{-3}
GOBP_ION_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORT [1169]	A process in which an ion is transported across a membrane. [GOC:mah]	12	7.6×10^{-6}	9.84×10^{-3}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_SMALL_MOLECULE_METABOLIC_PROCESS [152]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of a small molecule metabolic process. [GOC:vw]	5	2×10^{-5}	2.14×10^{-2}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_TRANSPORT [903]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of the directed movement of substances (such as macromolecules, small molecules, ions) into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore. [GOC:ai]	10	2.44×10^{-5}	2.14×10^{-2}

GOBP_METAL_ION_TRANSPORT [909]	The directed movement of metal ions, any metal ion with an electric charge, into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore. [GOC:ai]	10	2.58×10^{-5}	2.14×10^{-2}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_PHOSPHORUS_RUSTIC_BIOLOGICAL_PROCESS [916]	Any process that increases the frequency, rate or extent of the chemical reactions and pathways involving phosphorus or compounds containing phosphorus. [GOC:dph, GOC:tb]	10	2.76×10^{-5}	2.14×10^{-2}
GOBP_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORT [1577]	The process in which a solute is transported across a lipid bilayer, from one side of a membrane to the other. [GOC:dph, GOC:jid]	13	3.13×10^{-5}	2.21×10^{-2}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_MOLECULAR_ACTIVITY [1591]	Any process that activates or increases the rate or extent of a molecular function, an elemental biological activity occurring at the molecular level, such as catalysis or binding. [GO:j]	13	3.43×10^{-5}	2.22×10^{-2}

GOBP_CATION_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORT [949]	The process in which a cation is transported across a membrane. [GOC:dos, GOC:vw]	10	3.71 e ⁻⁵	2.22 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_CATALYTIC_IC_ACTIVITY [1196]	Any process that activates or increases the activity of an enzyme. [GOC:ebc, GOC:jl, GOC:tb, GOC:vw] An intracellular protein kinase cascade containing at least a MAPK, a MAPKK and a MAP3K. The cascade can also contain an additional tiers: the upstream MAP4K. The kinases in each tier phosphorylate and activate the kinase in the downstream tier to transmit a signal within a cell. [GOC:bf, GOC:mtg_signaling_feb11, PMID:20811974, PMID:9561267]	11	5.1 e ⁻⁵	2.67 e ⁻²
GOBP_MAPK_CASCADE [797]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of endocytosis.	9	5.49 e ⁻⁵	2.67 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_ENDOCYTOSIOSIS [97]	[GOC:go_curators]	4	5.89 e ⁻⁵	2.67 e ⁻²

GOBP_CATION_TRANSPORT [1221]	The directed movement of cations, atoms or small molecules with a net positive charge, into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore. [GOC:ai]	11	6.13 e ⁻⁵	2.67 e ⁻²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_SECRETION [626]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the controlled release of a substance from a cell or a tissue. [GOC:ai]	8	6.2 e ⁻⁵	2.67 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_PHOSPHORYLRYLATION [830]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of addition of phosphate groups to a molecule. [GOC:j]	9	7.48 e ⁻⁵	3.06 e ⁻²
GOBP_CHEMICAL_HOMEOSTASIS [1062]	Any biological process involved in the maintenance of an internal steady state of a chemical. [GOC:isa_complete]	10	9.44 e ⁻⁵	3.12 e ⁻²

GOBP_MINERALOCORTICOID_SECRETION [7]	The regulated release of any mineralocorticoid into the circulatory system. Mineralocorticoids are a class of steroid hormones that regulate water and electrolyte metabolism. [GOC:sl]	2	9.49 e ⁻⁵	3.12 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_DENDRITIC_IC_CELL_ANTI GEN_PROCESSING_AND_PRESENTATION [7]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate, or extent of dendritic cell antigen processing and presentation. [GOC:add]	2	9.49 e ⁻⁵	3.12 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_MAPK_CASCASCADE [498]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of signal transduction mediated by the MAPK cascade. [GOC:go_curators]	7	1.01 e ⁻⁴	3.12 e ⁻²
GOBP_CALCIUM_ION_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPOSPORT [3 45]	A process in which a calcium ion is transported from one side of a membrane to the other by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore. [GOC:mah]	6	1.03 e ⁻⁴	3.12 e ⁻²

GOBP_ERK1_AND_ERK2_CASCADE [346]	<p>An intracellular protein kinase cascade containing at least ERK1 or ERK2 (MAPKs), a MEK (a MAPKK) and a MAP3K. The cascade may involve 4 different kinases, as it can also contain an additional tier: the upstream MAP4K. The kinases in each tier phosphorylate and activate the kinase in the downstream tier to transmit a signal within a cell. [GOC:add, GOC:signaling, ISBN:0121245462, ISBN:0896039986, PMID:20811974, PMID:28903453]</p>	6	1.05 e^{-4}	3.12 e^{-2}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_LIPID_METABOLIC_PROPROCESS [346]	<p>Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the chemical reactions and pathways involving lipids. [GOC:go_curators]</p>	6	1.05 e^{-4}	3.12 e^{-2}
GOBP_CELL_ADHESION [1541]	<p>The attachment of a cell, either to another cell or to an underlying substrate such as the extracellular matrix, via cell adhesion molecules. [GOC:hb, GOC:pf]</p>	12	1.11 e^{-4}	3.2 e^{-2}

GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_ERK1_AND_ED_ERK2_CASCADE [226]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of signal transduction mediated by the ERK1 and ERK2 cascade. [GOC:mah]	5	1.31 e ⁻⁴	3.55 e ⁻²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_ION_TRANSMEMBRANE_TE_TRANSPORT [520]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the directed movement of ions from one side of a membrane to the other. [GOC:mah]	7	1.32 e ⁻⁴	3.55 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_ANTIGEN_PRESENTATION [9]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate, or extent of antigen processing and presentation. [GOC:add]	2	1.62 e ⁻⁴	3.93 e ⁻²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_ION_TRANSPORT [720]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the directed movement of charged atoms or small charged molecules into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore. [GOC:jl]	8	1.62 e ⁻⁴	3.93 e ⁻²

GOBP_REGULATION_OF_HORMONE_SECRETION [237]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the regulated release of a hormone from a cell. [GOC:ai]	5	1.64 e ⁻⁴	3.93 e ⁻²
GOBP_ERBB_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [127]	The series of molecular signals initiated by binding of a ligand to a member of the ERBB family of receptor tyrosine kinases on the surface of a cell, and ending with the regulation of a downstream cellular process, e.g. transcription. [GOC:jc, PMID:16460914, Wikipedia:ErbB]	4	1.67 e ⁻⁴	3.93 e ⁻²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_VESICLE_MEDIATED_TRANSPORT [549]	Any process that modulates the rate, frequency, or extent of vesicle-mediated transport, the directed movement of substances, either within a vesicle or in the vesicle membrane, into, out of or within a cell. [GOC:dph, GOC:tb]	7	1.85 e ⁻⁴	4.22 e ⁻²
GOBP_SECRETION [954]	The controlled release of a substance by a cell or a tissue. [GOC:ai]	9	2.12 e ⁻⁴	4.5 e ⁻²

GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_RECEPTOR_MR_MEDIATE D_ENDOCYTOSIS [54]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of receptor mediated endocytosis, the uptake of external materials by cells, utilizing receptors to ensure specificity of transport. [GOC:go_curators, GOC:tb]	3	2.19 e ⁻⁴	4.5 e ⁻²
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_LEUKOCYTE_TE_APOPTO TIC_PROCESS [55]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent of leukocyte apoptotic process. [GOC:BHF, GOC:mtg_apoptosis]	3	2.31 e ⁻⁴	4.5 e ⁻²
GOBP_ESTABLISHMENT_OF_PROTEIN_LOCALIZAIZATION [16 68]	The directed movement of a protein to a specific location. [GOC:bf]	12	2.32 e ⁻⁴	4.5 e ⁻²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_PHOSPHORUS_METABOLIOLIC_PRO CESS [1427]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the chemical reactions and pathways involving phosphorus or compounds containing phosphorus. [GOC:ai]	11	2.4 e ⁻⁴	4.5 e ⁻²

GOBP_CELL_CELL_SIGNALING [1679]	<p>Any process that mediates the transfer of information from one cell to another. This process includes signal transduction in the receiving cell and, where applicable, release of a ligand and any processes that actively facilitate its transport and presentation to the receiving cell. Examples include signaling via soluble ligands, via cell adhesion molecules and via gap junctions. [GOC:dos, GOC:mah]</p>	12	2.46 e^{-4}	4.5 e^{-2}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_DENDRITIC_CELL_ANTINTIGEN_PROCESSING_AND_PRESENTATION [11]	<p>Any process that modulates the frequency, rate, or extent of dendritic cell antigen processing and presentation. [GOC:add]</p>	2	2.47 e^{-4}	4.5 e^{-2}

GOBP_UTERINE_SMOOTH_MUSCLE_CONTRACTION [11]	<p>A process in which force is generated within smooth muscle tissue, resulting in a change in muscle geometry. This process occurs in the uterus. Force generation involves a chemo-mechanical energy conversion step that is carried out by the actin/myosin complex activity, which generates force through ATP hydrolysis. The uterus is a muscular organ of the female mammal for containing and usually for nourishing the young during development prior to birth. [GOC:sl]</p>	2	2.47 e ⁻⁴	4.5 e ⁻²
GOBP_RHO_PROTEIN_SIGNAL_TRANSDUCTION [141]	<p>The series of molecular signals within the cell that are mediated by a member of the Rho family of proteins switching to a GTP-bound active state. [GOC:bf]</p>	4	2.49 e ⁻⁴	4.5 e ⁻²

				The chemical reactions and pathways resulting in the formation of small molecules, any low molecular weight, monomeric, non-encoded molecule. [GOC:curators, GOC:pde, GOC:vw]	7	2.58×10^{-4}	4.55×10^{-2}
				Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of hydrolase activity, the catalysis of the hydrolysis of various bonds. [GOC:ai]	7	2.89×10^{-4}	4.94×10^{-2}
				The process of elimination of immature T cells which react strongly with self-antigens. [ISBN:0781735149, PMID:12414722]	2	2.96×10^{-4}	4.94×10^{-2}
				A circulatory process that occurs at the level of the vasculature. [GOC:mtg_cardio]	5	2.99×10^{-4}	4.94×10^{-2}
9	123			The attachment of a plasma membrane adhesion molecule in one cell to an identical molecule in an adjacent cell. [ISBN:0198506732]	7	9.52×10^{-7}	7.39×10^{-3}

10	277	REACTOME_REGULATION_OF_CHOLESTEROL_BIOBIOSYNTHESIS_BY_SREBP_SREBF [55]	Regulation of cholesterol biosynthesis by SREBP (SREBF)	7	9.14 e ⁻⁸	2.79 e ⁻⁴
		WP_STEROL_REGULATORY_ELEMENTBINDING_PR_PROTEINS_SREBP_SIGNALING [71]	Sterol regulatory element-binding proteins (SREBP) signaling	7	5.46 e ⁻⁷	8.33 e ⁻⁴
		REACTOME_RHO_GTPASE_CYCLE [450]	RHO GTPase cycle	14	2.82 e ⁻⁶	2.87 e ⁻³
		REACTOME_ACTIVATION_OF_GENE_EXPRESSIONION_BY_SREBF_SREBP [42]	Activation of gene expression by SREBF (SREBP)	5	9.4 e ⁻⁶	6.65 e ⁻³
		REACTOME_METABOLISM_OF_STEROIDS [154]	Metabolism of steroids	8	1.09 e ⁻⁵	6.65 e ⁻³
		WP_CHOLESTEROL_METABOLISM_WITH_BLOCH_AH_AND_KANDUTSCHRUSSELL_PATHWAYS [47]	Cholesterol metabolism with Bloch and Kandutsch-Russell pathways	5	1.65 e ⁻⁵	8.38 e ⁻³
		KEGG_ENDOCYTOSIS [181]	Endocytosis	8	3.49 e ⁻⁵	1.52 e ⁻²
		REACTOME_METABOLISM_OF_LIPIDS [742]	Metabolism of lipids	16	5.3 e ⁻⁵	2.02 e ⁻²
		REACTOME_MEMBRANE_TRAFFICKING [629]	Membrane Trafficking	14	1.12 e ⁻⁴	3.78 e ⁻²
		REACTOME_SIGNALING_BY_RHO_GTPASES_MIROIRO_GTPASES_AND_RHOBTB3 [721]	Signaling by Rho GTPases, Miro GTPases and RHOBTB3	15	1.34 e ⁻⁴	4.08 e ⁻²
		BIOCARTA_ARAP_PATHWAY [17]	ADP-Ribosylation Factor	3	1.93 e ⁻⁴	4.91 e ⁻²
		KEGG_STEROID_BIOSYNTHESIS [17]	Steroid biosynthesis	3	1.93 e ⁻⁴	4.91 e ⁻²

GOBP_VESICLE_MEDIATED_TRANSPORT [1620]	<p>A cellular transport process in which transported substances are moved in membrane-bounded vesicles; transported substances are enclosed in the vesicle lumen or located in the vesicle membrane. The process begins with a step that directs a substance to the forming vesicle, and includes vesicle budding and coating. Vesicles are then targeted to, and fuse with, an acceptor membrane. [GOC:ai, GOC:mah, ISBN:08789310662000]</p>	34	5.73×10^{-9}	4.45×10^{-5}
GOBP_INTRACELLULAR_TRANSPORT [1588]	<p>The directed movement of substances within a cell. [GOC:ai]</p>	33	1.24×10^{-8}	4.82×10^{-5}
GOBP_ENDOSOMAL_TRANSPORT [250]	<p>The directed movement of substances mediated by an endosome, a membrane-bounded organelle that carries materials enclosed in the lumen or located in the endosomal membrane. [ISBN:0198506732]</p>	12	1.63×10^{-7}	3.93×10^{-4}

GOBP_REGULATION_OF_SMALL_GTPASE_MEDIATED_SIGNAL_TRANSDUCTION [306]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of small GTPase mediated signal transduction. [GOC:go_curators]	13	2.03 e ⁻⁷	3.93 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_GTPASE_ACTIVITY [375]	Any process that modulates the rate of GTP hydrolysis by a GTPase. [GOC:jl, GOC:mah]	14	3.3 e ⁻⁷	5.12 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_SMALL_GTPASE_MEDIATED_SIGNAL_TRANSDUCTION [507]	The series of molecular signals in which a small monomeric GTPase relays a signal. [GOC:mah]	16	4.54 e ⁻⁷	5.87 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_VESICLE_MEDIATED_TRANSPORT_TO_THE_PLASMA_MEMBRANE [151]	The directed movement of substances to the plasma membrane in transport vesicles that fuse with the plasma membrane by exocytosis. [GOC:dos]	9	9.82 e ⁻⁷	1.09 e ⁻³
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_INTRACELLULAR_SIGNAL_TRANSDUCTION [1767]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of intracellular signal transduction. [GOC:dph, GOC:signaling, GOC:tb, GOC:TermGenie]	31	1.37 e ⁻⁶	1.33 e ⁻³

GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CATABOLIC_PROCESS [1002]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate, or extent of the chemical reactions and pathways resulting in the breakdown of substances. [GOC:go_curators]	22	1.57 e ⁻⁶	1.35 e ⁻³
GOBP_ENDOCYTIC_RECYCLING [86]	The directed movement of membrane-bounded vesicles from endosomes back to the plasma membrane, a trafficking pathway that promotes the recycling of internalized transmembrane proteins. [PMID:16473635, PMID:23563491]	7	2.03 e ⁻⁶	1.57 e ⁻³
GOBP_RECEPTOR_METABOLIC_PROCESS [61]	The chemical reactions and pathways involving a receptor molecule, a macromolecule that undergoes combination with a hormone, neurotransmitter, drug or intracellular messenger to initiate a change in cell function. [GOC:jl]	6	3.66 e ⁻⁶	2.58 e ⁻³
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_GTPASE_ACTIVITY [282]	Any process that activates or increases the activity of a GTPase. [GOC:jl, GOC:mah]	11	4.02 e ⁻⁶	2.59 e ⁻³

GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_MOLECULAR_AR_FUNCTI ON [1591]	Any process that activates or increases the rate or extent of a molecular function, an elemental biological activity occurring at the molecular level, such as catalysis or binding. [GO:jl]	28	4.34 e ⁻⁶	2.59 e ⁻³
GOBP_VESICLE_ORGANIZATION [353]	A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of a vesicle. [GOC:mah]	12	5.99 e ⁻⁶	3.16 e ⁻³
GOBP_TISSUE_DEVELOPMENT [1998]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a tissue over time, from its formation to the mature structure. [ISBN:0471245208]	32	6.11 e ⁻⁶	3.16 e ⁻³

pathway for the general turnover of cytoplasmic constituents in eukaryotic cells, it is also responsible for the degradation of active cytoplasmic enzymes and organelles during nutrient starvation. Macroautophagy involves the formation of double-membrane-bounded autophagosomes which enclose the cytoplasmic constituent targeted for degradation in a membrane-bounded structure.

Autophagosomes then fuse with a lysosome (or vacuole) releasing single-membrane-bounded autophagic bodies that are then degraded within the lysosome (or vacuole).

Some types of macroautophagy, e.g. pexophagy, mitophagy, involve selective targeting

GOBP_MACROAUTOPHAGY [321]

11

1.36×10^{-5}

6.53×10^{-3}

GOBP_REGULATION_OF_TRANSPORT [1793]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the directed movement of substances (such as macromolecules, small molecules, ions) into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore.	29	1.43 e ⁻⁵	6.53 e ⁻³
GOBP_MACROMOLECULE_CATABOLIC_PROCESS [1386]	The chemical reactions and pathways resulting in the breakdown of a macromolecule, any molecule of high relative molecular mass, the structure of which essentially comprises the multiple repetition of units derived, actually or conceptually, from molecules of low relative molecular mass.	24	2.8 e ⁻⁵	1.05 e ⁻²
GOBP_ESTABLISHMENT_OF_PROTEIN_LOCALIZATION [1668]	The directed movement of a protein to a specific location. [GOC:bf]	27	2.83 e ⁻⁵	1.05 e ⁻²

GOBP_NEUROGENESIS [1669]	Generation of cells within the nervous system. [GO_REF:0000021, GOC:cls, GOC:curators, GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:jid]	27	2.86 e ⁻⁵	1.05 e ⁻²
GOBP_LIPID_LOCALIZATION [483]	Any process in which a lipid is transported to, or maintained in, a specific location. [GOC:BHF, GOC:dph, GOC:tb]	13	2.93 e ⁻⁵	1.05 e ⁻²
GOBP_PROTEIN_MODIFICATION_BY_SMALL_PROPROTEIN_CONJUGATION_OR_REMOVAL [1039]	A protein modification process in which one or more groups of a small protein, such as ubiquitin or a ubiquitin-like protein, are covalently attached to or removed from a target protein. [GOC:mah]	20	3.13 e ⁻⁵	1.05 e ⁻²
GOBP_SECRETION [954]	The controlled release of a substance by a cell or a tissue. [GOC:ai]	19	3.14 e ⁻⁵	1.05 e ⁻²

GOBP_PROCESS_UTILIZING_AUTOPHAGIC_MECHANISM [560]	<p>A cellular process involving delivery of a portion of the cytoplasm to lysosomes or to the plant or fungal vacuole that does not involve direct transport through the endocytic or vacuolar protein sorting (Vps) pathways. This process typically leads to degradation of the cargo; however, it can also be used to deliver resident proteins, such as in the cytoplasm-to-vacuole targeting (Cvt) pathway. [PMID:21997368,</p>	PMID:22966490, PMID:28596378]	14	3.25 e ⁻⁵	1.05 e ⁻²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CELLULAR_CATABOLIC_IC_PROCESS [805]	<p>Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the chemical reactions and pathways resulting in the breakdown of substances, carried out by individual cells. [GOC:mah]</p>		17	4.01 e ⁻⁵	1.25 e ⁻²

cell that results in the release of intracellular molecules (e.g. hormones, matrix proteins) contained within a membrane-bounded vesicle.

Exocytosis can occur either by full fusion, when the vesicle collapses into the plasma membrane, or by a kiss-and-run mechanism that involves the formation of a transient contact, a pore, between a granule (for example of chromaffin cells) and the plasma membrane. The latter process most of the time leads to only partial secretion of the granule content. Exocytosis begins with steps that prepare vesicles for fusion with the membrane (tethering and docking) and ends when molecules are secreted from the cell. [GOC:mah, ISBN:0716731363,

GOBP_EXOCYTOSIS [372]

11

5.21 e^{-5} 1.56 e^{-2}

GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_HYDROLASE_SE_ACTIVITY [591]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of hydrolase activity, the catalysis of the hydrolysis of various bonds. [GOC:ai]	14	5.79×10^{-5}	1.61×10^{-2}
GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_ENDOGENOUS_STIMULUS [1643]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a stimulus arising within the organism. [GOC:sm] Any process in which a substance or cellular entity, such as a protein complex or organelle, is transported to, and/or maintained in, a specific location within a	26	5.8×10^{-5}	1.61×10^{-2}
GOBP_LOCALIZATION_WITHIN_MEMBRANE [678]	membrane. [GOC:ai]	15	6.82×10^{-5}	1.83×10^{-2}

GOBP_REGULATION_OF_HYDROLASE_ACTIVITY [1025]	<p>Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of hydrolase activity, the catalysis of the hydrolysis of various bonds, e.g. C-O, C-N, C-C, phosphoric anhydride bonds, etc. Hydrolase is the systematic name for any enzyme of EC class 3.</p>	19	8.11×10^{-5}	2.1×10^{-2}
GOBP_CONNECTIVE_TISSUE_DEVELOPMENT [275]	<p>The progression of a connective tissue over time, from its formation to the mature structure.</p>	9	1.17×10^{-4}	2.93×10^{-2}

GOBP_ANATOMICAL_STRUCTURE_FORMATION_IN_INVOLVE D_IN_MORPHOGENESIS [1244]	<p>The developmental process pertaining to the initial formation of an anatomical structure from unspecified parts. This process begins with the specific processes that contribute to the appearance of the discrete structure and ends when the structural rudiment is recognizable. An anatomical structure is any biological entity that occupies space and is distinguished from its surroundings. Anatomical structures can be macroscopic such as a carpel, or microscopic such as an acrosome. [GOC:dph, GOC:jid, GOC:tb]</p>	21	1.27 e ⁻⁴	3.07 e ⁻²
GOBP_COPII_COATED_VESICLE_CARGO_LOADINDING [15]	<p>The formation of a macromolecular complex between the COPII coat proteins and proteins and/or lipoproteins that are going to be transported by the COPII vesicle to the Golgi. [GOC:ascb_2009, GOC:dph, GOC:lb, GOC:tb]</p>	3	1.31 e ⁻⁴	3.07 e ⁻²

GOBP_EXPORT_FROM_CELL [893]	The directed movement of some substance from a cell, into the extracellular region. This may occur via transport across the plasma membrane or via exocytosis. [GOC:pg]	17	1.4 e ⁻⁴	3.21 e ⁻²
GOBP_PROTEIN_MODIFICATION_BY_SMALL_PROPROTEIN_CONJUGATION [897]	A protein modification process in which one or more groups of a small protein, such as ubiquitin or a ubiquitin-like protein, are covalently attached to a target protein. [GOC:mah]	17	1.48 e ⁻⁴	3.28 e ⁻²
GOBP_GENERATION_OF_NEURONS [1453]	The process in which nerve cells are generated. This includes the production of neuroblasts and their differentiation into neurons. [GOC:nln]	23	1.56 e ⁻⁴	3.36 e ⁻²
GOBP_LIPID_BIOSYNTHETIC_PROCESS [734]	The chemical reactions and pathways resulting in the formation of lipids, compounds soluble in an organic solvent but not, or sparingly, in an aqueous solvent. [GOC:go_curators]	15	1.62 e ⁻⁴	3.37 e ⁻²

GOBP_RAS_PROTEIN_SIGNAL_TRANSDUCTION [354]	The series of molecular signals within the cell that are mediated by a member of the Ras superfamily of proteins switching to a GTP-bound active state. [GOC:bf]	10	1.65 e ⁻⁴	3.37 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_CATALYTIC_IC_ACTIVITY [1196]	Any process that activates or increases the activity of an enzyme. [GOC:ebc, GOC:jl, GOC:tb, GOC:vw]	20	2.08 e ⁻⁴	4.14 e ⁻²
GOBP_CELLULAR_RESPONSE_TO_ENDOGENOUS_S_S_STIMULUS [1394]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell (in terms of	22	2.26 e ⁻⁴	4.39 e ⁻²
GOBP_ENDOMEMBRANE_SYSTEM_ORGANIZATION [597]	A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of the endomembrane system. [GOC:mah, GOC:sm]	13	2.41 e ⁻⁴	4.56 e ⁻²
GOBP_GOLGI_VESICLE_TRANSPORT [304]	The directed movement of substances into, out of or within the Golgi apparatus, mediated by vesicles. [GOC:jid, ISBN:0716731363, PMID:10219233]	9	2.47 e ⁻⁴	4.56 e ⁻²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CELL_PROJECTION_ORG ORGANIZATION [683]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of a process	14	2.59 e ⁻⁴	4.64 e ⁻²

GOBP_CELLULAR_COMPONENT_MORPHOGENESIS [768]	The process in which cellular structures, including whole cells or cell parts, are generated and organized. [GOC:dph, GOC:mah, GOC:tb]	15	2.63 e ⁻⁴	4.64 e ⁻²
GOBP_CALCIUM_ION_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPO	A process in which a calcium ion is transported from one side of a membrane to the other by means of a high voltage-	3	2.73 e ⁻⁴	4.7 e ⁻²
SPORT_VIA_HIGH_VOLTAGE_GATED_CALCIUM_C M_CHANNEL [19]				
GOBP_LUNG_ALVEOLUS_DEVELOPMENT [47]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of the alveolus over time, from its formation to the mature structure. The alveolus is a sac for holding air in the lungs; formed by the terminal dilation of air passageways. [GOC:mtg_lung, PMID:9751757]	4	2.89 e ⁻⁴	4.88 e ⁻²
GOMF_NUCLEOSIDE_TRIPHOSPHATASE_REGULAT LATOR_ACTIVITY [489]	Binds to and modulates the activity of an NTPase. [GOC:dph, GOC:tb]	20	1.97 e ⁻¹⁰	3.47 e ⁻⁷
GOMF_ENZYME_REGULATOR_ACTIVITY [1253]	Binds to and modulates the activity of an enzyme. [GOC:dph, GOC:mah, GOC:tb]	29	1.01 e ⁻⁸	8.92 e ⁻⁶
GOMF_GUANYL_NUCLEOTIDE_EXCHANGE_FACTOR TOR_ACTIVITY [225]	Stimulates the exchange of GDP to GTP on a signaling GTPase, changing its	12	5.18 e ⁻⁸	3.04 e ⁻⁵

GOMF_TRANSITION_METAL_ION_BINDING [1091]	Binding to a transition metal ions; a transition metal is an element whose atom has an incomplete d-subshell of extranuclear electrons, or which gives rise to a cation or cations with an incomplete d-subshell. Transition metals often have more than one valency state. Biologically relevant transition metals include vanadium, manganese, iron, copper, cobalt, nickel, molybdenum and silver. [ISBN:0198506732]	24	5 e^{-7}	2.21 e^{-4}
GOMF_ZINC_ION_BINDING [817]	Binding to a zinc ion (Zn). [GOC:ai]	20	9.24 e^{-7}	3.26 e^{-4}
GOMF_ENZYME_ACTIVATOR_ACTIVITY [566]	Binds to and increases the activity of an enzyme. [GOC:dph, GOC:mah, GOC:tb]	16	1.9 e^{-6}	5.58 e^{-4}
GOMF_GTPASE_ACTIVATOR_ACTIVITY [276]	Binds to and increases the activity of a GTPase, an enzyme that catalyzes the hydrolysis of GTP. [GOC:mah]	11	3.27 e^{-6}	8.25 e^{-4}

GOMF_SEQUENCE_SPECIFIC_DNA_BINDING [1686]	Binding to DNA of a specific nucleotide composition, e.g. GC-rich DNA binding, or with a specific sequence motif or type of DNA e.g. promotor binding or rDNA binding. [GOC:jl]	28	1.26 e ⁻⁵	2.78 e ⁻³
GOMF_PHOSPHATIDYLINOSITOL_BINDING [277]	Binding to an inositol-containing glycerophospholipid, i.e. phosphatidylinositol (PtdIns) and its phosphorylated derivatives. [GOC:bf, ISBN:0198506732, PMID:11395417]	10	2.15 e ⁻⁵	3.97 e ⁻³
GOMF_ADENYL_NUCLEOTIDE_BINDING [1552]	Binding to an adenylnucleotide, an adenosine esterified with (ortho)phosphate. [ISBN:0198506732]	26	2.25 e ⁻⁵	3.97 e ⁻³
GOMF_PHOSPHOLIPID_BINDING [476]	Binding to a phospholipid, a class of lipids containing phosphoric acid as a mono- or diester. [ISBN:0198506732]	13	2.52 e ⁻⁵	4.04 e ⁻³
GOMF_CALCIIUM_ION_BINDING [710]	Binding to a calcium ion (Ca ²⁺). [GOC:ai]	16	3.15 e ⁻⁵	4.62 e ⁻³

GOMF_RIBONUCLEOTIDE_BINDING [1904]	Binding to a ribonucleotide, any compound consisting of a ribonucleoside that is esterified with (ortho)phosphate or an oligophosphate at any hydroxyl group on the ribose moiety. [GOC:mah]	29	4.24 e ⁻⁵	5.57 e ⁻³
GOMF_RNA_POLYMERASE_II_TRANSCRIPTION_REGION_SPECIFIC_DNA_BINDING [1427]	Binding to a specific sequence of DNA that is part of a regulatory region that controls the transcription of a gene or Binding to a protein component of a cytoskeleton (actin, microtubule, or intermediate filament cytoskeleton). [GOC:mah]	24	4.43 e ⁻⁵	5.57 e ⁻³
GOMF_CYTOSKELETAL_PROTEIN_BINDING [992]	Catalysis of the reaction: 1-phosphatidyl-myo-inositol 3,5-bisphosphate + H ₂ O =	19	5.28 e ⁻⁵	6.2 e ⁻³
GOMF_PHOSPHATIDYLINOSITOL_3_5_BISPHOSPHATE_PHOSPHATASE_ACTIVITY [14]	Catalysis of the phosphorylation of an amino acid residue in a protein, usually according to the reaction: a protein + ATP = a phosphoprotein + ADP. [MetaCyc:PROTEIN-KINASE-RXN]	3	1.05 e ⁻⁴	1.16 e ⁻²
GOMF_PROTEIN_KINASE_ACTIVITY [580]		13	1.82 e ⁻⁴	1.89 e ⁻²

GOMF_LIPID_BINDING [842]	Binding to a lipid. [GOC:ai]	16	2.24 e ⁻⁴	2.2 e ⁻²
	A molecular function that controls the rate, timing and/or magnitude of gene transcription. The function of transcriptional regulators is to modulate gene expression at the transcription step so that they are expressed in the right cell at the right time and in the right amount throughout the life of the cell and the organism. Genes are transcriptional units, and include bacterial operons. [GOC:pg, GOC:txnOH-2018, Wikipedia:Transcription_factor]			
GOMF_TRANSCRIPTION_REGULATOR_ACTIVITY [1927]	Binding to a specific upstream regulatory DNA sequence (transcription	27	3.01 e ⁻⁴	2.68 e ⁻²
GOMF_CIS_REGULATORY_REGION_SEQUENCE_SPECIFIC_DNA_BINDING [1232]	Catalysis of the transfer of a ubiquitin-like from one protein to another via the	20	3.05 e ⁻⁴	2.68 e ⁻²
GOMF_UBIQUITIN_LIKE_PROTEIN_TRANSFERASE_ACTIVITY [465]	Binding to a neuregulin, a member of the EGF family of growth factors. [GOC:bf, GOC:signaling]	11	3.62 e ⁻⁴	3.04 e ⁻²
GOMF_NEUREGULIN_BINDING [5]		2	4.48 e ⁻⁴	3.29 e ⁻²

		GOMF_PHOSPHATIDYLINOSITOL_3_5_BISPHOSPHATE_5_PHOSPHATASE_ACTIVITY [5]	Catalysis of the reaction: phosphatidylinositol-3,5-bisphosphate + H2O =	2	4.48 e ⁻⁴	3.29 e ⁻²
		GOMF_VOLTAGE_GATED_CALCIUM_CHANNEL_ACTIVITY_INVOLVED_IN_CARDIAC_MUSCLE_CELL_ACTION_POTENTIAL [5]	Enables the transmembrane transfer of a calcium ion by a voltage-gated channel across the plasma membrane of a	2	4.48 e ⁻⁴	3.29 e ⁻²
		GOMF_UBIQUITIN_LIKE_PROTEIN_LIGASE_ACTIVITY [334]	Catalysis of the transfer of a ubiquitin-like protein (ULP) to a substrate	9	4.89 e ⁻⁴	3.45 e ⁻²
		GOMF_KINASE_ACTIVITY [745]	Catalysis of the transfer of a phosphate group, usually from ATP, to a substrate molecule. [ISBN:0198506732]	14	6.12 e ⁻⁴	4.15 e ⁻²
		GOMF_PHOSPHATIDYLINOSITOL_BISPHOSPHATE_ATE_PHOSPHATASE_ACTIVITY [26]	Catalysis of the reaction: phosphatidylinositol bisphosphate + H2O =	3	7.06 e ⁻⁴	4.61 e ⁻²
		GOMF_PROTEIN_SERINE_THREONINE_KINASE_AE_ACTIVITY [432]	Catalysis of the reactions: ATP + protein serine = ADP + protein serine	10	7.83 e ⁻⁴	4.81 e ⁻²
		GOMF_ATPASE_COUPLED_INTRAMEMBRANE_LIPID_TRANSPORTER_ACTIVITY [27]	Catalysis of the movement of lipids from one membrane leaflet to the	3	7.91 e ⁻⁴	4.81 e ⁻²
		GOMF_HYDROLASE_ACTIVITY_ACTING_ON_ESTER_BONDS [769]	Catalysis of the hydrolysis of any ester bond. [GOC:j]	14	8.3 e ⁻⁴	4.88 e ⁻²

11

122

GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_PROTEIN_METABOLIC_PROCESS [1140]

Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent

14

8 e⁻⁶4.6 e⁻²

				A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of cytoskeletal structures. [GOC:dph, GOC:jl, GOC:mah]	16	1.18 e ⁻⁵	4.6 e ⁻²
				Binding to a ribonucleotide, any compound consisting of a ribonucleoside that is esterified with (ortho)phosphate or an oligophosphate at any hydroxyl group on the ribose moiety. [GOC:mah]	18	1.39 e ⁻⁵	2.45 e ⁻²
				Binding to a calcium ion (Ca ²⁺). [GOC:ai]	10	5.49 e ⁻⁵	4.84 e ⁻²
12	290			Enables the directed movement of substances (such as macromolecules, small molecules, ions) into, out of or within a cell, or between cells. [GOC:ai, GOC:dgf]	32	3.07 e ⁻¹⁰	5.41 e ⁻⁷
				Binding to a kinase, any enzyme that catalyzes the transfer of a phosphate group. [GOC:jl]	24	2.44 e ⁻⁹	2.15 e ⁻⁶

GOMF_ION_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORTER_ACTIVITY [859]	Enables the transfer of an ion from one side of a membrane to the other.	24	1.48 e ⁻⁸	8.69 e ⁻⁶
GOMF_INORGANIC_MOLECULAR_ENTITY_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORTER_ACTIVITY [748]	Enables the transfer of an inorganic molecular entity from the outside of a cell to the inside of the cell	20	4.86 e ⁻⁷	2.14 e ⁻⁴
GOMF_LIPID_BINDING [842]	Binding to a lipid. [GOC:ai]	21	7.68 e ⁻⁷	2.71 e ⁻⁴
GOMF_TRANSCRIPTION_REGULATOR_ACTIVITY [1927]	A molecular function that controls the rate, timing and/or magnitude of gene transcription. The function of transcriptional regulators is to modulate gene expression at the transcription step so that they are expressed in the right cell at the right time and in the right amount throughout the life of the cell and the organism. Genes are transcriptional units, and include bacterial operons. [GOC:pg, GOC:txnOH-2018, Wikipedia:Transcription_factor]	32	7.63 e ⁻⁶	2.24 e ⁻³
GOMF_NUCLEOSIDE_TRIPHOSPHATASE_REGULATOR_ACTIVITY [489]	Binds to and modulates the activity of an NTPase. [GOC:dph, GOC:tb]	14	1.22 e ⁻⁵	2.82 e ⁻³

GOMF_CELL_ADHESION_MOLECULE_BINDING [559]	Binding to a cell adhesion molecule. [GOC:ai]	15	1.28 e ⁻⁵	2.82 e ⁻³
GOMF_CATION_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORTER_ACTIVITY [657]	Enables the transfer of cation from one side of a membrane to the other.	16	2.16 e ⁻⁵	4.24 e ⁻³
GOMF_RIBONUCLEOTIDE_BINDING [1904]	Binding to a ribonucleotide, any compound consisting of a ribonucleoside that is esterified with (ortho)phosphate or an oligophosphate at any hydroxyl group on the ribose moiety. [GOC:mah]	30	3.96 e ⁻⁵	5.95 e ⁻³
GOMF_PHOSPHOLIPID_BINDING [476]	Binding to a phospholipid, a class of lipids containing phosphoric acid as a mono- or diester. [ISBN:0198506732]	13	4.05 e ⁻⁵	5.95 e ⁻³
GOMF_PHOSPHATIDYLINOSITOL_TRANSFER_ACTIVITY [10]	Removes phosphatidylinositol from a membrane or a monolayer	3	4.05 e ⁻⁵	5.95 e ⁻³
GOMF_PASSIVE_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORTER_ACTIVITY [499]	Enables the transfer of a single solute from one side of a membrane to the	13	6.52 e ⁻⁵	8.84 e ⁻³
GOMF_PHOSPHORIC_ESTER_HYDROLASE_ACTIVITY [371]	Catalysis of the reaction: RPO-R' + H ₂ O = RPOOH + R'H. This reaction is the	11	7.67 e ⁻⁵	9.66 e ⁻³
GOMF_ENZYME_REGULATOR_ACTIVITY [1253]	Binds to and modulates the activity of an enzyme. [GOC:dph, GOC:mah, GOC:tb]	22	9.75 e ⁻⁵	1.15 e ⁻²

GOMF_LIPID_PHOSPHATASE_ACTIVITY [14]	Catalysis of the reaction: a phospholipid + H2O = a lipid + phosphate. [GOC:jl]	3	1.2 e ⁻⁴	1.32 e ⁻²
GOMF_CADHERIN_BINDING [334]	Binding to cadherin, a type I membrane protein involved in cell adhesion. [GOC:bf]	10	1.49 e ⁻⁴	1.55 e ⁻²
GOMF_GTPASE_ACTIVATOR_ACTIVITY [276]	Binds to and increases the activity of a GTPase, an enzyme that catalyzes the hydrolysis of GTP. [GOC:mah]	9	1.7 e ⁻⁴	1.66 e ⁻²
GOMF_CIS_REGULATORY_REGION_SEQUENCE_SP_SPECIFIC_DNA_BINDING [1232]	Binding to a specific upstream regulatory DNA sequence (transcription)	21	2.1 e ⁻⁴	1.94 e ⁻²
GOMF_ENZYME_ACTIVATOR_ACTIVITY [566]	Binds to and increases the activity of an enzyme. [GOC:dph, GOC:mah, GOC:tb]	13	2.25 e ⁻⁴	1.98 e ⁻²
GOMF_ADENYL_NUCLEOTIDE_BINDING [1552]	Binding to an adenylnucleotide, an adenosine esterified with (ortho)phosphate. [ISBN:0198506732]	24	3.14 e ⁻⁴	2.64 e ⁻²
GOMF_BETA_CATENIN_BINDING [88]	Binding to a catenin beta subunit. [GOC:bf]	5	4.14 e ⁻⁴	3.32 e ⁻²

GOMF_SEQUENCE_SPECIFIC_DNA_BINDING [1686]	Binding to DNA of a specific nucleotide composition, e.g. GC-rich DNA binding, or with a specific sequence motif or type of DNA e.g. promotor binding or rDNA binding. [GOC:jl]	25	4.38 e ⁻⁴	3.36 e ⁻²
GOMF_PROTEIN_TYROSINE_KINASE_ACTIVITY [144]	Catalysis of the reaction: ATP + a protein tyrosine = ADP + protein tyrosine phosphate. [RHEA:10596]	6	5.85 e ⁻⁴	4.3 e ⁻²
GOBP_NEUROGENESIS [1669]	Generation of cells within the nervous system. [GO_REF:0000021, GOC:cls, GOC:curators, GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:jid]	43	2.61 e ⁻¹³	2.03 e ⁻⁹

GOBP_CELL_CELL_SIGNALING [1679]	<p>Any process that mediates the transfer of information from one cell to another. This process includes signal transduction in the receiving cell and, where applicable, release of a ligand and any processes that actively facilitate its transport and presentation to the receiving cell. Examples include signaling via soluble ligands, via cell adhesion molecules and via gap junctions. [GOC:dos, GOC:mah]</p>	41	5.41 e ⁻¹²	2.1 e ⁻⁸
GOBP_CELL_PROJECTION_ORGANIZATION [1576]	<p>A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of a prolongation or process extending from a cell, e.g. a flagellum or axon. [GOC:j], GOC:mah, http://www.cogsci.princeton.edu/~wn/]</p>	38	5.07 e ⁻¹¹	1.31 e ⁻⁷

GOBP_TISSUE_DEVELOPMENT [1998]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a tissue over time, from its formation to the mature structure. [ISBN:0471245208]	43	8.74×10^{-11}	1.7×10^{-7}
GOBP_GENERATION_OF_NEURONS [1453]	The process in which nerve cells are generated. This includes the production of neuroblasts and their differentiation into neurons. [GOC:nln]	35	3.23×10^{-10}	5.01×10^{-7}
GOBP_CELL_ADHESION [1541]	The attachment of a cell, either to another cell or to an underlying substrate such as the extracellular matrix, via cell adhesion molecules. [GOC:hb, GOC:pf]	35	1.5×10^{-9}	1.94×10^{-6}
GOBP_ION_TRANSPORT [1587]	The directed movement of charged atoms or small charged molecules into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore. [GOC:ai]	35	3.18×10^{-9}	3.35×10^{-6}

GOBP_EPITHELIUM_DEVELOPMENT [1211]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of an epithelium over time, from its formation to the mature structure. An epithelium is a tissue that covers the internal or external surfaces of an anatomical structure. [GOC:dph, GOC:mtg_lung]	30	3.46 e ⁻⁹	3.35 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CELL_PROJECTION_ORG ORGANIZATION [683]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of a process	22	4.87 e ⁻⁹	4.2 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CELL_DIFFERENTIATIO TION [1641]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of cell	35	7.42 e ⁻⁹	5.68 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_NEURON_DEVELOPMENT [1113]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a neuron over time, from initial commitment of the cell to a specific fate, to the fully functional differentiated cell. [GOC:dph]	28	8.55 e ⁻⁹	5.68 e ⁻⁶

GOBP_LIPID_METABOLIC_PROCESS [1415]	The chemical reactions and pathways involving lipids, compounds soluble in an organic solvent but not, or sparingly, in an aqueous solvent. Includes fatty acids; neutral fats, other fatty-acid esters, and soaps; long-chain (fatty) alcohols and waxes; sphingoids and other long-chain bases; glycolipids, phospholipids and sphingolipids; and carotenes, polyprenols, sterols, terpenes and other isoprenoids. [GOC:ma]	32	8.84 e ⁻⁹	5.68 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORT [1577]	The process in which a solute is transported across a lipid bilayer, from one side of a membrane to the other. [GOC:dph, GOC:jid] Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent of a signaling process.	34	9.52 e ⁻⁹	5.68 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_SIGNALING [1431]	[GOC:mtg_signal] Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of addition	32	1.15 e ⁻⁸	6.38 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_PROTEIN_PHOSPHORYLATION [1124]		27	4.11 e ⁻⁸	2.13 e ⁻⁵

GOBP_CELL_SURFACE_RECEPTOR_SIGNALING_P	Any cell surface receptor signaling pathway that is involved in cell-cell signaling.			
G_PATHWAY_INVOLVED_IN_CELL_CELL_SIGNALING [583]	[GO_REF:0000060,	19	4.66 e ⁻⁸	2.26 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_RESPONSE_T E_TO_STIMULUS [1707]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent	34	6.41 e ⁻⁸	2.93 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_PROTEIN_MODIFICATIO TION_PROCESS [1584]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the	32	1.18 e ⁻⁷	5.07 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_PHOSPHORUS_METABOLI OLIC_PROCESS [1427]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the	30	1.29 e ⁻⁷	5.29 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_CELL_PROJE OJECTION_ORGANIZATION [193]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent	11	1.52 e ⁻⁷	5.62 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_NEURON_PROJECTION_D N_DEVELOPMENT [446]	Any process that modulates the rate, frequency or extent of	16	1.52 e ⁻⁷	5.62 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_PHOSPHORYLATION [1862]	The process of introducing a phosphate group into a molecule, usually with the formation of a phosphoric ester, a phosphoric anhydride or a phosphoric amide. [ISBN:0198506732]	35	1.62 e ⁻⁷	5.72 e ⁻⁵

GOBP_VESICLE_MEDIATED_TRANSPORT [1620]	<p>A cellular transport process in which transported substances are moved in membrane-bounded vesicles; transported substances are enclosed in the vesicle lumen or located in the vesicle membrane. The process begins with a step that directs a substance to the forming vesicle, and includes vesicle budding and coating. Vesicles are then targeted to, and fuse with, an acceptor membrane. [GOC:ai, GOC:mah, ISBN:08789310662000]</p>	32	1.94 e ⁻⁷	6.24 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_ANATOMICAL_STRUCTURE_MORPHOGENESIS [988]	<p>Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of</p>	24	1.97 e ⁻⁷	6.24 e ⁻⁵

GOBP_CELL_JUNCTION_ORGANIZATION [707]	<p>A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of a cell junction. A cell junction is a specialized region of connection between two cells or between a cell and the extracellular matrix.</p> <p>[GOC:dph, GOC:jl, GOC:mah]</p>	20	2.01×10^{-7}	6.24×10^{-5}
GOBP_TUBE_DEVELOPMENT [1155]	<p>The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a tube over time, from its initial formation to a mature structure. Epithelial and endothelial tubes transport gases, liquids and cells from one site to another and form the basic structure of many organs and tissues including lung and trachea, kidney, the mammary gland, the vascular system and the gastrointestinal and urinary-genital tracts.</p> <p>[PMID:12526790]</p>	26	2.59×10^{-7}	7.73×10^{-5}

GOBP_CELLULAR_LIPID_METABOLIC_PROCESS [1014]	The chemical reactions and pathways involving lipids, as carried out by individual cells. [GOC:jl]	24	3.13 e ⁻⁷	8.84 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_ION_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORT [1169]	A process in which an ion is transported across a membrane. [GOC:mah]	26	3.25 e ⁻⁷	8.84 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_ENZYME_LINKED_RECEPTOR_PROTEIN_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [1017]	The series of molecular signals initiated by an extracellular ligand binding	24	3.3 e ⁻⁷	8.84 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CYTOSKELETON_ORGANIZATION [540]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the	17	3.89 e ⁻⁷	1.01 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_OXYGEN_CONTAINING_COMPOUND [1695]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in	32	5.23 e ⁻⁷	1.31 e ⁻⁴
	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the directed movement of substances (such as macromolecules, small molecules, ions) into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore.			
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_TRANSPORT [1793]	[GOC:ai]	33	6.02 e ⁻⁷	1.46 e ⁻⁴

GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_ENDOGENOUS_STIMULUS [1643]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a stimulus arising within the organism. [GOC:sm]	31	8.07 e ⁻⁷	1.88 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_CELL_ACTIVATION [1150]	A change in the morphology or behavior of a cell resulting from exposure to an activating factor such as a cellular or soluble ligand. [GOC:mgi_curators]	25	8.36 e ⁻⁷	1.88 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_ORGANONITROGEN_COMPOUND_BIOSYNTHETIC_PROCESS [1821]	The chemical reactions and pathways resulting in the formation of	33	8.46 e ⁻⁷	1.88 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_DEVELOPMENTAL_PROCESS [1002]	Any process that stops, prevents or reduces the rate or extent of	23	9.39 e ⁻⁷	2.02 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_TRANSMEMBRANE_RECEPTOR_PROTEIN_TYROSINE_KINASE_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [645]	The series of molecular signals initiated by an extracellular ligand binding to a receptor on the	18	1 e ⁻⁶	2.06 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_CERAMIDE_METABOLIC_PROCESS [107]	The chemical reactions and pathways involving ceramides, any N-acylated sphingoid. [ISBN:0198547684]	8	1.01 e ⁻⁶	2.06 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_ANATOMICAL_STRUCTURE_FORMATION_IN	The developmental process pertaining to the initial			

_INVOLVED_IN_MORPHOGENESIS [1244]	formation of an anatomical	26	1.04 e ⁻⁶	2.07 e ⁻⁴
	Any process that mediates the transfer of information from one cell to another, mediated by a wnt family protein ligand. This process includes wnt signal transduction in the receiving cell, release of wnt ligand from a secreting cell as well as any processes that actively facilitate wnt transport and presentation to receptor on the receiving cell.			
GOBP_CELL_CELL_SIGNALING_BY_WNT [459]	[GOC:dos]	15	1.2 e ⁻⁶	2.32 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_ACTIN_FILAMENT_BASEASED_PROCESS [406]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of any	14	1.46 e ⁻⁶	2.76 e ⁻⁴
	The chemical reactions and pathways resulting in the formation of lipids, compounds soluble in an organic solvent but not, or sparingly, in an aqueous solvent. [GOC:go_curators]			
GOBP_LIPID_BIOSYNTHETIC_PROCESS [734]		19	1.52 e ⁻⁶	2.77 e ⁻⁴

GOBP_ENDOMEMBRANE_SYSTEM_ORGANIZATION [597]	A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of the endomembrane system. [GOC:mah, GOC:sm]	17	1.53 e ⁻⁶	2.77 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_LOCOMOTION [1446]	Self-propelled movement of a cell or organism from one location to another. [GOC:dgh]	28	1.73 e ⁻⁶	3.06 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_PROTEIN_KINASE_ACTIVITY [676]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of protein	18	1.94 e ⁻⁶	3.35 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_ORGANELLE_ORGANIZATION [1208]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of a process	25	2.01 e ⁻⁶	3.39 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_BIOLOGICAL_PROCESS_INVOLVED_IN_SYMBIOTIC_INTERACTION [308]	A process carried out by gene products in an organism that enable the	12	2.38 e ⁻⁶	3.89 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_MULTICELLULAR_ORGANISMAL_DEVELOPMENT [1471]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of	28	2.4 e ⁻⁶	3.89 e ⁻⁴

GOBP_CANONICAL_WNT_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [310]	<p>The series of molecular signals initiated by binding of a Wnt protein to a frizzled family receptor on the surface of the target cell, followed by propagation of the signal via beta-catenin, and ending with a change in transcription of target genes. In this pathway, the activated receptor signals via downstream effectors that result in the inhibition of beta-catenin phosphorylation, thereby preventing degradation of beta-catenin. Stabilized beta-catenin can then accumulate and travel to the nucleus to trigger changes in transcription of target genes. [GOC:bf, GOC:dph, PMID:11532397, PMID:19619488]</p>	12	2.55×10^{-6}	4.04×10^{-4}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_TRANSFERASE_ACTIVITIVITY [918]	<p>Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of</p>	21	2.98×10^{-6}	4.62×10^{-4}
REACTOME_SIGNALING_BY_RECEPTOR_TYROSIN KINASES [519]	<p>Signaling by Receptor Tyrosine Kinases</p>	19	7.38×10^{-9}	2.25×10^{-5}

REACTOME_METABOLISM_OF_LIPIDS [742]	Metabolism of lipids	22	2.13×10^{-8}	3.25×10^{-5}
REACTOME_SPHINGOLIPID_METABOLISM [90]	Sphingolipid metabolism	8	2.66×10^{-7}	2.71×10^{-4}
REACTOME_CDC42_GTPASE_CYCLE [155]	CDC42 GTPase cycle	9	1.78×10^{-6}	1.36×10^{-3}
REACTOME_RHO_GTPASE_CYCLE [450]	RHO GTPase cycle	14	4.78×10^{-6}	2.92×10^{-3}
KEGG_SPHINGOLIPID_METABOLISM [39]	Sphingolipid metabolism	5	8.07×10^{-6}	4.1×10^{-3}
WP_MALIGNANT_PLEURAL_MESOTHELIOMA [439]	Malignant pleural mesothelioma	13	1.76×10^{-5}	7.43×10^{-3}
WP_SPHINGOLIPID_METABOLISM_OVERVIEW [23]	Sphingolipid metabolism overview	4	1.95×10^{-5}	7.43×10^{-3}
WP_SPHINGOLIPID_METABOLISM_INTEGRATED_PATHWAY [26]	Sphingolipid metabolism: integrated pathway	4	3.24×10^{-5}	1.1×10^{-2}
REACTOME_NEUTROPHIL_DEGRANULATION [479]	Neutrophil degranulation	13	4.31×10^{-5}	1.31×10^{-2}
REACTOME_SIGNALING_BY_RHO_GTPASES_MIRO_IRO_GTPASES_AND_RHOBTB3 [721]	Signaling by Rho GTPases, Miro GTPases and RHOBTB3	16	6.51×10^{-5}	1.8×10^{-2}
WP_WNT_SIGNALING_PATHWAY_AND_PLURIPOTENCY [101]	Wnt signaling pathway and pluripotency	6	8.57×10^{-5}	2.18×10^{-2}
BIOCARTA_ACH_PATHWAY [14]	Role of nicotinic acetylcholine receptors in the regulation of apoptosis	3	1.2×10^{-4}	2.82×10^{-2}
WP_EFFECT_OF_PROGERIN_ON_GENES_INVOLVED_IN_HUTCHINSONGILFORD_PROGERIA_SYNDROME [37]	Effect of progerin on genes involved in Hutchinson-Gilford progeria syndrome	4	1.35×10^{-4}	2.93×10^{-2}
PID_AVB3_INTEGRIN_PATHWAY [74]	Integrins in angiogenesis	5	1.85×10^{-4}	3.75×10^{-2}
KEGG_LYSOSOME [121]	Lysosome	6	2.31×10^{-4}	4.19×10^{-2}

		REACTOME_TRANSPORT_OF_SMALL_MOLECULES [728]	Transport of small molecules	15	2.44 e ⁻⁴	4.19 e ⁻²
		REACTOME_CYTOKINE_SIGNALING_IN_IMMUNE_SYSTEM [729]	Cytokine Signaling in Immune system	15	2.47 e ⁻⁴	4.19 e ⁻²
		REACTOME_GLYCOSPHINGOLIPID_METABOLISM [45]	Glycosphingolipid metabolism	4	2.9 e ⁻⁴	4.22 e ⁻²
		REACTOME_SPHINGOLIPID_DE_NOVO_BIOSYNTHESIS [45]	Sphingolipid de novo biosynthesis	4	2.9 e ⁻⁴	4.22 e ⁻²
		WP_NEPHROTIC_SYNDROME [45]	Nephrotic syndrome	4	2.9 e ⁻⁴	4.22 e ⁻²
13	158	KEGG_THYROID_CANCER [29]	Thyroid cancer	4	4.67 e ⁻⁶	7.57 e ⁻³
		WP_NONSMALL_CELL_LUNG_CANCER [72]	Non-small cell lung cancer	5	9.05 e ⁻⁶	7.57 e ⁻³
		KEGG_ADHERENS_JUNCTION [73]	Adherens junction	5	9.68 e ⁻⁶	7.57 e ⁻³
		KEGG_CELL_ADHESION_MOLECULES_CAMS [133]	Cell adhesion molecules (CAMs)	6	1.36 e ⁻⁵	7.57 e ⁻³
		KEGG_SULFUR_METABOLISM [13]	Sulfur metabolism	3	1.56 e ⁻⁵	7.57 e ⁻³
		WP_MAMMARY_GLAND_DEVELOPMENT_PATHWAY_PUBERTY_STAGE_2_OF_4 [13]	Mammary gland development pathway - Puberty (Stage 2 of 4)	3	1.56 e ⁻⁵	7.57 e ⁻³
		WP_BLADDER_CANCER [40]	Bladder cancer	4	1.74 e ⁻⁵	7.57 e ⁻³
		KEGG_BLADDER_CANCER [42]	Bladder cancer	4	2.12 e ⁻⁵	8.07 e ⁻³
		KEGG_PATHWAYS_IN_CANCER [325]	Pathways in cancer	8	4.1 e ⁻⁵	1.39 e ⁻²
		KEGG_ENDOMETRIAL_CANCER [52]	Endometrial cancer	4	4.97 e ⁻⁵	1.52 e ⁻²
		KEGG_NON_SMALL_CELL_LUNG_CANCER [54]	Non-small cell lung cancer	4	5.77 e ⁻⁵	1.6 e ⁻²
		WP_PREIMPLANTATION_EMBRYO [59]	Pre-implantation embryo	4	8.18 e ⁻⁵	1.9 e ⁻²
		WP_PI3KAKTMTOR_VITAMIN_D3_SIGNALING [22]	PI3K/AKT/mTOR - vitamin D3 signaling	3	8.19 e ⁻⁵	1.9 e ⁻²
		WP_TYROBP_CAUSAL_NETWORK_IN_MICROGLIA [60]	TYROBP causal network in microglia	4	8.74 e ⁻⁵	1.9 e ⁻²

WP_ENDOMETRIAL_CANCER [63]	Endometrial cancer	4	1.06 e ⁻⁴	2.02 e ⁻²
BIOCARTA_VDR_PATHWAY [24]	Control of Gene Expression by Vitamin D Receptor	3	1.07 e ⁻⁴	2.02 e ⁻²
PID_ERA_GENOMIC_PATHWAY [64]	Validated nuclear estrogen receptor alpha network RXR and RAR heterodimerization with other nuclear receptor	4	1.13 e ⁻⁴	2.02 e ⁻²
PID_RXR_VDR_PATHWAY [26]		3	1.37 e ⁻⁴	2.31 e ⁻²
REACTOME_CIRCADIAN_CLOCK [70]	Circadian Clock	4	1.59 e ⁻⁴	2.44 e ⁻²
WP_ADIPOGENESIS [131]	Adipogenesis	5	1.6 e ⁻⁴	2.44 e ⁻²
KEGG_ARRHYTHMOGENIC_RIGHT_VENTRICULAR_AR_CARDIOMYOPATHY_ARVC [74]	Arrhythmogenic right ventricular cardiomyopathy (ARVC)	4	1.98 e ⁻⁴	2.68 e ⁻²
WP_ARRHYTHMOGENIC_RIGHT_VENTRICULAR_CA_CARDIOMYOPATHY [75]	Arrhythmogenic right ventricular cardiomyopathy	4	2.08 e ⁻⁴	2.68 e ⁻²
PID_RETINOIC_ACID_PATHWAY [30]	Retinoic acid receptors-mediated signaling	3	2.11 e ⁻⁴	2.68 e ⁻²
REACTOME_SUMOYLATION_OF_INTRACELLULAR_AR_RECEPTORS [30]	SUMOylation of intracellular receptors	3	2.11 e ⁻⁴	2.68 e ⁻²
PID_SMAD2_3NUCLEAR_PATHWAY [82]	Regulation of nuclear SMAD2/3 signaling	4	2.94 e ⁻⁴	3.47 e ⁻²
	Nuclear receptors coordinate the activities of chromatin remodeling complexes and coactivators to facilitate initiation of transcription in carcinoma cells			
BIOCARTA_RARRXR_PATHWAY [7]		2	3.06 e ⁻⁴	3.47 e ⁻²
KEGG_HYPERTROPHIC_CARDIOMYOPATHY_HCM [83]	Hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCM)	4	3.07 e ⁻⁴	3.47 e ⁻²

PID_CMYB_PATHWAY [84]	C-MYB transcription factor network	4	3.22 e ⁻⁴	3.51 e ⁻²
WP_BREAST_CANCER_PATHWAY [154]	Breast cancer pathway	5	3.39 e ⁻⁴	3.57 e ⁻²
REACTOME_PROTEIN_PROTEIN_INTERACTIONS_NS_AT_SYNAPSES [87]	Protein-protein interactions at synapses	4	3.68 e ⁻⁴	3.74 e ⁻²
BIOCARTA_PPARG_PATHWAY [8]	Role of PPAR-gamma Coactivators in Obesity and Thermogenesis	2	4.07 e ⁻⁴	4 e ⁻²
WP_NUCLEAR_RECEPTORS [38]	Nuclear receptors	3	4.29 e ⁻⁴	4.08 e ⁻²
REACTOME_POST_TRANSLATIONAL_PROTEIN_MODIFICATION [1438]	Post-translational protein modification	15	4.71 e ⁻⁴	4.35 e ⁻²
REACTOME_NR1H2_NR1H3_REGULATE_GENE_EXPRESSION_TO_CONTROL_BILE_ACID_HOMEOSTASIS [9]	NR1H2 & NR1H3 regulate gene expression to control bile acid homeostasis	2	5.22 e ⁻⁴	4.68 e ⁻²
GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_ENDOGENOUS_STIMULUS [1643]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a stimulus arising within the organism. [GOC:sm]	25	4.65 e ⁻⁹	3.61 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_CELLULAR_RESPONSE_TO_ENDOGENOUS_STIMULUS [1394]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell (in terms of	22	2.28 e ⁻⁸	8.84 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CELL_POPULATION_PROLIFERATION [1779]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of cell	24	9.37 e ⁻⁸	2.02 e ⁻⁴

GOBP_CELL_JUNCTION_ORGANIZATION [707]	A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of a cell junction. A cell junction is a specialized region of connection between two cells or between a cell and the extracellular matrix. [GOC:dph, GOC:jl, GOC:mah]	15	1.15 e ⁻⁷	2.02 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_CELL_ADHESION [1541]	The attachment of a cell, either to another cell or to an underlying substrate such as the extracellular matrix, via cell adhesion molecules. [GOC:hb, GOC:pf]	22	1.3 e ⁻⁷	2.02 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_ENZYME_LINKED_RECEPTOR_PROTEIN_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [1017]	The series of molecular signals initiated by an extracellular ligand binding	17	4.62 e ⁻⁷	5.39 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_ESTABLISHMENT_OF_PROTEIN_LOCALIZATION [1668]	The directed movement of a protein to a specific location. [GOC:bf]	22	4.97 e ⁻⁷	5.39 e ⁻⁴

GOBP_CELL_CELL_SIGNALING [1679]	<p>Any process that mediates the transfer of information from one cell to another. This process includes signal transduction in the receiving cell and, where applicable, release of a ligand and any processes that actively facilitate its transport and presentation to the receiving cell. Examples include signaling via soluble ligands, via cell adhesion molecules and via gap junctions. [GOC:dos, GOC:mah]</p>	22	5.55×10^{-7}	5.39×10^{-4}
GOBP_CELL_CELL_ADHESION [960]	<p>The attachment of one cell to another cell via adhesion molecules. [GOC:dos]</p>	15	5.12×10^{-6}	4.42×10^{-3}
GOBP_SYNAPSE_ORGANIZATION [432]	<p>A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of a synapse, the junction between a neuron and a target (neuron, muscle, or secretory cell). [GOC:ai, GOC:pr]</p>	10	7.58×10^{-6}	5.88×10^{-3}

GOBP_GLAND_DEVELOPMENT [442]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a gland over time, from its formation to the mature structure. A gland is an organ specialised for secretion. [GOC:jid]	10	9.24×10^{-6}	6.52×10^{-3}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_MACROMOLECULE_BIOSYNTHETIC_PROCESS [1908]	Any process that increases the rate, frequency or extent of the chemical Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of attachment of a cell to another cell or to the extracellular matrix. [GOC:mah]	21	1.51×10^{-5}	9.48×10^{-3}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CELL_ADHESION [805]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of cell	19	2×10^{-5}	1.04×10^{-2}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CELL_DIFFERENTIATION [1641]	The controlled release of a substance by a cell or a tissue. [GOC:ai]	14	2.14×10^{-5}	1.04×10^{-2}
GOBP_SECRETION [954]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell (in terms of	11	2.22×10^{-5}	1.04×10^{-2}
GOBP_CELLULAR_RESPONSE_TO_HORMONE_STIMULUS [597]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell (in terms of	16	2.28×10^{-5}	1.04×10^{-2}
GOBP_CELLULAR_RESPONSE_TO_OXYGEN_CONTAINING_COMPOUND [1226]				

GOBP_NEUROGENESIS [1669]	Generation of cells within the nervous system. [GO_REF:0000021, GOC:cls, GOC:curators, GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:jid]	19	2.51 e ⁻⁵	1.08 e ⁻²
GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_OXYGEN_CONTAINING_COMPOUND [1695]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a hormone stimulus. [GOC:jl]	19	3.1 e ⁻⁵	1.24 e ⁻²
GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_HORMONE [863]	The process in which the anatomical structures of branches in an epithelial	13	3.26 e ⁻⁵	1.24 e ⁻²
GOBP_BRANCHING_MORPHOGENESIS_OF_AN_EPITHELIAL_TUBE [157]	A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the	6	3.47 e ⁻⁵	1.24 e ⁻²
GOBP_NEUROMUSCULAR_JUNCTION_DEVELOPMENT [48]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent	4	3.61 e ⁻⁵	1.24 e ⁻²
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_RNA_METABOLIC_PROCESS [1419]	A process that results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or	17	3.68 e ⁻⁵	1.24 e ⁻²
GOBP_ACTIN_FILAMENT_BUNDLE_ORGANIZATION [166]		6	4.74 e ⁻⁵	1.53 e ⁻²

GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_TRANSPORT [903]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of the directed movement of substances (such as macromolecules, small molecules, ions) into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore. [GOC:ai]	13	5.17 e ⁻⁵	1.61 e ⁻²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_MULTICELLULAR_ORGANISMAL_DEVELOPMENT [1471]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of A homeostatic process involved in the maintenance of an internal steady state of a carbohydrate within an organism or cell.	17	5.73 e ⁻⁵	1.65 e ⁻²
GOBP_CARBOHYDRATE_HOMEOSTASIS [251]	[GOC:mah]	7	5.75 e ⁻⁵	1.65 e ⁻²
GOBP_PEPTIDE_ANTIGEN_ASSEMBLY_WITH_MHC_MHC_PROTEIN_COMPLEX [20]	The binding of a peptide to the antigen binding groove of an MHC protein	3	6.09 e ⁻⁵	1.65 e ⁻²
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_CELL_POPULATION_PROLIFERATION [791]	Any process that stops, prevents or reduces the rate or extent of cell	12	6.18 e ⁻⁵	1.65 e ⁻²

GOBP_STRESS_FIBER_ASSEMBLY [111]	The aggregation, arrangement and bonding together of a set of components to form a stress fiber. A stress fiber is a contractile actin filament bundle that consists of short actin filaments with alternating polarity. [GOC:go_curators, GOC:mah, PMID:16651381]	5	7.34 e ⁻⁵	1.9 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_RNA_METABOLIC_PROCESS [1835]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of the	19	8.9 e ⁻⁵	2.12 e ⁻²
GOBP_TISSUE_DEVELOPMENT [1998]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a tissue over time, from its formation to the mature structure. [ISBN:0471245208]	20	9.08 e ⁻⁵	2.12 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_TRANSCRIPTION_BY_RNA_POLYMERASE_II [1235]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of	15	9.27 e ⁻⁵	2.12 e ⁻²

GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_INSULIN [271]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of an insulin stimulus. Insulin is a polypeptide hormone produced by the islets of Langerhans of the pancreas in mammals, and by the homologous organs of other organisms. [GOC:mah, ISBN:0198506732]	7	9.28 e ⁻⁵	2.12 e ⁻²
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_BIOSYNTHETIC_PROCESS [1705]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the rate of the chemical	18	1.08 e ⁻⁴	2.35 e ⁻²
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_NUCLEOBASE	Any cellular process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent of the chemical reactions and pathways	17	1.09 e ⁻⁴	2.35 e ⁻²
ASE_CONTAINING_COMPOUND_METABOLIC_PROCESS [1551]	The process in which an antigen-presenting cell expresses peptide antigen	4	1.13 e ⁻⁴	2.36 e ⁻²
GOBP_ANTIGEN_PROCESSING_AND_PRESENTATION_OF_PEPTIDE_ANTIGEN [64]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of cell	9	1.17 e ⁻⁴	2.39 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_CELL_ADHESION [484]				

GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CELL_CELL_ADHESION [492]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of attachment of a cell to another cell. [GOC:isa_complete]	9	1.33 e ⁻⁴	2.64 e ⁻²
GOBP_ERBB_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [127]	The series of molecular signals initiated by binding of a ligand to a member of the ERBB family of receptor tyrosine kinases on the surface of a cell, and ending with the regulation of a downstream cellular process, e.g. transcription. [GOC:jc, PMID:16460914, Wikipedia:ErbB]	5	1.39 e ⁻⁴	2.69 e ⁻²
GOBP_MORPHOGENESIS_OF_A_BRANCHING_STRUCTURE [203]	The process in which the anatomical structures of branches are generated	6	1.44 e ⁻⁴	2.71 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_VITAMIN_D_D_RECEPTOR_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [5]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of vitamin D	2	1.46 e ⁻⁴	2.71 e ⁻²
GOBP_GENERATION_OF_NEURONS [1453]	The process in which nerve cells are generated. This includes the production of neuroblasts and their differentiation into neurons. [GOC:nln]	16	1.66 e ⁻⁴	2.98 e ⁻²

GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_EPIDERMAL_CELL_DIFFERENTIATION [28]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of epidermal	3	1.71 e ⁻⁴	2.98 e ⁻²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_LYMPHOCYTE_DIFFERENTIATION [210]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of	6	1.73 e ⁻⁴	2.98 e ⁻²
GOBP_ENDOCRINE_SYSTEM_DEVELOPMENT [135]	Progression of the endocrine system over time, from its formation to a mature structure. The endocrine system is a system of hormones and ductless glands, where the glands release hormones directly into the blood, lymph or other intercellular fluid, and the hormones circulate within the body to affect distant organs. The major glands that make up the human endocrine system are the hypothalamus, pituitary, thyroid, parathyroids, adrenals, pineal body, and the reproductive glands which include the ovaries and testes. [GOC:bf, Wikipedia:Development_of_the_endocrine_system]	5	1.84 e ⁻⁴	3.11 e ⁻²

GOBP_SYNAPTIC_SIGNALING [761]	Cell-cell signaling to, from or within a synapse. [GOC:dos]	11	1.91 e ⁻⁴	3.15 e ⁻²
	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the directed movement of substances (such as macromolecules, small molecules, ions) into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore.			
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_TRANSPORT [1793]	[GOC:ai]	18	2.01 e ⁻⁴	3.24 e ⁻²
	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of the mammary gland over time, from its formation to the mature structure. The mammary gland is a large compound sebaceous gland that in female mammals is modified to secrete milk. Its development starts with the formation of the mammary line and ends as the mature gland cycles between nursing and weaning stages.			
GOBP_MAMMARY_GLAND_DEVELOPMENT [138]	[PMID:9576833]	5	2.04 e ⁻⁴	3.24 e ⁻²

GOBP_REGULATION_OF_GLUCOSE_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORT [77]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of glucose Binding to a kinase, any enzyme that catalyzes the transfer of a phosphate group. [GOC:jl]	4	2.31×10^{-4}	3.58×10^{-2}
GOMF_KINASE_BINDING [782]	Binding to a transcription factor, a protein required to initiate or regulate transcription.	15	4.14×10^{-7}	7.31×10^{-4}
GOMF_TRANSCRIPTION_FACTOR_BINDING [597]	[ISBN:0198506732] Binding to a transcription coregulator, a protein involved in regulation of transcription via protein-protein interactions with transcription factors and other transcription regulatory proteins. Cofactors do not bind DNA directly, but rather mediate protein-protein interactions between regulatory transcription factors and the basal transcription machinery.	12	3.89×10^{-6}	2.55×10^{-3}
GOMF_TRANSCRIPTION_COREGULATOR_BINDING [109]	[GOC:krc] Binding to a sequence-specific DNA binding RNA polymerase II transcription factor, any of the factors	6	4.34×10^{-6}	2.55×10^{-3}
GOMF_RNA_POLYMERASE_II_SPECIFIC_DNA_BINDING_TRANSCRIPTION_FACTOR_BINDING [350]	Binding to a DNA-binding transcription factor, a	9	9.53×10^{-6}	4.2×10^{-3}
GOMF_DNA_BINDING_TRANSCRIPTION_FACTOR_				

OR_BINDING [476]	protein that interacts with	10	1.75×10^{-5}	5.14×10^{-3}
	Binding to a nuclear receptor protein. Nuclear receptor proteins are DNA-binding transcription factors which are regulated by binding to a ligand. [PMID:7776974]			
GOMF_NUCLEAR_RECEPTOR_BINDING [139]		6	1.75×10^{-5}	5.14×10^{-3}
	Catalysis of the transfer of a sulfate group from 3'-phosphoadenosine 5'-phosphosulfate to the hydroxyl group of an acceptor, producing the sulfated derivative and 3'-phosphoadenosine 5'-phosphate. [GOC:curators]			
GOMF_SULFOTRANSFERASE_ACTIVITY [52]		4	4.97×10^{-5}	1.25×10^{-2}
GOMF_TRANSFERASE_ACTIVITY_TRANSFERRING_SULPHUR_CONTAINING_GROUPS [69]	Catalysis of the transfer of a sulfur-containing group from one compound	4	1.51×10^{-4}	3.32×10^{-2}

14

270

GOMF_TRANSCRIPTION_REGULATOR_ACTIVITY [1927]	A molecular function that controls the rate, timing and/or magnitude of gene transcription. The function of transcriptional regulators is to modulate gene expression at the transcription step so that they are expressed in the right cell at the right time and in the right amount throughout the life of the cell and the organism. Genes are transcriptional units, and include bacterial operons. [GOC:pg, GOC:txnOH-2018, Wikipedia:Transcription_factor]	56	4.59×10^{-21}	8.09×10^{-18}
GOMF_TRANSCRIPTION_COREGULATOR_ACTIVITY [502]	A transcription regulator activity that modulates the transcription of specific	27	8×10^{-17}	7.05×10^{-14}
GOMF_TRANSCRIPTION_COACTIVATOR_ACTIVITY [273]	A transcription coregulator activity that activates or increases the transcription Binds to and modulates the activity of an enzyme. [GOC:dph, GOC:mah, GOC:tb]	17	4.83×10^{-12}	2.84×10^{-9}
GOMF_ENZYME_REGULATOR_ACTIVITY [1253]		31	3.3×10^{-10}	1.46×10^{-7}

GOMF_CYTOSKELETAL_PROTEIN_BINDING [992]	Binding to a protein component of a cytoskeleton (actin, microtubule, or intermediate filament cytoskeleton). [GOC:mah]	26	2.98 e ⁻⁹	1.05 e ⁻⁶
GOMF_GUANYL_NUCLEOTIDE_EXCHANGE_FACTOR_ACTIVITY [225]	Stimulates the exchange of GDP to GTP on a signaling GTPase, changing its activity.	13	4.04 e ⁻⁹	1.19 e ⁻⁶
GOMF_NUCLEOSIDE_TRIPHOSPHATASE_REGULATOR_ACTIVITY [489]	Binds to and modulates the activity of an NTPase. [GOC:dph, GOC:tb]	18	5.61 e ⁻⁹	1.41 e ⁻⁶
GOMF_SEQUENCE_SPECIFIC_DNA_BINDING [1686]	Binding to DNA of a specific nucleotide composition, e.g. GC-rich DNA binding, or with a specific sequence motif or type of DNA e.g. promotor binding or rDNA binding. [GOC:jl]	33	2.74 e ⁻⁸	6.04 e ⁻⁶

GOMF_TRANSCRIPTION_COREGULATOR_BINDING [109]	Binding to a transcription coregulator, a protein involved in regulation of transcription via protein-protein interactions with transcription factors and other transcription regulatory proteins. Cofactors do not bind DNA directly, but rather mediate protein-protein interactions between regulatory transcription factors and the basal transcription machinery. [GOC:krc]	9	4.88 e ⁻⁸	9.56 e ⁻⁶
GOMF_CIS_REGULATORY_REGION_SEQUENCE_SPECIFIC_DNA_BINDING [1232]	Binding to a specific upstream regulatory DNA sequence (transcription	27	5.96 e ⁻⁸	1.05 e ⁻⁵
GOMF_RNA_POLYMERASE_II_TRANSCRIPTION_REGION_REGULATORY_REGION_SEQUENCE_SPECIFIC_DNA_BINDING [1427]	Binding to a specific sequence of DNA that is part of a regulatory region that controls the transcription of a gene or	29	9.31 e ⁻⁸	1.49 e ⁻⁵
GOMF_TRANSCRIPTION_FACTOR_BINDING [597]	Binding to a transcription factor, a protein required to initiate or regulate transcription. [ISBN:0198506732]	18	1.15 e ⁻⁷	1.69 e ⁻⁵
GOMF_DNA_BINDING_TRANSCRIPTION_FACTOR_OR_BINDING [476]	Binding to a DNA-binding transcription factor, a protein that interacts with	16	1.38 e ⁻⁷	1.88 e ⁻⁵
GOMF_PROTEIN_CONTAINING_COMPLEX_BINDING	Binding to a macromolecular complex.			

DING [1302]	[GOC:jl]	27	1.79×10^{-7}	2.25×10^{-5}
GOMF_LIPID_BINDING [842]	Binding to a lipid. [GOC:ai]	21	2.37×10^{-7}	2.7×10^{-5}
	Binding to a transcription coactivator, a protein involved in positive regulation of transcription via protein-protein interactions with transcription factors and other proteins that positively regulate transcription. Transcription coactivators do not bind DNA directly, but rather mediate protein-protein interactions between activating transcription factors and the basal transcription machinery.			
GOMF_TRANSCRIPTION_COACTIVATOR_BINDING [40]	[GOC:krc]	6	2.45×10^{-7}	2.7×10^{-5}
	Binding to chromatin, the network of fibers of DNA, protein, and sometimes RNA, that make up the chromosomes of the eukaryotic nucleus during interphase. [GOC:jl, ISBN:0198506732, PMID:20404130]			
GOMF_CHROMATIN_BINDING [597]		17	5.74×10^{-7}	5.95×10^{-5}
GOMF_TRANSCRIPTION_COREPRESSOR_ACTIVITY [191]	A transcription coregulator activity that represses or decreases the transcription	10	6.38×10^{-7}	6.25×10^{-5}

GOMF_RNA_POLYMERASE_II_SPECIFIC_DNA_BINDING [350]	Binding to a sequence-specific DNA binding RNA polymerase II transcription factor, any of the factors	13	6.93 e ⁻⁷	6.43 e ⁻⁵
GOMF_MOLECULAR_ADAPTOR_ACTIVITY [492]	The binding activity of a molecule that brings together two or more molecules through a selective, non-covalent, often stoichiometric interaction, permitting those molecules to function in a coordinated way. [GOC:mtg_MIT_16mar07, GOC:vw]	15	1.16 e ⁻⁶	1.02 e ⁻⁴
GOMF_RIBONUCLEOTIDE_BINDING [1904]	Binding to a ribonucleotide, any compound consisting of a ribonucleoside that is esterified with (ortho)phosphate or an oligophosphate at any hydroxyl group on the ribose moiety. [GOC:mah]	32	1.3 e ⁻⁶	1.09 e ⁻⁴
GOMF_ENZYME_ACTIVATOR_ACTIVITY [566]	Binds to and increases the activity of an enzyme. [GOC:dph, GOC:mah, GOC:tb]	16	1.36 e ⁻⁶	1.09 e ⁻⁴
GOMF_BETA_CATENIN_BINDING [88]	Binding to a catenin beta subunit. [GOC:bf]	7	2 e ⁻⁶	1.53 e ⁻⁴

GOMF_ACTIN_FILAMENT_BINDING [222]	Binding to an actin filament, also known as F-actin, a helical filamentous polymer of globular G-actin subunits. [ISBN:0198506732]	10	2.49 e ⁻⁶	1.83 e ⁻⁴
GOMF_PHOSPHOLIPID_BINDING [476]	Binding to a phospholipid, a class of lipids containing phosphoric acid as a mono- or diester. [ISBN:0198506732]	14	3.99 e ⁻⁶	2.71 e ⁻⁴
GOMF_PROTEIN_MACROMOLECULE_ADAPTOR_ACTIVITY [348]	The binding activity of a protein that brings together two or more	12	4 e ⁻⁶	2.71 e ⁻⁴
GOMF_PROTEIN_DOMAIN_SPECIFIC_BINDING [693]	Binding to a specific domain of a protein. [GOC:go_curators]	17	4.26 e ⁻⁶	2.78 e ⁻⁴
GOMF_KINASE_BINDING [782]	Binding to a kinase, any enzyme that catalyzes the transfer of a phosphate group. [GOC:jl]	18	5.33 e ⁻⁶	3.36 e ⁻⁴
GOMF_DNA_BINDING_TRANSCRIPTION_ACTIVATOR_ACTIVITY [470]	A DNA-binding transcription factor activity that activates or increases	13	1.69 e ⁻⁵	1.03 e ⁻³
GOMF_ZINC_ION_BINDING [817]	Binding to a zinc ion (Zn). [GOC:ai]	17	3.49 e ⁻⁵	2.05 e ⁻³
GOMF_GTPASE_BINDING [305]	Binding to a GTPase, any enzyme that catalyzes the hydrolysis of GTP. [GOC:ai]	10	3.91 e ⁻⁵	2.18 e ⁻³

GOMF_ADENYL_NUCLEOTIDE_BINDING [1552]	Binding to an adenylnucleotide, an adenosine esterified with (ortho)phosphate. [ISBN:0198506732]	25	4.02 e ⁻⁵	2.18 e ⁻³
GOMF_ACTIN_BINDING [440]	Binding to monomeric or multimeric forms of actin, including actin filaments. [GOC:clt]	12	4.08 e ⁻⁵	2.18 e ⁻³
GOMF_PROTEIN_DEMETHYLASE_ACTIVITY [30]	Catalysis of the removal of a methyl group from a protein. [PMID:24498420, PMID:28360925]	4	4.4 e ⁻⁵	2.28 e ⁻³
GOMF_PHOSPHATASE_BINDING [195]	Binding to a phosphatase. [GOC:jl]	8	4.94 e ⁻⁵	2.49 e ⁻³
GOMF_PROTEIN_BINDING_INVOLVED_IN_HETEROTYPIC_CELL_CELL_ADHESION [12]	Binding to a protein or protein complex contributing to the	3	5.94 e ⁻⁵	2.91 e ⁻³
GOMF_DNA_BINDING_TRANSCRIPTION_REPRESSOR_ACTIVITY [327]	A DNA-binding transcription factor activity that represses or decreases	10	7 e ⁻⁵	3.33 e ⁻³
GOMF_HISTONE_H3_METHYL_LYSINE_9_DEMETHYLASE_ACTIVITY [13]	Catalysis of the removal of a methyl group from a modified lysine residue at	3	7.68 e ⁻⁵	3.57 e ⁻³
GOMF_GTPASE_ACTIVATOR_ACTIVITY [276]	Binds to and increases the activity of a GTPase, an enzyme that catalyzes the hydrolysis of GTP. [GOC:mah]	9	9.92 e ⁻⁵	4.4 e ⁻³

GOMF_PHOSPHATIDYLINOSITOL_BINDING [277]	Binding to an inositol-containing glycerophospholipid, i.e. phosphatidylinositol (PtdIns) and its phosphorylated derivatives. [GOC:bf, ISBN:0198506732, PMID:11395417]	9	1.02×10^{-4}	4.4×10^{-3}
GOMF_MICROFILAMENT_MOTOR_ACTIVITY [37]	A motor activity that generates movement along a microfilament, driven by ATP hydrolysis. [PMID:29716949]	4	1.02×10^{-4}	4.4×10^{-3}
GOMF_MANNOSIDASE_ACTIVITY [15]	Catalysis of the hydrolysis of mannosyl compounds, substances containing a group derived from a cyclic form of mannose or a mannose derivative. [GOC:ai]	3	1.21×10^{-4}	5.08×10^{-3}
GOMF_DEMETHYLASE_ACTIVITY [40]	Catalysis of the removal of a methyl group from a substrate. [GOC:mah]	4	1.39×10^{-4}	5.71×10^{-3}
GOMF_HISTONE_DEACETYLASE_BINDING [128]	Binding to histone deacetylase. [GOC:jl]	6	2.13×10^{-4}	8.55×10^{-3}
GOMF_PROTEIN_HOMODIMERIZATION_ACTIVITY [698]	Binding to an identical protein to form a homodimer. [GOC:jl]	14	2.49×10^{-4}	9.6×10^{-3}
GOMF_SYNTAXIN_1_BINDING [19]	Binding to a syntaxin-1 SNAP receptor. [GOC:ai]	3	2.53×10^{-4}	9.6×10^{-3}

GOMF_SIGNALING_RECEPTOR_BINDING [1544]	Binding to one or more specific sites on a receptor molecule, a macromolecule that undergoes combination with a hormone, neurotransmitter, drug or intracellular messenger to initiate a change in cell function. [GOC:bf, GOC:ceb, ISBN:0198506732]	23	2.56×10^{-4}	9.6×10^{-3}
GOMF_PROTEIN_DIMERIZATION_ACTIVITY [1067]	The formation of a protein dimer, a macromolecular structure consists of two noncovalently associated identical or nonidentical subunits. [ISBN:0198506732]	18	2.85×10^{-4}	1.05×10^{-2}
GOMF_NUCLEAR_RECEPTOR_BINDING [139]	Binding to a nuclear receptor protein. Nuclear receptor proteins are DNA-binding transcription factors which are regulated by binding to a ligand. [PMID:7776974]	6	3.33×10^{-4}	1.2×10^{-2}
GOMF_CALMODULIN_BINDING [200]	Binding to calmodulin, a calcium-binding protein with many roles, both in the calcium-bound and calcium-free states. [GOC:krc]	7	3.85×10^{-4}	1.36×10^{-2}

GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_RNA_METABOLIC_PROCESS [1835]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of the	47	1.32 e ⁻¹⁵	1.02 e ⁻¹¹
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_MACROMOLECULE_BIOSYNTHETIC_PROCESS [1908]	Any process that increases the rate, frequency or extent of the chemical	47	5.61 e ⁻¹⁵	2.18 e ⁻¹¹
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_MULTICELLULAR_ORGANISMAL_PROCESS [1556]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of an	40	2.01 e ⁻¹³	5.19 e ⁻¹⁰
GOBP_MUSCLE_STRUCTURE_DEVELOPMENT [690]	The progression of a muscle structure over time, from its formation to its mature state. Muscle structures are contractile cells, tissues or organs that are found in multicellular organisms. [GOC:dph]	26	1.19 e ⁻¹²	1.94 e ⁻⁹

GOBP_CIRCULATORY_SYSTEM_DEVELOPMENT [1211]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of the circulatory system over time, from its formation to the mature structure. The circulatory system is the organ system that passes nutrients (such as amino acids and electrolytes), gases, hormones, blood cells, etc. to and from cells in the body to help fight diseases and help stabilize body temperature and pH to maintain homeostasis. [GOC:mah, UBERON:0001009]	34	1.4×10^{-12}	1.94×10^{-9}
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_SIGNALING [1431]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent of a signaling process. [GOC:mtg_signal]	37	1.5×10^{-12}	1.94×10^{-9}
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_RESPONSE_TO_STIMULUS [1707]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent	40	3.63×10^{-12}	4.01×10^{-9}

GOBP_CELL_MOTILITY [1794]	Any process involved in the controlled self-propelled movement of a cell that results in translocation of the cell from one place to another. [GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:isa_complete, GOC:mlg]	41	4.13 e ⁻¹²	4.01 e ⁻⁹
GOBP_ACTIN_FILAMENT_BASED_PROCESS [819]	Any cellular process that depends upon or alters the actin cytoskeleton, that part of the cytoskeleton comprising actin filaments and their associated proteins. [GOC:mah]	27	9.26 e ⁻¹²	7.99 e ⁻⁹
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_TRANSCRIPTION_BY_RNA_POLYMERASE_II [1235]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of	33	1.14 e ⁻¹¹	8.84 e ⁻⁹
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_DEVELOPMENTAL_PROCESS [1388]	Any process that activates or increases the rate or extent of development, the	35	1.27 e ⁻¹¹	8.99 e ⁻⁹
GOBP_CELLULAR_RESPONSE_TO_ENDOGENOUS_S_S_STIMULUS [1394]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell (in terms of	35	1.43 e ⁻¹¹	9.28 e ⁻⁹

GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_ENDOGENOUS_STIMULUS [1643]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a stimulus arising within the organism. [GOC:sm]	38	1.96 e ⁻¹¹	1.17 e ⁻⁸
GOBP_CELL_CELL_SIGNALING [1679]	Any process that mediates the transfer of information from one cell to another. This process includes signal transduction in the receiving cell and, where applicable, release of a ligand and any processes that actively facilitate its transport and presentation to the receiving cell. Examples include signaling via soluble ligands, via cell adhesion molecules and via gap junctions. [GOC:dos, GOC:mah]	38	3.67 e ⁻¹¹	2.03 e ⁻⁸
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_MULTICELLULAR_ORGANISMAL_DEVELOPMENT [1471]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of	35	6.19 e ⁻¹¹	3.2 e ⁻⁸
GOBP_ESTABLISHMENT_OR_MAINTENANCE_OF_CELL_POLARITY [236]	Any cellular process that results in the specification, formation or maintenance	15	6.67 e ⁻¹¹	3.24 e ⁻⁸

GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_RNA_METABOLIC_PROCESS [1419]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent	34	9.93×10^{-11}	4.53×10^{-8}
GOBP_TISSUE_DEVELOPMENT [1998]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a tissue over time, from its formation to the mature structure. [ISBN:0471245208] Generation of cells within the nervous system. [GO_REF:0000021, GOC:cls, GOC:curators, GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:jid]	41	1.13×10^{-10}	4.77×10^{-8}
GOBP_NEUROGENESIS [1669]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of	37	1.22×10^{-10}	4.77×10^{-8}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_ANATOMICAL_STRUCTURE_MORPHOGENESIS [988]		28	1.23×10^{-10}	4.77×10^{-8}

GOBP_VESICLE_MEDIATED_TRANSPORT [1620]	A cellular transport process in which transported substances are moved in membrane-bounded vesicles; transported substances are enclosed in the vesicle lumen or located in the vesicle membrane. The process begins with a step that directs a substance to the forming vesicle, and includes vesicle budding and coating. Vesicles are then targeted to, and fuse with, an acceptor membrane. [GOC:ai, GOC:mah, ISBN:08789310662000]	36	2.09 e ⁻¹⁰	7.72 e ⁻⁸
GOBP_ENZYME_LINKED_RECEPTOR_PROTEIN_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [1017]	The series of molecular signals initiated by an extracellular ligand binding	28	2.36 e ⁻¹⁰	8.34 e ⁻⁸
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CELL_DIFFERENTIATION [1641]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of cell	36	2.96 e ⁻¹⁰	9.94 e ⁻⁸

GOBP_IMMUNE_SYSTEM_DEVELOPMENT [1029]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of an organismal system whose objective is to provide calibrated responses by an organism to a potential internal or invasive threat, over time, from its formation to the mature structure. A system is a regularly interacting or interdependent group of organs or tissues that work together to carry out a given biological process. [GOC:add, GOC:dph]	28	3.07 e ⁻¹⁰	9.94 e ⁻⁸
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_INTRACELLULAR_SIGNAL_TRANSDUCTION [1767]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of	37	5.87 e ⁻¹⁰	1.82 e ⁻⁷
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_NUCLEOBASE	Any cellular process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or			
ASE_CONTAINING_COMPOUND_METABOLIC_PROCESS [1551]	extent of the chemical reactions and pathways	34	9.88 e ⁻¹⁰	2.95 e ⁻⁷
GOBP_ANATOMICAL_STRUCTURE_FORMATION_IN_INVOLVED_IN_MORPHOGENESIS [1244]	The developmental process pertaining to the initial formation of an anatomical	30	1.18 e ⁻⁹	3.35 e ⁻⁷

GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_GROWTH_FACTOR [745]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a growth factor stimulus. [GOC:BHF, GOC:mah]	23	1.21 e ⁻⁹	3.35 e ⁻⁷
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_TRANSCRIPTION_BY_RNA_POLYMERASE_II [956]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent of the assembly or remodeling of chromatin composed of DNA complexed with histones, other associated proteins, and sometimes RNA. [PMID:20404130]	26	1.39 e ⁻⁹	3.71 e ⁻⁷
GOBP_CHROMATIN_ORGANIZATION [624]		21	1.44 e ⁻⁹	3.72 e ⁻⁷
GOBP_CYTOSKELETON_ORGANIZATION [1519]	A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of cytoskeletal structures. [GOC:dph, GOC:jl, GOC:mah]	33	2.23 e ⁻⁹	5.57 e ⁻⁷

GOBP_EMBRYO_DEVELOPMENT [1133]

The process whose specific outcome is the progression of an embryo from its formation until the end of its embryonic life stage. The end of the embryonic stage is organism-specific. For example, for mammals, the process would begin with zygote formation and end with birth. For insects, the process would begin at zygote formation and end with larval hatching. For plant zygotic embryos, this would be from zygote formation to the end of seed dormancy. For plant vegetative embryos, this would be from the initial determination of the cell or group of cells to form an embryo until the point when the embryo becomes independent of the parent plant. [GOC:go_curators, GOC:isa_complete, GOC:mtg_sensu]

28

2.58×10^{-9} 6.25×10^{-7}

GOBP_GENERATION_OF_NEURONS [1453]	The process in which nerve cells are generated. This includes the production of neuroblasts and their differentiation into neurons. [GOC:nln]	32	2.87×10^{-9}	6.76×10^{-7}
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_BIOSYNTHETIC_PROCESS [1705]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the rate of the chemical	35	2.99×10^{-9}	6.83×10^{-7}
GOBP_CELL_ADHESION [1541]	The attachment of a cell, either to another cell or to an underlying substrate such as the extracellular matrix, via cell adhesion molecules. [GOC:hb, GOC:pf]	33	3.17×10^{-9}	7.02×10^{-7}

GOBP_TUBE_DEVELOPMENT [1155]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a tube over time, from its initial formation to a mature structure. Epithelial and endothelial tubes transport gases, liquids and cells from one site to another and form the basic structure of many organs and tissues including lung and trachea, kidney, the mammary gland, the vascular system and the gastrointestinal and urinary-genital tracts. [PMID:12526790]	28	3.91×10^{-9}	8.43×10^{-7}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CELLULAR_RESPONSE_T	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of cellular response to transforming growth factor beta	11	5.84×10^{-9}	1.23×10^{-6}
E_TO_TRANSFORMING_GROWTH_FACTOR_BETA_SA_STIMULUS [151]	The directed movement of substances within a cell. [GOC:ai]	33	6.57×10^{-9}	1.34×10^{-6}
GOBP_INTRACELLULAR_TRANSPORT [1588]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in	14	6.78×10^{-9}	1.35×10^{-6}
GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_TRANSFORMING_GROWTH_FACTOR_BETA [281]	The series of molecular signals in which a small monomeric GTPase relays	18	9.8×10^{-9}	1.9×10^{-6}
GOBP_SMALL_GTPASE_MEDIATED_SIGNAL_TRANSDUCTION [507]				

GOBP_PEPTIDYL_AMINO_ACID_MODIFICATION [1289]	The alteration of an amino acid residue in a peptide. [GOC:mah]	29	1.06 e ⁻⁸	2 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_ANIMAL_ORGAN_MORPHOGENESIS [1058]	Morphogenesis of an animal organ. An organ is defined as a tissue or set of tissues that work together to perform a specific function or functions. Morphogenesis is the process in which anatomical structures are generated and organized. Organs are commonly observed as visibly distinct structures, but may also exist as loosely associated clusters of cells that work together to perform a specific function or functions. [GOC:dgh, GOC:go_curators, ISBN:0471245208, ISBN:0721662544]	26	1.11 e ⁻⁸	2.04 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_DEVELOPMENTAL_PROCESS [1002]	Any process that stops, prevents or reduces the rate or extent of	25	1.6 e ⁻⁸	2.89 e ⁻⁶

GOBP_TUBE_MORPHOGENESIS [944]	The process in which the anatomical structures of a tube are generated and organized. Epithelial and endothelial tubes transport gases, liquids and cells from one site to another and form the basic structure of many organs and tissues, with tube shape and organization varying from the single-celled excretory organ in <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> to the branching trees of the mammalian kidney and insect tracheal system. [GOC:bf, PMID:14624839]	24	2.21 e ⁻⁸	3.81 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_SIGNALING [1758]	Any process that activates, maintains or increases the frequency, rate or extent of a signaling process. [GOC:mtg_signal]	34	2.21 e ⁻⁸	3.81 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_HISTONE_MODIFICATION [478]	The covalent alteration of one or more amino acid residues within a histone protein. [GOC:krc]	17	2.48 e ⁻⁸	4.19 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_SECRETION [954]	The controlled release of a substance by a cell or a tissue. [GOC:ai]	24	2.69 e ⁻⁸	4.45 e ⁻⁶

GOBP_MUSCLE_TISSUE_DEVELOPMENT [423]	The progression of muscle tissue over time, from its initial formation to its mature state. Muscle tissue is a contractile tissue made up of actin and myosin fibers. [GOC:dph]	16	2.76 e ⁻⁸	4.47 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_HEART_DEVELOPMENT [608]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of the heart over time, from its formation to the mature structure. The heart is a hollow, muscular organ, which, by contracting rhythmically, keeps up the circulation of the blood. [GOC:jid, UBERON:0000948]	19	2.89 e ⁻⁸	4.58 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_TRANSFORMING_GROWTH_FACTOR_BETA_RA_RECEPTOR_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [220]	The series of molecular signals initiated by an extracellular ligand binding	12	3.05 e ⁻⁸	4.74 e ⁻⁶
WP_PATHWAYS_AFFECTED_IN_ADENOID_CYSTIC_TIC_CARCINOMA [65]	Pathways affected in adenoid cystic carcinoma	9	4.71 e ⁻¹⁰	8.15 e ⁻⁷
REACTOME_CHROMATIN_MODIFYING_ENZYMES [274]	Chromatin modifying enzymes	15	5.35 e ⁻¹⁰	8.15 e ⁻⁷
REACTOME_SIGNALING_BY_RHO_GTPASES_MIRO_IRO_GTPASES_AND_RHOBTB3 [721]	Signaling by Rho GTPases, Miro GTPases and RHOBTB3	22	3.47 e ⁻⁹	3.53 e ⁻⁶
REACTOME_RHOB_GTPASE_CYCLE [70]	RHOB GTPase cycle	8	2.11 e ⁻⁸	1.3 e ⁻⁵
PID_RHOA_REG_PATHWAY [46]	Regulation of RhoA activity	7	2.13 e ⁻⁸	1.3 e ⁻⁵

REACTOME_RHOC_GTPASE_CYCLE [74]	RHOC GTPase cycle	8	3.29×10^{-8}	1.67×10^{-5}
REACTOME_RHOA_GTPASE_CYCLE [149]	RHOA GTPase cycle	10	6.33×10^{-8}	2.46×10^{-5}
REACTOME_RHO_GTPASE_CYCLE [450]	RHO GTPase cycle	16	6.47×10^{-8}	2.46×10^{-5}
REACTOME_CDC42_GTPASE_CYCLE [155]	CDC42 GTPase cycle	10	9.18×10^{-8}	3.11×10^{-5}
REACTOME_NRAGE_SIGNALS_DEATH_THROUGH_JH_JNK [59]	NRAGE signals death through JNK	6	2.59×10^{-6}	7.8×10^{-4}
REACTOME_DEVELOPMENTAL_BIOLOGY [1151]	Developmental Biology	23	2.81×10^{-6}	7.8×10^{-4}
REACTOME_DISEASES_OF_SIGNAL_TRANSDUCTION_BY_GROWTH_FACTOR_RECEPTORS_AND_SECOND_MESSENGERS [432]	Diseases of signal transduction by growth factor receptors and second messengers	13	6.93×10^{-6}	1.76×10^{-3}
REACTOME_CELL_DEATH_SIGNALLING_VIA_NRAGE_NRIF_AND_NADE [76]	Cell death signalling via NRAGE, NRIF and NADE	6	1.14×10^{-5}	2.68×10^{-3}
REACTOME_G_ALPHA_12_13_SIGNALLING_EVENTS [80]	G alpha (12/13) signalling events	6	1.54×10^{-5}	3.29×10^{-3}
REACTOME_NOTCH1_INTRACELLULAR_DOMAIN_REGULATES_TRANSCRIPTION [48]	NOTCH1 Intracellular Domain Regulates Transcription	5	1.62×10^{-5}	3.29×10^{-3}
REACTOME_SEMA4D_IN_SEMAPHORIN_SIGNALING [24]	Sema4D in semaphorin signaling	4	1.76×10^{-5}	3.35×10^{-3}
REACTOME_HDMS_DEMETHYLATE_HISTONES [50]	HDMs demethylate histones	5	1.98×10^{-5}	3.53×10^{-3}
REACTOME_NOTCH3_INTRACELLULAR_DOMAIN_REGULATES_TRANSCRIPTION [25]	NOTCH3 Intracellular Domain Regulates Transcription	4	2.08×10^{-5}	3.53×10^{-3}
BIOCARTA_CARM_ER_PATHWAY [26]	CARM1 and Regulation of the Estrogen Receptor	4	2.45×10^{-5}	3.93×10^{-3}

REACTOME_RAC1_GTPASE_CYCLE [184]	RAC1 GTPase cycle	8	3.27×10^{-5}	4.74×10^{-3}
REACTOME_TRANSCRIPTIONAL_REGULATION_BY_BY_RUNX1 [239]	Transcriptional regulation by RUNX1	9	3.28×10^{-5}	4.74×10^{-3}
REACTOME_FORMATION_OF_THE_BETA_CATENIN_NIN_TCF_TRANSACTIVATING_COMPLEX [92]	Formation of the beta-catenin:TCF transactivating complex	6	3.42×10^{-5}	4.74×10^{-3}
REACTOME_SUMOYLATION [187]	SUMOylation	8	3.67×10^{-5}	4.87×10^{-3}
REACTOME_RHOQ_GTPASE_CYCLE [59]	RHOQ GTPase cycle	5	4.46×10^{-5}	5.42×10^{-3}
REACTOME_P75_NTR_RECEPTOR_MEDIATED_SIG SIGNALLING [97]	p75 NTR receptor-mediated signalling	6	4.61×10^{-5}	5.42×10^{-3}
WP_ECTODERM_DIFFERENTIATION [142]	Ectoderm differentiation	7	4.63×10^{-5}	5.42×10^{-3}
REACTOME_RNA_POLYMERASE_II_TRANSCRIPTI PTION [1378]	RNA Polymerase II Transcription	23	4.85×10^{-5}	5.47×10^{-3}
WP_NOTCH_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [61]	Notch signaling pathway	5	5.24×10^{-5}	5.71×10^{-3}
KEGG_FOCAL_ADHESION [199]	Focal adhesion	8	5.7×10^{-5}	5.99×10^{-3}
REACTOME_ACTIVATION_OF_THE_TFAP2_AP_2_ _2_FAMILY_OF_TRANSCRIPTION_FACTORS [12]	Activation of the TFAP2 (AP-2) family of transcription factors	3	5.94×10^{-5}	6.04×10^{-3}
REACTOME_INTRA_GOLGI_AND_RETROGRADE_GO _GOLGI_TO_ER_TRAFFIC [203]	Intra-Golgi and retrograde Golgi-to-ER traffic	8	6.55×10^{-5}	6.3×10^{-3}
REACTOME_SEMAPHORIN_INTERACTIONS [64]	Semaphorin interactions	5	6.61×10^{-5}	6.3×10^{-3}
PID_HDAC_CLASSII_PATHWAY [34]	Signaling events mediated by HDAC Class II	4	7.29×10^{-5}	6.74×10^{-3}
PID_HDAC_CLASSI_PATHWAY [66]	Signaling events mediated by HDAC Class I	5	7.67×10^{-5}	6.88×10^{-3}

REACTOME_MEMBRANE_TRAFFICKING [629]	Membrane Trafficking	14	8.52 e ⁻⁵	7.42 e ⁻³
KEGG_REGULATION_OF_ACTIN_CYTOSKELETON [213]	Regulation of actin cytoskeleton	8	9.16 e ⁻⁵	7.76 e ⁻³
WP_TH17_CELL_DIFFERENTIATION_PATHWAY [69]	Th17 cell differentiation pathway	5	9.49 e ⁻⁵	7.81 e ⁻³
REACTOME_RUNX3_REGULATES_NOTCH_SIGNALING [14]	RUNX3 regulates NOTCH signaling	3	9.73 e ⁻⁵	7.81 e ⁻³
WP_EGFEGFR_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [162]	EGF/EGFR signaling pathway	7	1.06 e ⁻⁴	8.29 e ⁻³
REACTOME_RHO_GTPASE_CYCLE [74]	RHO GTPase cycle	5	1.32 e ⁻⁴	9.85 e ⁻³
REACTOME_SIGNALING_BY_NOTCH1 [74]	Signaling by NOTCH1	5	1.32 e ⁻⁴	9.85 e ⁻³
REACTOME_REGULATION_OF_LIPID_METABOLISM_BY_PPARG [118]	Regulation of lipid metabolism by PPARalpha	6	1.37 e ⁻⁴	9.94 e ⁻³
REACTOME_NERVOUS_SYSTEM_DEVELOPMENT [580]	Nervous system development	13	1.42 e ⁻⁴	1 e ⁻²
REACTOME_FOXO_MEDIATED_TRANSCRIPTION_OF_CELL_DEATH_GENES [16]	FOXO-mediated transcription of cell death genes	3	1.48 e ⁻⁴	1 e ⁻²
REACTOME_REGULATION_OF_GENE_EXPRESSION_IN_LATE_STAGE_BRANCHING_MORPHOGENESIS_PANCREATIC_BUD_PRECURSOR_CELLS [16]	Regulation of gene expression in late stage (branching morphogenesis) pancreatic bud precursor cells	3	1.48 e ⁻⁴	1 e ⁻²
WP_VEGFAVEGFR2_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [431]	VEGFA-VEGFR2 signaling pathway	11	1.52 e ⁻⁴	1.01 e ⁻²
REACTOME_ACTIVATION_OF_GENE_EXPRESSION_BY_SREBF (SREBP) [42]	Activation of gene expression by SREBF (SREBP)	4	1.69 e ⁻⁴	1.07 e ⁻²
REACTOME_DEACTIVATION_OF_THE_BETA_CATENIN_TRANSACTIVATING	Deactivation of the beta- catenin transactivating			

		ATENIN_TRANSACTIVATING_COMPLEX [42]	complex	4	1.69 e ⁻⁴	1.07 e ⁻²
		REACTOME_TCF_DEPENDENT_SIGNALING_IN_RE_RESPONSE_TO_WNT [234]	TCF dependent signaling in response to WNT	8	1.75 e ⁻⁴	1.09 e ⁻²
		REACTOME_RORA_ACTIVATES_GENE_EXPRESSION [18]	RORA activates gene expression	3	2.14 e ⁻⁴	1.26 e ⁻²
15	395	REACTOME_CHROMATIN_MODIFYING_ENZYMES [274]	Chromatin modifying enzymes	17	1.85 e ⁻⁹	5.64 e ⁻⁶
		REACTOME_RNA_POLYMERASE_II_TRANSCRIPTION [1378]	RNA Polymerase II Transcription	36	8.01 e ⁻⁸	1.12 e ⁻⁴
		REACTOME_DEVELOPMENTAL_BIOLOGY [1151]	Developmental Biology	32	1.1 e ⁻⁷	1.12 e ⁻⁴
		REACTOME_SIGNALING_BY_RHO_GTPASES_MIRO_GTPASES_AND_RHOBTB3 [721]	Signaling by Rho GTPases, Miro GTPases and RHOBTB3	23	7.19 e ⁻⁷	5.48 e ⁻⁴
		REACTOME_RHO_GTPASE_CYCLE [450]	RHO GTPase cycle	17	2.24 e ⁻⁶	1.37 e ⁻³
		REACTOME_NERVOUS_SYSTEM_DEVELOPMENT [580]	Nervous system development	19	4.58 e ⁻⁶	2.33 e ⁻³
		WP_PRIMARY_FOCAL_SEGMENTAL_GLOMERULOSCLEROSIS_FSGS [72]	Primary focal segmental glomerulosclerosis (FSGS)	7	6.27 e ⁻⁶	2.73 e ⁻³
		REACTOME_IRE1ALPHA_ACTIVATES_CHAPERONES [50]	IRE1alpha activates chaperones	6	8.54 e ⁻⁶	3.25 e ⁻³
		REACTOME_SENSORY_PROCESSING_OF_SOUND [77]	Sensory processing of sound	7	9.82 e ⁻⁶	3.33 e ⁻³
		BIOCARTA_INTEGRIN_PATHWAY [34]	Integrin Signaling Pathway	5	1.79 e ⁻⁵	5.14 e ⁻³
		REACTOME_CDC42_GTPASE_CYCLE [155]	CDC42 GTPase cycle	9	2.12 e ⁻⁵	5.14 e ⁻³
		WP_VEGFAVEGFR2_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [431]	VEGFA-VEGFR2 signaling pathway	15	2.3 e ⁻⁵	5.14 e ⁻³

REACTOME_TRANSCRIPTIONAL_REGULATION_BY_BY_RUNX1 [239]	Transcriptional regulation by RUNX1	11	2.35 e ⁻⁵	5.14 e ⁻³
REACTOME_DISEASES_OF_SIGNAL_TRANSDUCTION_BY_GROWTH_FACTOR_RECEPTORS_AND_SECOND_MESSENGERS [432]	Diseases of signal transduction by growth factor receptors and second messengers	15	2.36 e ⁻⁵	5.14 e ⁻³
REACTOME_POST_TRANSLATIONAL_PROTEIN_MODIFICATION [1438]	Post-translational protein modification	31	3.03 e ⁻⁵	6.16 e ⁻³
REACTOME_INFECTIOUS_DISEASE [1077]	Infectious disease	25	5.68 e ⁻⁵	1.08 e ⁻²
REACTOME_RAC1_GTPASE_CYCLE [184]	RAC1 GTPase cycle	9	8.09 e ⁻⁵	1.45 e ⁻²
REACTOME_VESICLE_MEDIATED_TRANSPORT [724]	Vesicle-mediated transport	19	9.36 e ⁻⁵	1.58 e ⁻²
WP_RETT_SYNDROME_CAUSING_GENES [48]	Rett syndrome causing genes	5	9.84 e ⁻⁵	1.58 e ⁻²
PID_BETA_CATENIN_NUC_PATHWAY [80]	Regulation of nuclear beta catenin signaling and target gene transcription	6	1.27 e ⁻⁴	1.93 e ⁻²
REACTOME_MEMBRANE_TRAFFICKING [629]	Membrane Trafficking	17	1.53 e ⁻⁴	2.23 e ⁻²
REACTOME_REGULATION_OF_TP53_ACTIVITY_THROUGH_ACETYLATION [30]	Regulation of TP53 Activity through Acetylation	4	1.9 e ⁻⁴	2.64 e ⁻²
REACTOME_INTRACELLULAR_SIGNALING_BY_SECOND_MESSENGERS [307]	Intracellular signaling by second messengers	11	2.18 e ⁻⁴	2.89 e ⁻²
REACTOME_TRANSCRIPTIONAL_REGULATION_BY_BY_TP53 [363]	Transcriptional Regulation by TP53	12	2.39 e ⁻⁴	3.04 e ⁻²
KEGG_AXON_GUIDANCE [129]	Axon guidance	7	2.66 e ⁻⁴	3.14 e ⁻²

REACTOME_UNFOLDED_PROTEIN_RESPONSE_UPR [92]	Unfolded Protein Response (UPR)	6	2.73 e ⁻⁴	3.14 e ⁻²
BIOCARTA_AGR_PATHWAY [33]	Agrin in Postsynaptic Differentiation	4	2.78 e ⁻⁴	3.14 e ⁻²
BIOCARTA_UCALPAIN_PATHWAY [14]	uCalpain and friends in Cell spread	3	2.98 e ⁻⁴	3.14 e ⁻²
REACTOME_SEMA3A_PLEXIN_REPULSION_SIGNA	SEMA3A-Plexin repulsion signaling by inhibiting			
GNALING_BY_INHIBITING_INTEGRIN_ADHESION [14]	Integrin adhesion	3	2.98 e ⁻⁴	3.14 e ⁻²
WP_DYRK1A [62]	DYRK1A	5	3.33 e ⁻⁴	3.39 e ⁻²
KEGG_UBIQUITIN_MEDIATED_PROTEOLYSIS [135]	Ubiquitin mediated proteolysis	7	3.51 e ⁻⁴	3.45 e ⁻²
REACTOME_SEMAPHORIN_INTERACTIONS [64]	Semaphorin interactions	5	3.86 e ⁻⁴	3.65 e ⁻²
REACTOME_CELLULAR_RESPONSES_TO_STIMULI [812]	Cellular responses to stimuli	19	3.95 e ⁻⁴	3.65 e ⁻²
REACTOME_SIGNALING_BY_WNT [331]	Signaling by WNT	11	4.12 e ⁻⁴	3.69 e ⁻²
REACTOME_CRMP5_IN_SEMA3A_SIGNALING [16]	CRMP5 in Sema3A signaling	3	4.52 e ⁻⁴	3.94 e ⁻²
REACTOME_HATS_ACETYLATE_HISTONES [142]	HATs acetylate histones	7	4.76 e ⁻⁴	4.03 e ⁻²
REACTOME_FCGAMMA_RECEPTOR_FCGR_DEPENDENT_PHAGOCYTOSIS [143]	Fcgamma receptor (FCGR) dependent phagocytosis	7	4.96 e ⁻⁴	4.09 e ⁻²
REACTOME_CLATHRIN_MEDIATED_ENDOCYTOSIS [145]	Clathrin-mediated endocytosis	7	5.39 e ⁻⁴	4.33 e ⁻²
GOMF_ADENYL_NUCLEOTIDE_BINDING [1552]	Binding to an adenylylated nucleotide, an adenosine esterified with (ortho)phosphate. [ISBN:0198506732]	51	2.65 e ⁻¹⁴	4.68 e ⁻¹¹

GOMF_RIBONUCLEOTIDE_BINDING [1904]	Binding to a ribonucleotide, any compound consisting of a ribonucleoside that is esterified with (ortho)phosphate or an oligophosphate at any hydroxyl group on the ribose moiety. [GOC:mah]	54	1.48 e ⁻¹²	1.3 e ⁻⁹
GOMF_CHROMATIN_BINDING [597]	Binding to chromatin, the network of fibers of DNA, protein, and sometimes RNA, that make up the chromosomes of the eukaryotic nucleus during interphase. [GOC:j], ISBN:0198506732, PMID:20404130]	28	8.55 e ⁻¹²	5.02 e ⁻⁹
GOMF_CYTOSKELETAL_PROTEIN_BINDING [992]	Binding to a protein component of a cytoskeleton (actin, microtubule, or intermediate filament cytoskeleton). [GOC:mah]	34	2.38 e ⁻¹⁰	8.42 e ⁻⁸
GOMF_TRANSCRIPTION_FACTOR_BINDING [597]	Binding to a transcription factor, a protein required to initiate or regulate transcription. [ISBN:0198506732]	26	2.39 e ⁻¹⁰	8.42 e ⁻⁸

GOMF_TRANSCRIPTION_REGULATOR_ACTIVITY [1927]	A molecular function that controls the rate, timing and/or magnitude of gene transcription. The function of transcriptional regulators is to modulate gene expression at the transcription step so that they are expressed in the right cell at the right time and in the right amount throughout the life of the cell and the organism. Genes are transcriptional units, and include bacterial operons. [GOC:pg, GOC:txnOH-2018, Wikipedia:Transcription_factor]	49	7.3×10^{-10}	2.14×10^{-7}
GOMF_TRANSCRIPTION_COREGULATOR_ACTIVITY [502]	A transcription regulator activity that modulates the transcription of specific	23	1.01×10^{-9}	2.55×10^{-7}
GOMF_TRANSFERASE_ACTIVITY_TRANSFERRING_PHOSPHORUS_CONTAINING_GROUPS [889]	Catalysis of the transfer of a phosphorus-containing group from one compound (donor) to another	30	4.03×10^{-9}	8.88×10^{-7}

GOMF_ATP_DEPENDENT_ACTIVITY [555]	A molecular function characterized by the coupling of ATP hydrolysis to other steps of a reaction mechanism to make the reaction energetically favorable, for example to catalyze a reaction or drive transport against a concentration gradient. [PMID:24878343, PMID:25750732, PMID:32933017, PMID:33818025, PMID:33873056, PMID:33988324]	23	6.72 e ⁻⁹	1.32 e ⁻⁶
GOMF_DNA_BINDING_TRANSCRIPTION_FACTOR_OR_BINDING [476]	Binding to a DNA-binding transcription factor, a protein that interacts with	21	1.05 e ⁻⁸	1.7 e ⁻⁶
GOMF_PROTEIN_SERINE_THREONINE_KINASE_AE_ACTIVITY [432]	Catalysis of the reactions: ATP + protein serine = ADP + protein serine	20	1.06 e ⁻⁸	1.7 e ⁻⁶
GOMF_ACTIN_BINDING [440]	Binding to monomeric or multimeric forms of actin, including actin filaments. [GOC:clt]	20	1.44 e ⁻⁸	2 e ⁻⁶
GOMF_MODIFICATION_DEPENDENT_PROTEIN_BINDING [172]	Binding to a protein upon post-translation modification of the target	13	1.47 e ⁻⁸	2 e ⁻⁶
GOMF_PROTEIN_CONTAINING_COMPLEX_BINDING [1302]	Binding to a macromolecular complex. [GOC:jl]	36	1.96 e ⁻⁸	2.41 e ⁻⁶

GOMF_PROTEIN_SERINE_KINASE_ACTIVITY [363]	Catalysis of the reactions: ATP + protein serine = ADP + protein serine phosphate. [RHEA:17989]	18	2.05 e ⁻⁸	2.41 e ⁻⁶
GOMF_KINASE_BINDING [782]	Binding to a kinase, any enzyme that catalyzes the transfer of a phosphate group. [GOC:jl]	26	6.03 e ⁻⁸	6.64 e ⁻⁶
GOMF_SEQUENCE_SPECIFIC_DNA_BINDING [1686]	Binding to DNA of a specific nucleotide composition, e.g. GC-rich DNA binding, or with a specific sequence motif or type of DNA e.g. promotor binding or rDNA binding. [GOC:jl]	41	6.74 e ⁻⁸	6.99 e ⁻⁶
GOMF_TRANSCRIPTION_COACTIVATOR_ACTIVIT VITY [273]	A transcription coregulator activity that activates or increases the transcription	15	8.3 e ⁻⁸	8.13 e ⁻⁶
GOMF_CADHERIN_BINDING [334]	Binding to cadherin, a type I membrane protein involved in cell adhesion. [GOC:bf]	16	2.01 e ⁻⁷	1.86 e ⁻⁵
GOMF_PROTEIN_DIMERIZATION_ACTIVITY [1067]	The formation of a protein dimer, a macromolecular structure consists of two noncovalently associated identical or nonidentical subunits. [ISBN:0198506732]	30	2.2 e ⁻⁷	1.94 e ⁻⁵

GOMF_PROTEIN_KINASE_ACTIVITY [580]	Catalysis of the phosphorylation of an amino acid residue in a protein, usually according to the reaction: a protein + ATP = a phosphoprotein + ADP. [MetaCyc:PROTEIN-KINASE-RXN]	21	2.91×10^{-7}	2.35×10^{-5}
GOMF_ACTIN_FILAMENT_BINDING [222]	Binding to an actin filament, also known as F-actin, a helical filamentous polymer of globular G-actin subunits. [ISBN:0198506732]	13	2.94×10^{-7}	2.35×10^{-5}
GOMF_CALCIUM_ION_BINDING [710]	Binding to a calcium ion (Ca ²⁺). [GOC:ai]	23	5.53×10^{-7}	4.24×10^{-5}
GOMF_PHOSPHATIDYLINOSITOL_BINDING [277]	Binding to an inositol-containing glycerophospholipid, i.e. phosphatidylinositol (PtdIns) and its phosphorylated derivatives. [GOC:bf, ISBN:0198506732, PMID:11395417]	14	6.14×10^{-7}	4.51×10^{-5}
GOMF_CELL_ADHESION_MOLECULE_BINDING [559]	Binding to a cell adhesion molecule. [GOC:ai]	20	6.72×10^{-7}	4.74×10^{-5}
GOMF_ENZYME_REGULATOR_ACTIVITY [1253]	Binds to and modulates the activity of an enzyme. [GOC:dph, GOC:mah, GOC:tb]	32	7.09×10^{-7}	4.81×10^{-5}

GOMF_PHOSPHOLIPID_BINDING [476]	Binding to a phospholipid, a class of lipids containing phosphoric acid as a mono- or diester. [ISBN:0198506732]	18	1.12 e ⁻⁶	7.29 e ⁻⁵
GOMF_KINASE_ACTIVITY [745]	Catalysis of the transfer of a phosphate group, usually from ATP, to a substrate molecule. [ISBN:0198506732]	23	1.25 e ⁻⁶	7.88 e ⁻⁵
GOMF_RNA_BINDING [1961]	Binding to an RNA molecule or a portion thereof. [GOC:j, GOC:mah]	42	1.32 e ⁻⁶	8.04 e ⁻⁵

GOMF_HISTONE_BINDING [258]	Binding to a histone, any of a group of water-soluble proteins found in association with the DNA of eukaryotic or archaeal chromosomes. They are involved in the condensation and coiling of chromosomes during cell division and have also been implicated in gene regulation and DNA replication. They may be chemically modified (methylated, acetylated and others) to regulate gene transcription. [GOC:jl], PMID:16209651, PMID:30212449, PMID:9305837]	13	1.6 e ⁻⁶	9.39 e ⁻⁵
GOMF_ZINC_ION_BINDING [817]	Binding to a zinc ion (Zn). [GOC:ai]	24	1.74 e ⁻⁶	9.8 e ⁻⁵
GOMF_MOLECULAR_ADAPTOR_ACTIVITY [492]	The binding activity of a molecule that brings together two or more molecules through a selective, non-covalent, often stoichiometric interaction, permitting those molecules to function in a coordinated way. [GOC:mtg_MIT_16mar07, GOC:vw]	18	1.78 e ⁻⁶	9.8 e ⁻⁵

GOMF_SIGNALING_RECEPTOR_BINDING [1544]	Binding to one or more specific sites on a receptor molecule, a macromolecule that undergoes combination with a hormone, neurotransmitter, drug or intracellular messenger to initiate a change in cell function. [GOC:bf, GOC:ceb, ISBN:0198506732]	35	3.13×10^{-6}	1.67×10^{-4}
GOMF_CALMODULIN_BINDING [200]	Binding to calmodulin, a calcium-binding protein with many roles, both in the calcium-bound and calcium-free states. [GOC:krc]	11	4.4×10^{-6}	2.28×10^{-4}
GOMF_PROTEIN_DOMAIN_SPECIFIC_BINDING [693]	Binding to a specific domain of a protein. [GOC:go_curators]	21	4.84×10^{-6}	2.44×10^{-4}
GOMF_NUCLEOSIDE_TRIPHOSPHATASE_REGULATOR_ACTIVITY [489]	Binds to and modulates the activity of an NTPase. [GOC:dph, GOC:tb]	17	6.73×10^{-6}	3.3×10^{-4}

GOMF_RNA_POLYMERASE_II_ACTIVITY [5]	Catalysis of the reaction: nucleoside triphosphate + RNA(n) = diphosphate + RNA(n+1). Utilizes a DNA template that contains an RNA polymerase II specific promoter to direct initiation and catalyses DNA-template-directed extension of the 3'-end of an RNA strand by one nucleotide at a time. Can initiate a chain 'de novo'. [GOC:txnOH]	3	8.74 e ⁻⁶	4.16 e ⁻⁴
GOMF_RNA_POLYMERASE_II_SPECIFIC_DNA_BI _BINDING_TRANSCRIPTION_FACTOR_BINDING [350]	Binding to a sequence- specific DNA binding RNA polymerase II transcription factor, any of the factors	14	9.26 e ⁻⁶	4.3 e ⁻⁴
GOMF_ATP_DEPENDENT_CHROMATIN_REMODELER LER_ACTIVITY [33]	An activity, driven by ATP hydrolysis, that modulates the contacts between Binding to an identical protein to form a	5	1.54 e ⁻⁵	6.94 e ⁻⁴
GOMF_PROTEIN_HOMODIMERIZATION_ACTIVITY [698]	homodimer. [GOC:jl] Catalysis of the reaction: ATP + H2O = ADP + phosphate, to drive the unwinding of a DNA or RNA	20	1.82 e ⁻⁵	8 e ⁻⁴
GOMF_HELICASE_ACTIVITY [157]	helix. [GOC:jl] Catalytic activity that acts to modify DNA, driven by ATP hydrolysis. [GOC:pdt]	9	2.35 e ⁻⁵	9.87 e ⁻⁴
GOMF_ATP_DEPENDENT_ACTIVITY_ACTING_ON_ ON_DNA [121]		8	2.41 e ⁻⁵	9.87 e ⁻⁴

GOMF_KINASE_ACTIVATOR_ACTIVITY [121]	Binds to and increases the activity of a kinase, an enzyme which catalyzes of the transfer of a phosphate group, usually from ATP, to a substrate molecule. [GOC:ai]	8	2.41 e ⁻⁵	9.87 e ⁻⁴
GOMF_TRANSITION_METAL_ION_BINDING [1091]	Binding to a transition metal ions; a transition metal is an element whose atom has an incomplete d-subshell of extranuclear electrons, or which gives rise to a cation or cations with an incomplete d-subshell. Transition metals often have more than one valency state. Biologically relevant transition metals include vanadium, manganese, iron, copper, cobalt, nickel, molybdenum and silver. [ISBN:0198506732]	26	2.61 e ⁻⁵	1.05 e ⁻³
GOMF_LIPID_BINDING [842]	Binding to a lipid. [GOC:ai] Binds to and increases the activity of an enzyme. [GOC:dph, GOC:mah,	22	2.84 e ⁻⁵	1.11 e ⁻³
GOMF_ENZYME_ACTIVATOR_ACTIVITY [566]	GOC:tb]	17	4.3 e ⁻⁵	1.65 e ⁻³

			GOMF_UNMETHYLATED_CPG_BINDING [8]	Binding to unmethylated CpG motif. Unmethylated CpG dinucleotides are often associated with gene promoters. [GOC:ai, PMID:10688657]	3	4.79 e ⁻⁵	1.8 e ⁻³
			GOMF_NUCLEAR_RECEPTOR_BINDING [139]	Binding to a nuclear receptor protein. Nuclear receptor proteins are DNA-binding transcription factors which are regulated by binding to a ligand. [PMID:7776974]	8	6.48 e ⁻⁵	2.34 e ⁻³
			GOMF_LYSINE_ACETYLATED_HISTONE_BINDING [23]	Binding to a histone in which a lysine residue has been modified by acetylation. [GOC:BHF, GOC:mah, GOC:rl, PMID:17582821]	4	6.49 e ⁻⁵	2.34 e ⁻³
			GOMF_PHOSPHATIDYLINOSITOL_PHOSPHATE_BINDING [180]	Binding to phosphatidylinositol phosphate.	9	6.84 e ⁻⁵	2.41 e ⁻³
16	126	none					
17	49		GOMF_TUBULIN_BINDING [377]	Binding to monomeric or multimeric forms of tubulin, including microtubules. [GOC:clt]	6	5.81 e ⁻⁶	9 e ⁻³
			GOMF_DYNEIN_INTERMEDIATE_CHAIN_BINDING [35]	Binding to an intermediate chain of the dynein complex. [GOC:bf]	3	1.02 e ⁻⁵	9 e ⁻³

GOMF_PROTEIN_Glutamic_Acid_Ligase_Activity [10]	Catalysis of the posttranslational transfer of one or more glutamate	2	6.25×10^{-5}	3.68×10^{-2}
GOBP_CILIUM_MOVEMENT [195]	The directed, self-propelled movement of a cilium. [GOC:dph, GOC:jl]	16	1.06×10^{-25}	8.24×10^{-22}
GOBP_MICROTUBULE_BUNDLE_FORMATION [125]	A process that results in a parallel arrangement of microtubules. [GOC:dph]	13	2.46×10^{-22}	9.56×10^{-19}
GOBP_MICROTUBULE_BASED_MOVEMENT [418]	A microtubule-based process that results in the movement of organelles, other microtubules, or other cellular components. Examples include motor-driven movement along microtubules and movement driven by polymerization or depolymerization of microtubules. [GOC:cjm, ISBN:0815316194]	17	4.81×10^{-22}	1.25×10^{-18}

GOBP_AXONEME_ASSEMBLY [93]	The assembly and organization of an axoneme, the bundle of microtubules and associated proteins that forms the core of cilia (also called flagella) in eukaryotic cells and is responsible for their movements. [GOC:bf, GOC:cilia, GOC:jl, ISBN:0815316194]	11	1.2 e ⁻¹⁹	2.33 e ⁻¹⁶
GOBP_MICROTUBULE_BASED_PROCESS [946]	Any cellular process that depends upon or alters the microtubule cytoskeleton, that part of the cytoskeleton comprising microtubules and their associated proteins. [GOC:mah]	19	6.48 e ⁻¹⁹	1.01 e ⁻¹⁵
GOBP_MICROTUBULE_CYTOSKELETON_ORGANIZATION [663]	A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the Cell motility due to movement of eukaryotic cilia or bacterial-type	15	1.09 e ⁻¹⁵	1.41 e ⁻¹²
GOBP_CILIUM_OR_FLAGELLUM_DEPENDENT_CELL_MOTILITY [159]	Any process that modulates the frequency of cilium movement, the	10	4.15 e ⁻¹⁵	4.61 e ⁻¹²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CILIUM_BEAT_FREQUENCY [17]		6	2.59 e ⁻¹⁴	2.52 e ⁻¹¹

GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CILIUM_MOVEMENT [40]	Any process that modulates the rate, frequency, or extent of cilium movement, the directed, self-propelled movement of a cilium. [GOC:dph]	7	4.02 e ⁻¹⁴	3.46 e ⁻¹¹
GOBP_CILIUM_ORGANIZATION [416]	A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of a cilium, a specialized eukaryotic organelle that consists of a filiform extrusion of the cell surface. Each cilium is bounded by an extrusion of the cytoplasmic membrane, and contains a regular longitudinal array of microtubules, anchored basally in a centriole. [GOC:cilia, GOC:jl]	12	6.66 e ⁻¹⁴	5.17 e ⁻¹¹
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_MICROTUBULE_BASED_M D_MOVEMENT [55]	Any process that modulates the rate, frequency, or extent of	7	4.31 e ⁻¹³	3.04 e ⁻¹⁰

GOBP_CELL_PROJECTION_ASSEMBLY [607]	Formation of a prolongation or process extending from a cell, e.g. a flagellum or axon. [GOC:jl, GOC:mah, http://www.cogsci.princeton.edu/~wn/]	12	5.56×10^{-12}	3.59×10^{-9}
GOBP_AXONEMAL_DYNEIN_COMPLEX_ASSEMBLY [39]	The aggregation, arrangement and bonding together of a set of components to form an axonemal dynein complex, a dynein complex found in eukaryotic cilia and flagella, in which the motor domain heads interact with adjacent microtubules to generate a sliding force which is converted to a bending motion. [GOC:cilia, GOC:mah, PMID:19052621]	6	6.7×10^{-12}	4×10^{-9}
GOBP_CYTOSKELETON_ORGANIZATION [1519]	A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of cytoskeletal structures. [GOC:dph, GOC:jl, GOC:mah]	16	1.22×10^{-11}	6.78×10^{-9}

GOBP_ORGANELLE_ASSEMBLY [976]	The aggregation, arrangement and bonding together of a set of components to form an organelle. An organelle is an organized structure of distinctive morphology and function. Includes the nucleus, mitochondria, plastids, vacuoles, vesicles, ribosomes and the cytoskeleton. Excludes the plasma membrane.	13	8.63 e ⁻¹¹	4.46 e ⁻⁸
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_MICROTUBULE_BASED_PROCESS [252]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of any	8	6.59 e ⁻¹⁰	3.2 e ⁻⁷
GOBP_INNER_DYNEIN_ARM_ASSEMBLY [17]	The aggregation, arrangement and bonding together of a set of components to form an axonemal dynein inner arm, an inner arm structure present on the outer doublet microtubules of ciliary and flagellar axonemes. [GOC:BHF, GOC:vk, PMID:19944400]	4	4.23 e ⁻⁹	1.93 e ⁻⁶

GOBP_MOTILE_CILIUM_ASSEMBLY [61]	The aggregation, arrangement and bonding together of a set of components to form a motile cilium. [GO_REF:0000079, GOC:cilia, GOC:krc, GOC:TermGenie, PMID:19776033, PMID:21129373, ZFIN:dsf]	5	1.12 e ⁻⁸	4.61 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_SPERM_MOTILITY [130]	Any process involved in the controlled movement of a sperm cell. [GOC:cilia, GOC:krc]	6	1.13 e ⁻⁸	4.61 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_CELL_PROJECTION_ORGANIZATION [1576]	A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of a prolongation or process extending from a cell, e.g. a flagellum or axon. [GOC:jl, GOC:mah, http://www.cogsci.princeton.edu/~wn/]	12	2.45 e ⁻⁷	9.51 e ⁻⁵

GOBP_OUTER_DYNEIN_ARM_ASSEMBLY [23]	The aggregation, arrangement and bonding together of a set of components to form an axonemal dynein outer arm, an outer arm structure present on the outer doublet microtubules of ciliary and flagellar axonemes. [GOC:BHF, GOC:vk, PMID:19944400]	3	2.79×10^{-6}	1.03×10^{-3}
GOBP_SPERM_AXONEME_ASSEMBLY [28]	The assembly and organization of the sperm flagellar axoneme, the bundle of microtubules and associated proteins that forms the core of the eukaryotic sperm flagellum, and is responsible for movement. [GOC:bf, GOC:cilia, ISBN:0198547684]	3	5.14×10^{-6}	1.81×10^{-3}
GOBP_CELL_MOTILITY [1794]	Any process involved in the controlled self-propelled movement of a cell that results in translocation of the cell from one place to another. [GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:isa_complete, GOC:mlg]	11	6.82×10^{-6}	2.3×10^{-3}

GOBP_SPERM_FLAGELLUM_ASSEMBLY [36]	The assembly and organization of the sperm flagellum, the microtubule-based axoneme and associated structures that are part of a sperm flagellum (or cilium). [GOC:krc, PMID:32791035]	3	1.11 e ⁻⁵	3.6 e ⁻³
GOBP_EXTRACELLULAR_TRANSPORT [45]	The transport of substances that occurs outside cells. [GOC:go_curators]	3	2.19 e ⁻⁵	6.82 e ⁻³
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CILIUM_BEAT_FREQUENCY_INVOLVED_IN_CILIARY_MOTILITY [10]	Any process that modulates the frequency of cilium beating involved in ciliary motility.	2	6.25 e ⁻⁵	1.87 e ⁻²
GOBP_SPERMATID_DIFFERENTIATION [196]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a spermatid over time, from initial commitment of the cell to a specific fate, to the fully functional differentiated cell. [GOC:dph, GOC:jjd]	4	9.06 e ⁻⁵	2.6 e ⁻²
GOBP_EPITHELIAL_CILIUM_MOVEMENT_INVOLVED_IN_DETERMINATION_OF_LEFT_RIGHT_ANTASYMMETRY [13]	The movement of cilia of epithelial cells of the Left Right Organizer (LRO), also referred to as the node in mouse or the Kupffer's	2	1.08 e ⁻⁴	2.9 e ⁻²

			The addition of one or more alpha-linked glutamyl units to the gamma carboxyl group of peptidyl-glutamic acid.			
	GOBP_PROTEIN_POLYGLUTAMYLATION [13]		[RESID:AA0202]	2	1.08 e ⁻⁴	2.9 e ⁻²
	WP_CILIOPATHIES [184]		Ciliopathies	7	2.39 e ⁻⁹	7.29 e ⁻⁶

18

32

			A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of a cilium, a specialized eukaryotic organelle that consists of a filiform extrusion of the cell surface. Each cilium is bounded by an extrusion of the cytoplasmic membrane, and contains a regular longitudinal array of microtubules, anchored basally in a centriole.			
	GOBP_CILIUM_ORGANIZATION [416]		[GOC:cilia, GOC:jl]	9	2.38 e ⁻¹¹	1.85 e ⁻⁷
	GOBP_CILIUM_OR_FLAGELLUM_DEPENDENT_CEL CELL_MOTILITY [159]		Cell motility due to movement of eukaryotic cilia or bacterial-type	6	2.57 e ⁻⁹	9.99 e ⁻⁶
	GOBP_CILIUM_MOVEMENT [195]		The directed, self-propelled movement of a cilium. [GOC:dph, GOC:jl]	6	8.74 e ⁻⁹	2.26 e ⁻⁵

GOBP_CELL_PROJECTION_ASSEMBLY [607]	Formation of a prolongation or process extending from a cell, e.g. a flagellum or axon. [GOC:jl, GOC:mah, http://www.cogsci.princeton.edu/~wn/]	8	1.69 e ⁻⁸	3.28 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_SPECIFICATION_OF_SYMMETRY [142]	The establishment of an organism's body plan or part of an organism such that a similar arrangement in form and relationship of parts around a common axis, or around each side of a plane is created. [GOC:go_curators]	5	8.66 e ⁻⁸	1.34 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_MICROTUBULE_BASED_PROCESS [946]	Any cellular process that depends upon or alters the microtubule cytoskeleton, that part of the cytoskeleton comprising microtubules and their associated proteins. [GOC:mah]	8	5.01 e ⁻⁷	6.48 e ⁻⁴

GOBP_ORGANELLE_ASSEMBLY [976]	<p>The aggregation, arrangement and bonding together of a set of components to form an organelle. An organelle is an organized structure of distinctive morphology and function. Includes the nucleus, mitochondria, plastids, vacuoles, vesicles, ribosomes and the cytoskeleton. Excludes the plasma membrane.</p> <p>[GOC:mah]</p>	8	6.33 e ⁻⁷	7.02 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_MICROTUBULE_BASED_MOVEMENT [418]	<p>A microtubule-based process that results in the movement of organelles, other microtubules, or other cellular components. Examples include motor-driven movement along microtubules and movement driven by polymerization or depolymerization of microtubules. [GOC:cjm, ISBN:0815316194]</p>	6	7.83 e ⁻⁷	7.32 e ⁻⁴

GOBP_AXONEME_ASSEMBLY [93]	The assembly and organization of an axoneme, the bundle of microtubules and associated proteins that forms the core of cilia (also called flagella) in eukaryotic cells and is responsible for their movements. [GOC:bf, GOC:cilia, GOC:jl, ISBN:0815316194]	4	8.48 e ⁻⁷	7.32 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_CELL_PROJECTION_ORGANIZATION [1576]	A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of a prolongation or process extending from a cell, e.g. a flagellum or axon. [GOC:jl, GOC:mah, http://www.cogsci.princeton.edu/~wn/]	9	2.25 e ⁻⁶	1.74 e ⁻³
GOBP_MICROTUBULE_BUNDLE_FORMATION [125]	A process that results in a parallel arrangement of microtubules. [GOC:dph]	4	2.77 e ⁻⁶	1.95 e ⁻³
GOBP_SPERM_MOTILITY [130]	Any process involved in the controlled movement of a sperm cell. [GOC:cilia, GOC:krc]	4	3.23 e ⁻⁶	2.09 e ⁻³

GOBP_MOTILE_CILIUM_ASSEMBLY [61]	The aggregation, arrangement and bonding together of a set of components to form a motile cilium. [GO_REF:0000079, GOC:cilia, GOC:krc, GOC:TermGenie, PMID:19776033, PMID:21129373, ZFIN:dsf]	3	1.51 e ⁻⁵	8.99 e ⁻³
GOBP_PATTERN_SPECIFICATION_PROCESS [472]	Any developmental process that results in the creation of defined areas or spaces within an organism to which cells respond and eventually are instructed to differentiate. [GOC:go_curators, GOC:isa_complete, ISBN:0521436125]	5	3.08 e ⁻⁵	1.71 e ⁻²
GOBP_CELL_MOTILITY [1794]	Any process involved in the controlled self-propelled movement of a cell that results in translocation of the cell from one place to another. [GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:isa_complete, GOC:mlg]	8	5.41 e ⁻⁵	2.8 e ⁻²

19

26

REACTOME_INTERFERON_ALPHA_BETA_SIGNALI

Interferon alpha/beta

ALING [73]	signaling	9	3.28 e ⁻¹⁹	9.99 e ⁻¹⁶
REACTOME_INTERFERON_SIGNALING [204]	Interferon Signaling	10	3.68 e ⁻¹⁷	5.6 e ⁻¹⁴
REACTOME_CYTOKINE_SIGNALING_IN_IMMUNE_SYSTEM [729]	Cytokine Signaling in Immune system	13	1.34 e ⁻¹⁶	1.36 e ⁻¹³
REACTOME_OAS_ANTIVIRAL_RESPONSE [9]	OAS antiviral response	3	1.89 e ⁻⁸	1.44 e ⁻⁵
REACTOME_ANTIVIRAL_MECHANISM_BY_IFN_STIMULATED_GENES [82]	Antiviral mechanism by IFN-stimulated genes	4	2.15 e ⁻⁷	1.31 e ⁻⁴
REACTOME_INTERFERON_GAMMA_SIGNALING [94]	Interferon gamma signaling	4	3.72 e ⁻⁷	1.73 e ⁻⁴
WP_IMMUNE_RESPONSE_TO_TUBERCULOSIS [23]	Immune response to tuberculosis	3	3.97 e ⁻⁷	1.73 e ⁻⁴
WP_NETWORK_MAP_OF_SARSCOV2_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [218]	Network map of SARS-CoV-2 signaling pathway	4	1.06 e ⁻⁵	4.04 e ⁻³
WP_NONGENOMIC_ACTIONS_OF_1,25_DIHYDROXYVITAMIN_D3 [75]	Non-genomic actions of 1,25 dihydroxyvitamin D3 Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a stimulus from a virus.	3	1.48 e ⁻⁵	5.02 e ⁻³
GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_VIRUS [410]	[GOC:hb]	15	5.38 e ⁻²⁴	4.18 e ⁻²⁰

GOBP_DEFENSE_RESPONSE_TO_SYMBIONT [306]	Reactions triggered in response to the presence of a symbiont that act to protect the cell or organism from damage caused by that symbiont. [GOC:pg]	12	2.11 e ⁻¹⁹	8.18 e ⁻¹⁶
GOBP_BIOLOGICAL_PROCESS_INVOLVED_IN_IN _INTERSPECIES_INTERACTION_BETWEEN_ORGA RGANISMS [1722]	Any process evolved to enable an interaction with an organism of a different species. [GOC:cc]	17	7.91 e ⁻¹⁸	2.05 e ⁻¹⁴
GOBP_DEFENSE_RESPONSE_TO_OTHER_ORGANIS MISM [1178]	Reactions triggered in response to the presence of another organism that Innate immune responses are defense responses mediated by germline encoded components that directly recognize components of potential pathogens. [GO_REF:0000022, GOC:add, GOC:ebc, GOC:mtg_sensu]	15	3.93 e ⁻¹⁷	7.63 e ⁻¹⁴
GOBP_INNATE_IMMUNE_RESPONSE [921]	Any immune system process that functions in the calibrated response of an organism to a potential internal or invasive threat. [GO_REF:0000022, GOC:add]	14	5.66 e ⁻¹⁷	8.78 e ⁻¹⁴
GOBP_IMMUNE_RESPONSE [1940]		16	2 e ⁻¹⁵	2.59 e ⁻¹²

GOBP_DEFENSE_RESPONSE [1816]	Reactions, triggered in response to the presence of a foreign body or the occurrence of an injury, which result in restriction of damage to the organism attacked or prevention/recovery from the infection caused by the attack. [GOC:go_curators]	15	2.27 e ⁻¹⁴	2.52 e ⁻¹¹
GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_CYTOKINE [932]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a cytokine stimulus. [GOC:sl]	11	4.45 e ⁻¹²	4.32 e ⁻⁹
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_VIRAL_PROCESS [162]	Any process that modulates the rate or extent of the viral life cycle, the set of processes by which a virus reproduces and spreads among hosts. [GOC:go_curators, GOC:tb]	7	8.13 e ⁻¹²	7.01 e ⁻⁹
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_VIRAL_GENOME_REPLICATION [57]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent	5	2.79 e ⁻¹⁰	2.16 e ⁻⁷

GOBP_VIRAL_LIFE_CYCLE [320]	A set of processes which all viruses follow to ensure survival; includes attachment and entry of the virus particle, decoding of genome information, translation of viral mRNA by host ribosomes, genome replication, and assembly and release of viral particles containing the genome. [ISBN:1555811272]	7	9.55 e ⁻¹⁰	6.74 e ⁻⁷
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_RESPONSE_TO_BIOTIC_IC_STIMULUS [361]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate, or extent of a	7	2.2 e ⁻⁹	1.42 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_VIRAL_GENOME_REPLICATION [87]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of viral	5	2.43 e ⁻⁹	1.45 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_IMMUNE_RESPONSE [918]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the immune response, the immunological reaction of an organism to an immunogenic stimulus. [GOC:ai]	9	3.01 e ⁻⁹	1.58 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_VIRAL_PROCESS [91]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent	5	3.05 e ⁻⁹	1.58 e ⁻⁶

GOBP_VIRAL_PROCESS [419]	A multi-organism process in which a virus is a participant. The other participant is the host. Includes infection of a host cell, replication of the viral genome, and assembly of progeny virus particles. In some cases the viral genetic material may integrate into the host genome and only subsequently, under particular circumstances, 'complete' its life cycle. [GOC:bf, GOC:jl, GOC:mah]	7	6.15 e ⁻⁹	2.98 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_INTERLEUKIN_27_MEDIATED_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [7]	The series of molecular signals initiated by interleukin-27 binding to a Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a stimulus from a virus. [GOC:dos]	3	7.9 e ⁻⁹	3.61 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_CELLULAR_RESPONSE_TO_VIRUS [117]	Any process involved directly in viral genome replication, including viral nucleotide metabolism. [ISBN:0781702534]	5	1.09 e ⁻⁸	4.69 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_VIRAL_GENOME_REPLICATION [130]		5	1.85 e ⁻⁸	7.35 e ⁻⁶

GOBP_REGULATION_OF_RIBONUCLEASE_ACTIVI VITY [9]	Any process that modulates the rate, frequency, or extent of	3	1.89 e ⁻⁸	7.35 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_RESPONSE_T E_TO_BIOTIC_STIMULUS [188]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate, or extent of a	5	1.17 e ⁻⁷	4.31 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_PATTERN_RECOGNITION_RECEPTOR_SIGN IGNALING_PATHWAY [191]	The series of molecular signals initiated by a ligand binding to a pattern Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a type I interferon stimulus. Type I interferons include the interferon- alpha, beta, delta, epsilon, zeta, kappa, tau, and omega gene families. [GOC:add, ISBN:0126896631, PMID:15546383, PMID:16681834]	5	1.26 e ⁻⁷	4.46 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_TYPE_I_INTERFERON [83]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate, or extent of an	4	2.25 e ⁻⁷	7.48 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_IMMUNE_SYSTEM_PROCE CESS [1523]		9	2.31 e ⁻⁷	7.48 e ⁻⁵

GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_INTERFERON_ALPHA [20]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of an interferon-alpha stimulus. Interferon-alpha is a type I interferon. [GOC:sl, PMID:11356686]	3	2.56 e ⁻⁷	7.95 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_NUCLEASE_ACTIVITY [22]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of nuclease activity, the hydrolysis of ester linkages within nucleic acids. [GOC:mah]	3	3.45 e ⁻⁷	1.03 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_RESPONSE_TO_EXTERNAL_STIMULUS [464]	Any process that activates, maintains or increases the rate of a response to an	6	3.86 e ⁻⁷	1.09 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_INNATE_IMMUNE_RESPONSE [240]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the innate	5	3.92 e ⁻⁷	1.09 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_BACTERIUM [783]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a stimulus from a bacterium. [GOC:hb]	7	4.32 e ⁻⁷	1.16 e ⁻⁴

GOBP_CYTOKINE_MEDIATED_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [495]	The series of molecular signals initiated by the binding of a cytokine to a	6	5.62 e ⁻⁷	1.46 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_IMMUNE_RESPONSE [601]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of the	6	1.73 e ⁻⁶	4.25 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_IMMUNE_SYSTEM_PROCESS [966]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate, or extent of an	7	1.75 e ⁻⁶	4.25 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_TYPE_I_INTERFERON_MEDIATED_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [41]	Any process that modulates the rate, frequency or extent of a	3	2.37 e ⁻⁶	5.58 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_RESPONSE_TO_EXTERNAL_STIMULUS [1017]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of a	7	2.46 e ⁻⁶	5.62 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_PATTERN_RECOGNITION_RECEPTOR_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [45]	Any process that decreases the rate, frequency or extent of a pattern recognition receptor	3	3.15 e ⁻⁶	6.99 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_RESPONSE_TO_CYTOKINE_STIMULUS [179]	Any process that modulates the rate, frequency, or extent of a	4	4.87 e ⁻⁶	1.05 e ⁻³
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_SIGNALING [1758]	Any process that activates, maintains or increases the frequency, rate or extent of a signaling process. [GOC:mtg_signal]	8	8.77 e ⁻⁶	1.84 e ⁻³
GOBP_IMMUNE_RESPONSE_REGULATING_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [500]	The cascade of processes by which a signal interacts with a receptor, causing a	5	1.41 e ⁻⁵	2.87 e ⁻³
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_INNATE_IMMUNE_RESPONSE [77]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent	3	1.6 e ⁻⁵	3.19 e ⁻³

GOBP_CELLULAR_RESPONSE_TO_INTERFERON_ALPHA [10]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell (in terms of	2	1.73 e ⁻⁵	3.28 e ⁻³
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_RIG_I_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [10]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of RIG-I	2	1.73 e ⁻⁵	3.28 e ⁻³
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_RESPONSE_TO_CYTOKINE_STIMULUS [94]	Any process that decreases the rate, frequency, or extent of a response to	3	2.92 e ⁻⁵	5.39 e ⁻³
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_HYDROLASE_ACTIVITY [1025]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of hydrolase activity, the catalysis of the hydrolysis of various bonds, e.g. C-O, C-N, C-C, phosphoric anhydride bonds, etc. Hydrolase is the systematic name for any enzyme of EC class 3. [GOC:ai]	6	3.6 e ⁻⁵	6.5 e ⁻³
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_MONOCYTE_CHEMOTACTIC_PROTEIN_1_PRODUCTION [15]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate, or extent of production of monocyte	2	4.04 e ⁻⁵	6.96 e ⁻³
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_T_CELL_APOPTOTIC_PROCESS [15]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of T cell	2	4.04 e ⁻⁵	6.96 e ⁻³
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_PATTERN_RECOGNITION_ION_RECEPTOR_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [108]	Any process that modulates the rate, frequency or extent of a pattern recognition	3	4.42 e ⁻⁵	7.45 e ⁻³
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_TUMOR_NECROSIS_FACTOR_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [108]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency,			

ECROSIS_FACTOR_SUPERFAMILY_CYTOKINE_PR _PRODUCTION [109]	rate or extent of tumor necrosis factor superfamily cytokine production.	3	4.54×10^{-5}	7.5×10^{-3}
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_RESPONSE_T E_TO_BIOTIC_STIMULUS [116]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate, or extent	3	5.47×10^{-5}	8.84×10^{-3}
GOBP_CELLULAR_RESPONSE_TO_INTERFERON_G N_GAMMA [117]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell (in terms of	3	5.61×10^{-5}	8.88×10^{-3}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_LYMPHOCYTE YTE_APOPTOTIC_PROCESS [18]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of	2	5.88×10^{-5}	9.12×10^{-3}
GOMF_DOUBLE_STRANDED_RNA_BINDING [77]	Binding to double-stranded RNA. [GOC:jl]	5	1.3×10^{-9}	2.3×10^{-6}
GOMF_ADENYLYLTRANSFERASE_ACTIVITY [32]	Catalysis of the transfer of an adenylyl group to an acceptor. [GOC:mah]	3	1.11×10^{-6}	9.77×10^{-4}
GOMF_RIBONUCLEOTIDE_BINDING [1904]	Binding to a ribonucleotide, any compound consisting of a ribonucleoside that is esterified with (ortho)phosphate or an oligophosphate at any hydroxyl group on the ribose moiety. [GOC:mah]	8	1.57×10^{-5}	9.21×10^{-3}
GOMF_NUCLEOTIDYLTRANSFERASE_ACTIVITY [122]	Catalysis of the transfer of a nucleotidyl group to a reactant. [ISBN:0198506732]	3	6.35×10^{-5}	2.8×10^{-2}

20	71		Binding to a carboxylic acid, an organic acid containing one or more carboxyl (COOH) groups or anions (COO-). [GOC:mah, ISBN:0198506732]	5	1.63×10^{-5}	2.87×10^{-2}
		GOMF_CARBOXYLIC_ACID_BINDING [181]				
			Binding to icosanoids, any C20 polyunsaturated fatty acids or their derivatives, including the leukotrienes and the prostanoids. [ISBN:0198506732]	2	6.17×10^{-5}	4.05×10^{-2}
		GOMF_ICOSANOID_BINDING [7]				
			Binding to a protein antigen. [PMID:9360996]	2	8.22×10^{-5}	4.05×10^{-2}
		GOMF_PROTEIN_ANTIGEN_BINDING [8]				
			Binding to a fatty acid, an aliphatic monocarboxylic acids liberated from naturally occurring fats and oils by hydrolysis. [ISBN:0198506732]	3	9.19×10^{-5}	4.05×10^{-2}
		GOMF_FATTY_ACID_BINDING [50]				

GOMF_CARBOHYDRATE_BINDING [275]	<p>Binding to a carbohydrate, which includes monosaccharides, oligosaccharides and polysaccharides as well as substances derived from monosaccharides by reduction of the carbonyl group (alditols), by oxidation of one or more hydroxy groups to afford the corresponding aldehydes, ketones, or carboxylic acids, or by replacement of one or more hydroxy group(s) by a hydrogen atom. Cyclitols are generally not regarded as carbohydrates.</p>	5	1.19×10^{-4}	4.18×10^{-2}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_DEVELOPMENTAL_PROCESS [1388]	<p>Any process that activates or increases the rate or extent of development, the</p>	13	6.76×10^{-7}	5.25×10^{-3}

GOBP_CELL_MOTILITY [1794]	Any process involved in the controlled self-propelled movement of a cell that results in translocation of the cell from one place to another. [GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:isa_complete, GOC:mlg]	14	2.06×10^{-6}	8×10^{-3}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_MYELINATION [18]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of the	3	3.98×10^{-6}	1.03×10^{-2}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_MULTICELLULAR_ORGANISMAL_DEVELOPMENT [1471]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of The progression of a connective tissue over time, from its formation to the mature structure.	12	7.83×10^{-6}	1.33×10^{-2}
GOBP_CONNECTIVE_TISSUE_DEVELOPMENT [275]	[GOC:BHF]	6	8.55×10^{-6}	1.33×10^{-2}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_MULTICELLULAR_ORGANISMAL_PROCESS [1556]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of an	12	1.37×10^{-5}	1.78×10^{-2}
GOBP_MESENCHYME_DEVELOPMENT [314]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a mesenchymal tissue over time, from its formation to the mature structure. A mesenchymal tissue is made up of loosely packed stellate cells. [GOC:dph]	6	1.81×10^{-5}	2.01×10^{-2}

GOBP_NEUROGENESIS [1669]	Generation of cells within the nervous system. [GO_REF:0000021, GOC:cls, GOC:curators, GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:jid]	12	2.74 e ⁻⁵	2.23 e ⁻²
GOBP_OLIGODENDROCYTE_DIFFERENTIATION [100]	The process in which a relatively unspecialized cell acquires the specialized features of an oligodendrocyte. An oligodendrocyte is a type of glial cell involved in myelinating the axons of neurons in the central nervous system. [GOC:vp, PMID:15139015]	4	2.85 e ⁻⁵	2.23 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_MORPHOGENESIS_OF_AN_EPITHELIUM [36]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of	3	3.41 e ⁻⁵	2.23 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_NERVOUS_SYSTEM_PROCESS [36]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of a	3	3.41 e ⁻⁵	2.23 e ⁻²
GOBP_TISSUE_DEVELOPMENT [1998]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a tissue over time, from its formation to the mature structure. [ISBN:0471245208]	13	3.45 e ⁻⁵	2.23 e ⁻²

GOBP_GENERATION_OF_NEURONS [1453]	The process in which nerve cells are generated. This includes the production of neuroblasts and their differentiation into neurons. [GOC:nln]	11	3.87×10^{-5}	2.31×10^{-2}
GOBP_METANEPHRIC_TUBULE_FORMATION [6]	The developmental process pertaining to the initial formation of a metanephric tubule. [GOC:mtg_kidney_jan10]	2	4.41×10^{-5}	2.35×10^{-2}
GOBP_GLIAL_CELL_DIFFERENTIATION [227]	The process in which a relatively unspecialized cell acquires the specialized features of a glial cell. [GOC:go_curators, GOC:mtg_sensu]	5	4.81×10^{-5}	2.35×10^{-2}
GOBP_CELLULAR_RESPONSE_TO_OXYGEN_CONTAINING_COMPOUND [1226]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell (in terms of	10	4.85×10^{-5}	2.35×10^{-2}
GOBP_ANATOMICAL_STRUCTURE_FORMATION_INVOLVED_IN_MORPHOGENESIS [1244]	The developmental process pertaining to the initial formation of an anatomical	10	5.47×10^{-5}	2.5×10^{-2}

GOBP_OLIGODENDROCYTE_DEVELOPMENT [43]	The process aimed at the progression of an oligodendrocyte over time, from initial commitment of the cell to a specific fate, to the fully functional differentiated cell. An oligodendrocyte is a type of glial cell involved in myelinating the axons in the central nervous system. [GOC:dgh, GOC:ef]	3	5.84×10^{-5}	2.52×10^{-2}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_GASTRULATION [7]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of a system process, a multicellular organismal process carried out by any of the organs or tissues in an organ system. [GOC:j]	2	6.17×10^{-5}	2.52×10^{-2}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_SYSTEM_PROCESS [595]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the formation of a myelin sheath around nerve axons. [GOC:mah]	7	7.78×10^{-5}	2.77×10^{-2}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_MYELENATION [48]		3	8.13×10^{-5}	2.77×10^{-2}

GOBP_MESENCHYMAL_CELL_DIFFERENTIATION [254]	The process in which a relatively unspecialized cell acquires specialized features of a mesenchymal cell. A mesenchymal cell is a loosely associated cell that is part of the connective tissue in an organism. Mesenchymal cells give rise to more mature connective tissue cell types. [GOC:dph, GOC:jid]	5	8.17×10^{-5}	2.77×10^{-2}
GOBP_METANEPHRIC_NEPHRON_TUBULE_MORPHOGENESIS [8]	The process in which the anatomical structures of a metanephric nephron	2	8.22×10^{-5}	2.77×10^{-2}
GOBP_CENTRAL_NERVOUS_SYSTEM_DEVELOPMENT [1061]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of the central nervous	9	8.88×10^{-5}	2.87×10^{-2}

process which begins when a cell receives an internal (e.g. DNA damage) or external signal (e.g. an extracellular death ligand), and proceeds through a series of biochemical events (signaling pathway phase) which trigger an execution phase. The execution phase is the last step of an apoptotic process, and is typically characterized by rounding-up of the cell, retraction of pseudopodes, reduction of cellular volume (pyknosis), chromatin condensation, nuclear fragmentation (karyorrhexis), plasma membrane blebbing and fragmentation of the cell into apoptotic bodies. When the execution phase is completed, the cell has died. [GOC:cjm, GOC:dhl, GOC:ecd, GOC:go_curators,

GOBP_APOPTOTIC_PROCESS [1933]

12

1.12 e⁻⁴ 3.48 e⁻²

GOBP_ENSHEATHMENT_OF_NEURONS [144]	The process in which glial cells envelop neuronal cell bodies and/or axons to form an insulating layer. This can take the form of myelinating or non-myelinating ensheathment. [GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:tb]	4	1.18 e ⁻⁴	3.48 e ⁻²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_NERVOUS_SYSTEM_PROCESS [145]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of a	4	1.21 e ⁻⁴	3.48 e ⁻²
GOBP_CELL_FATE_COMMITMENT [282]	The commitment of cells to specific cell fates and their capacity to differentiate into particular kinds of cells. Positional information is established through protein signals that emanate from a localized source within a cell (the initial one-cell zygote) or within a developmental field. [ISBN:0716731185]	5	1.33 e ⁻⁴	3.7 e ⁻²
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_BIOSYNTHETIC_PROCESS [1705]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the rate of the chemical	11	1.6 e ⁻⁴	4.03 e ⁻²

GOBP_METANEPHRIC_TUBULE_MORPHOGENESIS [11]	The process in which the anatomical structures of a metanephric tubule are generated and organized from an epithelium. A metanephric tubule is an epithelial tube that is part of the metanephros. [GOC:mtg_kidney_jan10]	2	1.61 e ⁻⁴	4.03 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_KIDNEY_DEVELOPMENT [11]	Any process that increases the rate, frequency or extent of kidney	2	1.61 e ⁻⁴	4.03 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_CELL_DIFFERENTIATION [916]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of cell	8	1.84 e ⁻⁴	4.38 e ⁻²
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_MULTICELLULAR_ORGANISMAL_PROCESS [1171]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent	9	1.86 e ⁻⁴	4.38 e ⁻²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_MORPHOGENESIS_OF_AN_EPITHELIUM [65]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of	3	2.01 e ⁻⁴	4.59 e ⁻²
GOBP_GLIOGENESIS [310]	The process that results in the generation of glial cells. This includes the production of glial progenitors and their differentiation into mature glia. [GOC:dgh, GOC:jjd]	5	2.07 e ⁻⁴	4.59 e ⁻²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_INTRACELLULAR_SIGNAL_TRANSDUCTION [1767]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of	11	2.18 e ⁻⁴	4.7 e ⁻²

GOBP_TUBE_MORPHOGENESIS [944]	<p>The process in which the anatomical structures of a tube are generated and organized. Epithelial and endothelial tubes transport gases, liquids and cells from one site to another and form the basic structure of many organs and tissues, with tube shape and organization varying from the single-celled excretory organ in <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> to the branching trees of the mammalian kidney and insect tracheal system.</p> <p>[GOC:bf, PMID:14624839]</p>	8	2.26 e ⁻⁴	4.74 e ⁻²
-------------------------------	---	---	----------------------	----------------------

GOBP_CIRCULATORY_SYSTEM_DEVELOPMENT [1211]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of the circulatory system over time, from its formation to the mature structure. The circulatory system is the organ system that passes nutrients (such as amino acids and electrolytes), gases, hormones, blood cells, etc. to and from cells in the body to help fight diseases and help stabilize body temperature and pH to maintain homeostasis.	9	2.39 e ⁻⁴	4.78 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_GLIOGENESIS [69]	[GOC:mah, UBERON:0001009] Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of	3	2.4 e ⁻⁴	4.78 e ⁻²

		GOBP_REGULATION_OF_TRANSPORT [1793]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the directed movement of substances (such as macromolecules, small molecules, ions) into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore. [GOC:ai]	11	2.47×10^{-4}	4.8×10^{-2}
		REACTOME_EXTRACELLULAR_MATRIX_ORGANIZATION [300]	Extracellular matrix organization	7	9.31×10^{-7}	2.84×10^{-3}
21	53	GOMF_SIGNALING_RECEPTOR_REGULATOR_ACTIVITY [532]	Binds to and modulates the activity of a receptor. [GOC:ceb]	9	2.59×10^{-8}	4.57×10^{-5}
		GOMF_SIGNALING_RECEPTOR_BINDING [1544]	Binding to one or more specific sites on a receptor molecule, a macromolecule that undergoes combination with a hormone, neurotransmitter, drug or intracellular messenger to initiate a change in cell function. [GOC:bf, GOC:ceb, ISBN:0198506732]	13	5.99×10^{-8}	5.28×10^{-5}

GOMF_CYTOKINE_ACTIVITY [236]	<p>The activity of a soluble extracellular gene product that interacts with a receptor to effect a change in the activity of the receptor to control the survival, growth, differentiation and effector function of tissues and cells. [ISBN:0198599471, PMID:11530802]</p>	6	6.24×10^{-7}	3.67×10^{-4}
GOMF_GROWTH_FACTOR_ACTIVITY [162]	<p>The function that stimulates a cell to grow or proliferate. Most growth factors have other actions besides the induction of cell growth or proliferation. [ISBN:0815316194]</p>	4	5.91×10^{-5}	2.6×10^{-2}
GOBP_TISSUE_DEVELOPMENT [1998]	<p>The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a tissue over time, from its formation to the mature structure. [ISBN:0471245208]</p>	21	1.76×10^{-14}	1.37×10^{-10}

GOBP_EPITHELIUM_DEVELOPMENT [1211]	<p>The process whose specific outcome is the progression of an epithelium over time, from its formation to the mature structure. An epithelium is a tissue that covers the internal or external surfaces of an anatomical structure.</p> <p>[GOC:dph, GOC:mtg_lung]</p>	16	1.61 e ⁻¹²	6.25 e ⁻⁹
GOBP_CIRCULATORY_SYSTEM_DEVELOPMENT [1211]	<p>The process whose specific outcome is the progression of the circulatory system over time, from its formation to the mature structure. The circulatory system is the organ system that passes nutrients (such as amino acids and electrolytes), gases, hormones, blood cells, etc. to and from cells in the body to help fight diseases and help stabilize body temperature and pH to maintain homeostasis.</p> <p>[GOC:mah, UBERON:0001009]</p>	15	2.27 e ⁻¹¹	4.12 e ⁻⁸

GOBP_LOCOMOTION [1446]	Self-propelled movement of a cell or organism from one location to another. [GOC:dgh]	16	2.28 e ⁻¹¹	4.12 e ⁻⁸
GOBP_TISSUE_MORPHOGENESIS [637]	The process in which the anatomical structures of a tissue are generated and organized. [GOC:dph, GOC:jid]	12	2.66 e ⁻¹¹	4.12 e ⁻⁸
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CELL_POPULATION_PROLIFERATION [1779]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of cell	17	4.61 e ⁻¹¹	5.97 e ⁻⁸
GOBP_MORPHOGENESIS_OF_AN_EPITHELIUM [524]	The process in which the anatomical structures of epithelia are generated and organized. An epithelium consists of closely packed cells arranged in one or more layers, that covers the outer surfaces of the body or lines any internal cavity or tube. [GOC:dph, GOC:jl, GOC:tb, ISBN:0198506732]	11	6.27 e ⁻¹¹	6.95 e ⁻⁸
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_LOCOMOTION [1132]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of locomotion of a cell or organism. [GOC:ems]	14	1.21 e ⁻¹⁰	1.18 e ⁻⁷

GOBP_HEART_DEVELOPMENT [608]	<p>The process whose specific outcome is the progression of the heart over time, from its formation to the mature structure. The heart is a hollow, muscular organ, which, by contracting rhythmically, keeps up the circulation of the blood. [GOC:jid, UBERON:0000948]</p>	11	3.01 e^{-10}	2.6 e^{-7}
GOBP_EPITHELIAL_CELL_PROLIFERATION [492]	<p>The multiplication or reproduction of epithelial cells, resulting in the expansion of a cell population. Epithelial cells make up the epithelium, the covering of internal and external surfaces of the body, including the lining of vessels and other small cavities. It consists of cells joined by small amounts of cementing substances. [ISBN:0721662544]</p>	10	6.93 e^{-10}	5.38 e^{-7}
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_SIGNALING [1431]	<p>Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent of a signaling process. [GOC:mtg_signal]</p>	14	2.5 e^{-9}	1.77 e^{-6}

GOBP_CELL_MOTILITY [1794]	<p>Any process involved in the controlled self-propelled movement of a cell that results in translocation of the cell from one place to another. [GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:isa_complete, GOC:mlg]</p>	15	5.03 e ⁻⁹	3.25 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_ANIMAL_ORGAN_MORPHOGENESIS [1058]	<p>Morphogenesis of an animal organ. An organ is defined as a tissue or set of tissues that work together to perform a specific function or functions. Morphogenesis is the process in which anatomical structures are generated and organized. Organs are commonly observed as visibly distinct structures, but may also exist as loosely associated clusters of cells that work together to perform a specific function or functions. [GOC:dgh, GOC:go_curators, ISBN:0471245208, ISBN:0721662544]</p>	12	8.22 e ⁻⁹	4.75 e ⁻⁶

GOBP_CHEMICAL_HOMEOSTASIS [1062]	Any biological process involved in the maintenance of an internal steady state of a chemical. [GOC:isa_complete]	12	8.57 e ⁻⁹	4.75 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_ENDOGENOUS_STIMULUS [1643]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a stimulus arising within the organism. [GOC:sm]	14	1.44 e ⁻⁸	7.44 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CELL_DEATH [1689]	Any process that modulates the rate or frequency of cell death. Cell death is the specific activation or halting of processes within a cell so that its vital functions markedly cease, rather than simply deteriorating gradually over time, which culminates in cell death. [GOC:dph, GOC:tb]	14	2.03 e ⁻⁸	9.86 e ⁻⁶

GOBP_TUBE_DEVELOPMENT [1155]	<p>The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a tube over time, from its initial formation to a mature structure. Epithelial and endothelial tubes transport gases, liquids and cells from one site to another and form the basic structure of many organs and tissues including lung and trachea, kidney, the mammary gland, the vascular system and the gastrointestinal and urinary-genital tracts.</p>	12	2.16×10^{-8}	9.87×10^{-6}
GOBP_HOMEOSTATIC_PROCESS [1708]	<p>Any biological process involved in the maintenance of an internal steady state. [GOC:j], ISBN:0395825172]</p>	14	2.34×10^{-8}	1.01×10^{-5}

GOBP_TUBE_MORPHOGENESIS [944]	<p>The process in which the anatomical structures of a tube are generated and organized. Epithelial and endothelial tubes transport gases, liquids and cells from one site to another and form the basic structure of many organs and tissues, with tube shape and organization varying from the single-celled excretory organ in <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> to the branching trees of the mammalian kidney and insect tracheal system.</p>	11	2.86×10^{-8}	1.17×10^{-5}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_SIGNALING [1758]	<p>Any process that activates, maintains or increases the frequency, rate or extent of a signaling process.</p>	14	3.35×10^{-8}	1.3×10^{-5}
GOBP_G_PROTEIN_COUPLED_RECEPTOR_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [1276]	<p>The series of molecular signals initiated by a ligand binding to its receptor, in</p>	12	6.41×10^{-8}	2.32×10^{-5}

GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_LOCOMOTION [419]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent of locomotion of a cell or organism. [GOC:go_curators]	8	6.58 e ⁻⁸	2.32 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_CIRCULATORY_SYSTEM_PROCESS [610]	A organ system process carried out by any of the organs or tissues of the circulatory system. The circulatory system is an organ system that moves extracellular fluids to and from tissue within a multicellular organism. [GOC:mtg_cardio]	9	8.31 e ⁻⁸	2.81 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CELL_DIFFERENTIATION [1641]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of cell	13	1.21 e ⁻⁷	3.92 e ⁻⁵

GOBP_CELL_CELL_SIGNALING [1679]	Any process that mediates the transfer of information from one cell to another. This process includes signal transduction in the receiving cell and, where applicable, release of a ligand and any processes that actively facilitate its transport and presentation to the receiving cell. Examples include signaling via soluble ligands, via cell adhesion molecules and via gap junctions. [GOC:dos, GOC:mah]	13	1.58×10^{-7}	4.75×10^{-5}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_DEVELOPMENTAL_PROCESS [1388]	Any process that activates or increases the rate or extent of development, the	12	1.59×10^{-7}	4.75×10^{-5}
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_RESPONSE_TO_STIMULUS [1707]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent	13	1.9×10^{-7}	5.48×10^{-5}

GOBP_REGULATION_OF_RESPONSE_TO_STRESS [1437]	<p>Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of a response to stress. Response to stress is a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a disturbance in organismal or cellular homeostasis, usually, but not necessarily, exogenous (e.g. temperature, humidity, ionizing radiation). [GOC:dh]</p>	12	2.31×10^{-7}	6.39×10^{-5}
GOBP_ENDOTHELIAL_CELL_PROLIFERATION [206]	<p>The multiplication or reproduction of endothelial cells, resulting in the expansion of a cell population. Endothelial cells are thin flattened cells which line the inside surfaces of body cavities, blood vessels, and lymph vessels, making up the endothelium. [GOC:add, ISBN:0781735149]</p>	6	2.81×10^{-7}	7.53×10^{-5}

GOBP_EPITHELIAL_CELL_DIFFERENTIATION [721]	The process in which a relatively unspecialized cell acquires specialized features of an epithelial cell, any of the cells making up an epithelium. [GOC:ecd, PMID:11839751]	9	3.39×10^{-7}	8.77×10^{-5}
GOBP_COLUMNAR_CUBOIDAL_EPITHELIAL_CELL_DIFFERENTIATION [116]	The process in which a relatively unspecialized cell acquires specialized Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a growth factor stimulus. [GOC:BHF, GOC:mah]	5	4.27×10^{-7}	1.07×10^{-4}
GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_GROWTH_FACTOR [745]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of	9	4.45×10^{-7}	1.08×10^{-4}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_ANATOMICAL_STRUCTURE_MORPHOGENESIS [988]	The process in which the population of cells that make up a tissue undergo directed movement. [GOC:ascb_2009, GOC:dph, GOC:tb]	10	4.8×10^{-7}	1.13×10^{-4}
GOBP_TISSUE_MIGRATION [376]		7	5.52×10^{-7}	1.26×10^{-4}

GOBP_RENAL_SYSTEM_PROCESS [125]	A organ system process carried out by any of the organs or tissues of the renal system. The renal system maintains fluid balance, and contributes to electrolyte balance, acid/base balance, and disposal of nitrogenous waste products. In humans, the renal system comprises a pair of kidneys, a pair of ureters, urinary bladder, urethra, sphincter muscle and associated blood vessels; in other species, the renal system may comprise related structures (e.g., nephrocytes and malpighian tubules in Drosophila). [GOC:cjm, GOC:mtg_cardio, GOC:mtg_kidney_jan10]	5	6.19 e ⁻⁷	1.35 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_ENZYME_LINKED_RECEPTOR_PROTEIN_SI_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [1017]	The series of molecular signals initiated by an extracellular ligand binding	10	6.24 e ⁻⁷	1.35 e ⁻⁴

GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_CELL_DEATH [1031]	Any process that decreases the rate or frequency of cell death. Cell death is the specific activation or halting of processes within a cell so that its vital functions markedly cease, rather than simply deteriorating gradually over time, which culminates in cell death. [GOC:BHF, GOC:dph, GOC:tb]	10	7.06 e^{-7}	1.48 e^{-4}
GOBP_TRANSMEMBRANE_RECEPTOR_PROTEIN_SE	The series of molecular signals initiated by an extracellular ligand binding to a receptor on the surface of the target cell	7	7.67 e^{-7}	1.55 e^{-4}
_SERINE_THREONINE_KINASE_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [395]				

GOBP_APOPTOTIC_PROCESS [1933]	<p>process which begins when a cell receives an internal (e.g. DNA damage) or external signal (e.g. an extracellular death ligand), and proceeds through a series of biochemical events (signaling pathway phase) which trigger an execution phase. The execution phase is the last step of an apoptotic process, and is typically characterized by rounding-up of the cell, retraction of pseudopodes, reduction of cellular volume (pyknosis), chromatin condensation, nuclear fragmentation (karyorrhexis), plasma membrane blebbing and fragmentation of the cell into apoptotic bodies. When the execution phase is completed, the cell has died. [GOC:cjm, GOC:dhl, GOC:ecd,</p>	13	7.8×10^{-7}	1.55×10^{-4}
GOBP_STRIATED_MUSCLE_TISSUE_DEVELOPMENT [258]	<p>The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a striated muscle over</p>	6	1.05×10^{-6}	2.03×10^{-4}

GOBP_HEART_MORPHOGENESIS [259]	The developmental process in which the heart is generated and organized. The heart is a hollow, muscular organ, which, by contracting rhythmically, keeps up the circulation of the blood. [GOC:dph, GOC:isa_complete]	6	1.07 e ⁻⁶	2.03 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_CELL_DEATH [614]	Any process that increases the rate or frequency of cell death. Cell death is the specific activation or halting of processes within a cell so that its vital functions markedly cease, rather than simply deteriorating gradually over time, which culminates in cell death. [GOC:dph, GOC:tb]	8	1.18 e ⁻⁶	2.18 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_MUSCLE_TISSUE_DEVELOPMENT [423]	The progression of muscle tissue over time, from its initial formation to its mature state. Muscle tissue is a contractile tissue made up of actin and myosin fibers. [GOC:dph]	7	1.21 e ⁻⁶	2.18 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_PEPTIDYL_TYROSINE_P E_PHOSPHORYLATION [266]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the	6	1.25 e ⁻⁶	2.21 e ⁻⁴

GOBP_GAP_JUNCTION_ASSEMBLY [18]	Assembly of gap junctions, which are found in most animal tissues, and serve as direct connections between the cytoplasm of adjacent cells. They provide open channels through the plasma membrane, allowing ions and small molecules (less than approximately a thousand daltons) to diffuse freely between neighboring cells, but preventing the passage of proteins and nucleic acids. [GOC:jid, ISBN:0716731363]	3	1.64 e ⁻⁶	2.83 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_TRANSMEMBRANE_RECEPTOR_PROTEIN_SERINE_THREONINE_KINASE_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [292]	Any process that modulates the rate, frequency, or extent of the series of molecular signals generated as a	6	2.14 e ⁻⁶	3.62 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_MULTICELLULAR_ORGANISMAL_DEVELOPMENT [1471]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of	11	2.32 e ⁻⁶	3.83 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_CELL_DIFFERENTIATION [916]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of cell	9	2.44 e ⁻⁶	3.93 e ⁻⁴

GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_LIPID [919]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a lipid stimulus. [GOC:sl]	9	2.51×10^{-6}	3.93×10^{-4}
GOBP_GLANDULAR_EPITHELIAL_CELL_DIFFERENTIATION [73]	The process in which a relatively unspecialized cell acquires specialized	4	2.53×10^{-6}	3.93×10^{-4}
NABA_MATRISOME [1026]	Ensemble of genes encoding extracellular matrix and extracellular matrix-associated proteins	11	6.64×10^{-8}	2.03×10^{-4}
WP_OVERVIEW_OF_PROINFLAMMATORY_AND_PROFIBROTIC_MEDIATORS [128]	Overview of proinflammatory and profibrotic mediators	5	6.96×10^{-7}	1.06×10^{-3}
WP_VITAMIN_D_RECEPTOR_PATHWAY [185]	Vitamin D receptor pathway	5	4.26×10^{-6}	2.35×10^{-3}
REACTOME_CLASS_A_1_RHODOPSIN_LIKE_RECEPTORS [331]	Class A/1 (Rhodopsin-like receptors)	6	4.4×10^{-6}	2.35×10^{-3}
REACTOME_INTERLEUKIN_20_FAMILY_SIGNALING [26]	Interleukin-20 family signaling	3	5.19×10^{-6}	2.35×10^{-3}
NABA_MATRISOME_ASSOCIATED [751]	Ensemble of genes encoding ECM-associated proteins including ECM-affiliated proteins, ECM regulators and secreted factors	8	5.22×10^{-6}	2.35×10^{-3}

NABA_SECRETED_FACTORS [343]	Genes encoding secreted soluble factors	6	5.4×10^{-6}	2.35×10^{-3}
REACTOME_NUCLEAR_SIGNALING_BY_ERBB4 [32]	Nuclear signaling by ERBB4	3	9.84×10^{-6}	3.75×10^{-3}
REACTOME_GPCR_LIGAND_BINDING [463]	GPCR ligand binding	6	2.94×10^{-5}	9.95×10^{-3}
REACTOME_METABOLISM_OF_LIPIDS [742]	Metabolism of lipids	7	4.61×10^{-5}	1.37×10^{-2}
REACTOME_G_ALPHA_I_SIGNALLING_EVENTS [314]	G alpha (i) signalling events	5	5.41×10^{-5}	1.37×10^{-2}
REACTOME_SIGNALING_BY_RECEPTOR_TYROSIN SINE_KINASES [519]	Signaling by Receptor Tyrosine Kinases	6	5.53×10^{-5}	1.37×10^{-2}
REACTOME_SIGNALING_BY_ERBB4 [58]	Signaling by ERBB4	3	5.98×10^{-5}	1.37×10^{-2}
REACTOME_RHOQ_GTPASE_CYCLE [59]	RHOQ GTPase cycle	3	6.29×10^{-5}	1.37×10^{-2}
WP_MAMMARY_GLAND_DEVELOPMENT_PATHWAY_P Y_PUBERTY_STAGE_2_OF_4 [13]	Mammary gland development pathway - Puberty (Stage 2 of 4)	2	1.27×10^{-4}	2.44×10^{-2}
REACTOME_PEPTIDE_LIGAND_BINDING_RECEPT EPTORS [198]	Peptide ligand-binding receptors	4	1.28×10^{-4}	2.44×10^{-2}
REACTOME_ESR_MEDIATED_SIGNALING [221]	ESR-mediated signaling	4	1.95×10^{-4}	3.5×10^{-2}
WP_MALIGNANT_PLEURAL_MESOTHELIOMA [439]	Malignant pleural mesothelioma	5	2.58×10^{-4}	4.37×10^{-2}
REACTOME_SIGNALING_BY_GPCR [702]	Signaling by GPCR	6	2.85×10^{-4}	4.58×10^{-2}

22

139

NABA_MATRISOME [1026]	Ensemble of genes encoding extracellular matrix and extracellular matrix-associated proteins	17	8.11×10^{-8}	2.47×10^{-4}
REACTOME_NGF_STIMULATED_TRANSCRIPTION [39]	NGF-stimulated transcription	4	9.48×10^{-6}	1.22×10^{-2}

REACTOME_SIGNALING_BY_RECEPTOR_TYROSIN SINE_KINASES [519]	Signaling by Receptor Tyrosine Kinases	10	1.2×10^{-5}	1.22×10^{-2}
NABA_CORE_MATRISOME [275]	Ensemble of genes encoding core extracellular matrix including ECM glycoproteins, collagens and proteoglycans	7	4.53×10^{-5}	2.97×10^{-2}
REACTOME_NUCLEAR_EVENTS_KINASE_AND_TRA TRANSCRIPTION_FACTOR_ACTIVATION [61]	Nuclear Events (kinase and transcription factor activation)	4	5.67×10^{-5}	2.97×10^{-2}
NABA_ECM_GLYCOPROTEINS [196]	Genes encoding structural ECM glycoproteins	6	5.85×10^{-5}	2.97×10^{-2}
GOBP_TISSUE_DEVELOPMENT [1998]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a tissue over time, from its formation to the mature structure. [ISBN:0471245208]	34	3.72×10^{-15}	2.89×10^{-11}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_MULTICELLU LLULAR_ORGANISMAL_PROCESS [1556]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of an	27	2.58×10^{-12}	1×10^{-8}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_DEVELOPMEN TAL_PROCESS [1388]	Any process that activates or increases the rate or extent of development, the	24	5.36×10^{-11}	1.39×10^{-7}

GOBP_ANIMAL_ORGAN_MORPHOGENESIS [1058]	<p>Morphogenesis of an animal organ. An organ is defined as a tissue or set of tissues that work together to perform a specific function or functions. Morphogenesis is the process in which anatomical structures are generated and organized. Organs are commonly observed as visibly distinct structures, but may also exist as loosely associated clusters of cells that work together to perform a specific function or functions. [GOC:dgh, GOC:go_curators, ISBN:0471245208, ISBN:0721662544]</p>	21	8.16×10^{-11}	1.58×10^{-7}
GOBP_CELL_MOTILITY [1794]	<p>Any process involved in the controlled self-propelled movement of a cell that results in translocation of the cell from one place to another. [GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:isa_complete, GOC:mlg]</p>	25	1.77×10^{-9}	2.74×10^{-6}

GOBP_NEUROGENESIS [1669]	Generation of cells within the nervous system. [GO_REF:0000021, GOC:cls, GOC:curators, GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:jid]	24	2.12 e ⁻⁹	2.75 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_GENERATION_OF_NEURONS [1453]	The process in which nerve cells are generated. This includes the production of neuroblasts and their differentiation into neurons. [GOC:nln]	22	4.28 e ⁻⁹	4.58 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_MULTICELLULAR_ORGANISMAL_HOMEOSTASIS [536]	Any process involved in the maintenance of an internal steady state at the level of	14	4.72 e ⁻⁹	4.58 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_MULTICELLULAR_ORGANISMAL_DEVELOPMENT [1471]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of	22	5.34 e ⁻⁹	4.61 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CELL_DIFFERENTIATION [1641]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of cell	23	7.74 e ⁻⁹	5.49 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_NEURON_DEVELOPMENT [1113]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a neuron over time, from initial commitment of the cell to a specific fate, to the fully functional differentiated cell. [GOC:dph]	19	8.14 e ⁻⁹	5.49 e ⁻⁶

GOBP_REGULATION_OF_TRANSPORT [1793]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the directed movement of substances (such as macromolecules, small molecules, ions) into, out of or within a cell, or between cells, by means of some agent such as a transporter or pore.	24	8.49 e ⁻⁹	5.49 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_CELL_PROJECTION_ORGANIZATION [1576]	[GOC:ai] A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of a prolongation or process extending from a cell, e.g. a flagellum or axon. [GOC:jl, GOC:mah, http://www.cogsci.princeton.edu/~wn/]	22	1.83 e ⁻⁸	1.09 e ⁻⁵
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_NEURON_PROJECTION_D N_DEVELOPMENT [446]	Any process that modulates the rate, frequency or extent of	12	4.53 e ⁻⁸	2.51 e ⁻⁵

GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_WOUNDING [580]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a stimulus indicating damage to the organism. [GOC:go_curators]	13	1.02×10^{-7}	5.26×10^{-5}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_SYSTEM_PROCESS [595]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of a system process, a multicellular organismal process carried out by any of the organs or tissues in an organ system. [GOC:j]	13	1.36×10^{-7}	6.6×10^{-5}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CELL_POPULATION_PROLIFERATION [1779]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of cell	22	1.51×10^{-7}	6.92×10^{-5}
GOBP_EPITHELIUM_DEVELOPMENT [1211]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of an epithelium over time, from its formation to the mature structure. An epithelium is a tissue that covers the internal or external surfaces of an anatomical structure. [GOC:dph, GOC:mtg_lung]	18	1.64×10^{-7}	7.08×10^{-5}

GOBP_CELL_CELL_SIGNALING [1679]	Any process that mediates the transfer of information from one cell to another. This process includes signal transduction in the receiving cell and, where applicable, release of a ligand and any processes that actively facilitate its transport and presentation to the receiving cell. Examples include signaling via soluble ligands, via cell adhesion molecules and via gap junctions. [GOC:dos, GOC:mah]	21	2.5 e ⁻⁷	1.02 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_OXYGEN_CONTAINING_COMPOUND [1695]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in	21	2.91 e ⁻⁷	1.13 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_HOMEOSTATIC_PROCESS [1708]	Any biological process involved in the maintenance of an internal steady state. [GOC:jl, ISBN:0395825172]	21	3.3 e ⁻⁷	1.22 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_CELL_MORPHOGENESIS [1019]	The developmental process in which the size or shape of a cell is generated and organized. [GOC:clt, GOC:dph, GOC:go_curators, GOC:tb]	16	4.1 e ⁻⁷	1.45 e ⁻⁴

GOBP_DIVALENT_INORGANIC_CATION_HOMEOSTOSTASIS [357]	Any process involved in the maintenance of an internal steady state of divalent	10	4.34 e ⁻⁷	1.47 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_CELL_DIFFERENTIATION [916]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of cell	15	5.73 e ⁻⁷	1.85 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_NEURON_PROJECTION_DEVELOPMENT [142]	Any process that decreases the rate, frequency or extent of neuron	7	5.99 e ⁻⁷	1.86 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_AXON_INJURY [89]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of an axon injury stimulus. [GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:jid, GOC:lm]	6	6.27 e ⁻⁷	1.86 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CELL_PROJECTION_ORGANIZATION [683]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of a process	13	6.46 e ⁻⁷	1.86 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_ENDOGENOUS_STIMULUS [1643]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a stimulus arising within the organism. [GOC:sm]	20	7.58 e ⁻⁷	2.09 e ⁻⁴

GOBP_REGULATION_OF_SYNAPSE_STRUCTURE_OR_ACTIVITY [215]	Any process that modulates the physical form or the activity of a	8	7.82×10^{-7}	2.09×10^{-4}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CATION_TRANSMEMBRANE_TRANSPORT [394]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of cation	10	1.06×10^{-6}	2.74×10^{-4}
GOBP_CELL_ADHESION [1541]	The attachment of a cell, either to another cell or to an underlying substrate such as the extracellular matrix, via cell adhesion molecules. [GOC:hb, GOC:pf]	19	1.22×10^{-6}	3.02×10^{-4}
GOBP_CALCIIUM_ION_HOMEOSTASIS [310]	Any process involved in the maintenance of an internal steady state of calcium ions within an organism or cell. [GOC:ceb, GOC:jid, GOC:mah]	9	1.24×10^{-6}	3.02×10^{-4}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_ANATOMICAL_STRUCTURE_MORPHOGENESIS [988]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of	15	1.46×10^{-6}	3.44×10^{-4}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_SECRETION [626]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the controlled release of a substance from a cell or a tissue. [GOC:ai]	12	1.65×10^{-6}	3.77×10^{-4}

GOBP_METAL_ION_HOMEOSTASIS [520]	Any process involved in the maintenance of an internal steady state of metal ions within an organism or cell. [GOC:ai, GOC:jid, GOC:mah]	11	1.78 e ⁻⁶	3.95 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_TRANSPORTER_ACTIVITY [326]	Any process that modulates the activity of a transporter. [GOC:mah]	9	1.88 e ⁻⁶	4.02 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_CELLULAR_METAL_ION_HOMEOSTASIS [421]	Any process involved in the maintenance of an internal steady state of metal ions at the level of a cell. [GOC:ai, GOC:mah]	10	1.92 e ⁻⁶	4.02 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_SYNAPSE_ORGANIZATION [432]	A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of a synapse, the junction between a neuron and a target (neuron, muscle, or secretory cell). [GOC:ai, GOC:pr]	10	2.41 e ⁻⁶	4.93 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_MULTICELLULAR_ORGANISMAL_PROCESS [1171]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent	16	2.49 e ⁻⁶	4.96 e ⁻⁴

The process whose specific outcome is the progression of the circulatory system over time, from its formation to the mature structure. The circulatory system is the organ system that passes nutrients (such as amino acids and electrolytes), gases, hormones, blood cells, etc. to and from cells in the body to help fight diseases and help stabilize body temperature and pH to maintain homeostasis.

[GOC:mah,
UBERON:0001009]

GOBP_CIRCULATORY_SYSTEM_DEVELOPMENT [1211]

16

3.82×10^{-6}

7.4×10^{-4}

	The process in which the anatomical structures of a tube are generated and organized. Epithelial and endothelial tubes transport gases, liquids and cells from one site to another and form the basic structure of many organs and tissues, with tube shape and organization varying from the single-celled excretory organ in <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> to the branching trees of the mammalian kidney and insect tracheal system. [GOC:bf, PMID:14624839]	14	4.36 e ⁻⁶	8.26 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_TUBE_MORPHOGENESIS [944]				
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_CELL_PROJECTION_ORGANIZATION [193]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent	7	4.63 e ⁻⁶	8.56 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_TRANSPORTER_ACTIVITY [126]	Any process that activates or increases the activity of a transporter. [GOC:mah]	6	4.8 e ⁻⁶	8.66 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_SECRETION [954]	The controlled release of a substance by a cell or a tissue. [GOC:ai]	14	4.92 e ⁻⁶	8.68 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CATION_CHANNEL_ACTIVITY [197]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of cation	7	5.3 e ⁻⁶	9.03 e ⁻⁴
GOBP_ANATOMICAL_STRUCTURE_FORMATION_IN	The developmental process pertaining to the initial			

_INVOLVED_IN_MORPHOGENESIS [1244]	<p>formation of an anatomical</p> <p>A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of a cell junction. A cell junction is a specialized region of connection between two cells or between a cell and the extracellular matrix.</p>	16	5.35×10^{-6}	9.03×10^{-4}
GOBP_CELL_JUNCTION_ORGANIZATION [707]	<p>[GOC:dph, GOC:jl, GOC:mah]</p>	12	5.7×10^{-6}	9.42×10^{-4}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_SIGNALING [1758]	<p>Any process that activates, maintains or increases the frequency, rate or extent of a signaling process.</p> <p>[GOC:mtg_signal]</p>	19	8.15×10^{-6}	1.29×10^{-3}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_CATION_CHANNEL_ACTIVITY [80]	<p>Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of cation</p>	5	8.15×10^{-6}	1.29×10^{-3}

GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_CELL_DEATH [614]	Any process that increases the rate or frequency of cell death. Cell death is the specific activation or halting of processes within a cell so that its vital functions markedly cease, rather than simply deteriorating gradually over time, which culminates in cell death. [GOC:dph, GOC:tb]	11	8.59 e ⁻⁶	1.33 e ⁻³
GOMF_SIGNALING_RECEPTOR_BINDING [1544]	Binding to one or more specific sites on a receptor molecule, a macromolecule that undergoes combination with a hormone, neurotransmitter, drug or intracellular messenger to initiate a change in cell function. [GOC:bf, GOC:ceb, ISBN:0198506732]	19	1.26 e ⁻⁶	2.21 e ⁻³
GOMF_SIGNALING_RECEPTOR_REGULATOR_ACTIVITY [532]	Binds to and modulates the activity of a receptor. [GOC:ceb]	10	1.48 e ⁻⁵	1.31 e ⁻²

23

55

GOMF_SIGNALING_RECEPTOR_BINDING [1544]

Binding to one or more specific sites on a receptor molecule, a macromolecule that undergoes combination with a hormone, neurotransmitter, drug or intracellular messenger to initiate a change in cell function. [GOC:bf, GOC:ceb, ISBN:0198506732]

11

5.41 e⁻⁶6.44 e⁻³

GOMF_SERINE_HYDROLASE_ACTIVITY [199]

Catalysis of the hydrolysis of a substrate by a catalytic mechanism that involves a catalytic triad consisting of a serine nucleophile that is activated by a proton relay involving an acidic residue (e.g. aspartate or glutamate) and a basic residue (usually histidine). [Wikipedia:Serine_hydrolase]

5

7.3 e⁻⁶6.44 e⁻³

GOMF_TYPE_II_TRANSFORMING_GROWTH_FACTOR_BETA_RECEPTOR_BINDING [10]

Binding to a type II transforming growth factor beta receptor. [GOC:ceb,

2

7.89 e⁻⁵4.25 e⁻²

GOMF_DYSTROGLYCAN_BINDING [11]	Binding to dystroglycan, a glycoprotein found in non-muscle tissues as well as in muscle tissues, often in association with dystrophin. The native dystroglycan cleaved into two non-covalently associated subunits, alpha (N-terminal) and beta (C-terminal). [GOC:hjd]	2	9.64 e ⁻⁵	4.25 e ⁻²
GOBP_TUBE_DEVELOPMENT [1155]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a tube over time, from its initial formation to a mature structure. Epithelial and endothelial tubes transport gases, liquids and cells from one site to another and form the basic structure of many organs and tissues including lung and trachea, kidney, the mammary gland, the vascular system and the gastrointestinal and urinary-genital tracts. [PMID:12526790]	12	3.38 e ⁻⁸	2.62 e ⁻⁴

GOBP_CELL_MORPHOGENESIS [1019]	The developmental process in which the size or shape of a cell is generated and organized. [GOC:clt, GOC:dph, GOC:go_curators, GOC:tb]	11	9.3×10^{-8}	3.51×10^{-4}
GOBP_ANIMAL_ORGAN_MORPHOGENESIS [1058]	Morphogenesis of an animal organ. An organ is defined as a tissue or set of tissues that work together to perform a specific function or functions. Morphogenesis is the process in which anatomical structures are generated and organized. Organs are commonly observed as visibly distinct structures, but may also exist as loosely associated clusters of cells that work together to perform a specific function or functions. [GOC:dgh, GOC:go_curators, ISBN:0471245208, ISBN:0721662544]	11	1.35×10^{-7}	3.51×10^{-4}
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_DEVELOPMENTAL_PROCESS [1388]	Any process that activates or increases the rate or extent of development, the	12	2.46×10^{-7}	4.77×10^{-4}

GOBP_TUBE_MORPHOGENESIS [944]	The process in which the anatomical structures of a tube are generated and organized. Epithelial and endothelial tubes transport gases, liquids and cells from one site to another and form the basic structure of many organs and tissues, with tube shape and organization varying from the single-celled excretory organ in <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> to the branching trees of the mammalian kidney and insect tracheal system. [GOC:bf, PMID:14624839]	10	4.56×10^{-7}	7.08×10^{-4}
GOBP_TISSUE_DEVELOPMENT [1998]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a tissue over time, from its formation to the mature structure. [ISBN:0471245208]	13	1.78×10^{-6}	2.3×10^{-3}
GOBP_CELL_PART_MORPHOGENESIS [666]	The process in which the anatomical structures of a cell part are generated and organized. [GOC:mah]	8	2.88×10^{-6}	3.2×10^{-3}

GOBP_CELL_MOTILITY [1794]	Any process involved in the controlled self-propelled movement of a cell that results in translocation of the cell from one place to another. [GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:isa_complete, GOC:mlg]	12	3.61 e ⁻⁶	3.5 e ⁻³
GOBP_NEURON_MIGRATION [177]	The characteristic movement of an immature neuron from germinal zones to specific positions where they will reside as they mature. [CL:0000540, GOC:go_curators]	5	4.13 e ⁻⁶	3.56 e ⁻³
GOBP_SYNAPSE_ASSEMBLY [184]	The aggregation, arrangement and bonding together of a set of components to form a synapse. This process ends when the synapse is mature (functional). [GOC:mah]	5	4.99 e ⁻⁶	3.75 e ⁻³
GOBP_ANATOMICAL_STRUCTURE_FORMATION_IN_INVOLVED_IN_MORPHOGENESIS [1244]	The developmental process pertaining to the initial formation of an anatomical	10	5.37 e ⁻⁶	3.75 e ⁻³

GOBP_SECONDARY_PALATE_DEVELOPMENT [26]	The biological process whose specific outcome is the progression of the secondary palate from an initial condition to its mature state. This process begins with the formation of the structure and ends with the mature structure. The secondary palate is the part of the palate formed from the fusion of the two palatine shelves, extensions of the maxillary prominences. [PMID:28784960]	3	5.8×10^{-6}	3.75×10^{-3}
GOBP_ENZYME_LINKED_RECEPTOR_PROTEIN_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [1017]	The series of molecular signals initiated by an extracellular ligand binding. The process in which cellular structures, including whole cells or cell parts, are generated and organized. [GOC:dph, GOC:mah, GOC:tb]	9	7.82×10^{-6}	4.53×10^{-3}
GOBP_CELLULAR_COMPONENT_MORPHOGENESIS [768]	Any process that modulates the physical form or the activity of a	8	8.16×10^{-6}	4.53×10^{-3}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_SYNAPSE_STRUCTURE_OR_ACTIVITY [215]		5	1.06×10^{-5}	5.5×10^{-3}

GOBP_GENERATION_OF_NEURONS [1453]	The process in which nerve cells are generated. This includes the production of neuroblasts and their differentiation into neurons. [GOC:nln]	10	2.06×10^{-5}	1×10^{-2}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_MULTICELLULAR_ORGANISMAL_DEVELOPMENT [1471]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of	10	2.29×10^{-5}	1.05×10^{-2}
GOBP_CIRCULATORY_SYSTEM_DEVELOPMENT [1211]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of the circulatory system over time, from its formation to the mature structure. The circulatory system is the organ system that passes nutrients (such as amino acids and electrolytes), gases, hormones, blood cells, etc. to and from cells in the body to help fight diseases and help stabilize body temperature and pH to maintain homeostasis. [GOC:mah, UBERON:0001009]	9	3.1×10^{-5}	1.29×10^{-2}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_NERVOUS_SYSTEM_DEVELOPMENT [456]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of nervous	6	3.34×10^{-5}	1.29×10^{-2}

GOBP_ODONTOGENESIS [135]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a tooth or teeth over time, from formation to the mature structure(s). A tooth is any hard bony, calcareous, or chitinous organ found in the mouth or pharynx of an animal and used in procuring or masticating food. [GOC:jl, GOC:mah]	4	3.36 e ⁻⁵	1.29 e ⁻²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CELL_PROJECTION_ORG ORGANIZATION [683]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of a process The process in which the anatomical structures of the digestive tract are generated and organized. The digestive tract is the anatomical structure through which food passes and is processed. [GOC:dph, GOC:go_curators, PMID:12618131]	7	3.49 e ⁻⁵	1.29 e ⁻²
GOBP_DIGESTIVE_TRACT_MORPHOGENESIS [49]		3	4.02 e ⁻⁵	1.31 e ⁻²

GOBP_CELL_PROJECTION_ORGANIZATION [1576]	<p>A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of a prolongation or process extending from a cell, e.g. a flagellum or axon. [GOC:jl, GOC:mah, http://www.cogsci.princeton.edu/~wn/]</p>	10	4.12×10^{-5}	1.31×10^{-2}
GOBP_BLOOD_VESSEL_MORPHOGENESIS [702]	<p>The process in which the anatomical structures of blood vessels are generated and organized. The blood vessel is the vasculature carrying blood. [GOC:jid]</p>	7	4.16×10^{-5}	1.31×10^{-2}

GOBP_DIGESTIVE_SYSTEM_DEVELOPMENT [143]	<p>The process whose specific outcome is the progression of the digestive system over time, from its formation to the mature structure. The digestive system is the entire structure in which digestion takes place. Digestion is all of the physical, chemical, and biochemical processes carried out by multicellular organisms to break down ingested nutrients into components that may be easily absorbed and directed into metabolism.</p>	4	4.21 e ⁻⁵	1.31 e ⁻²
GOBP_L_PHENYLALANINE_METABOLIC_PROCESS [8]	<p>The chemical reactions and pathways involving L-phenylalanine, the L-enantiomer of 2-amino-3-phenylpropanoic acid, i.e. (2S)-2-amino-3-phenylpropanoic acid.</p>	2	4.92 e ⁻⁵	1.46 e ⁻²

GOBP_EPITHELIAL_CELL_PROLIFERATION [492]	The multiplication or reproduction of epithelial cells, resulting in the expansion of a cell population. Epithelial cells make up the epithelium, the covering of internal and external surfaces of the body, including the lining of vessels and other small cavities. It consists of cells joined by small amounts of cementing substances.	6	5.09 e ⁻⁵	1.46 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_CELLULAR_CR_COMPONENT_BIOGENESIS [499]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of cellular	6	5.51 e ⁻⁵	1.51 e ⁻²
GOBP_VENTRICULAR_CARDIAC_MUSCLE_TISSUE_SUE_DEVELOPMENT [55]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of ventricular cardiac	3	5.7 e ⁻⁵	1.51 e ⁻²
GOBP_RESPONSE_TO_ENDOGENOUS_STIMULUS [1643]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell or an organism (in terms of movement, secretion, enzyme production, gene expression, etc.) as a result of a stimulus arising within the organism. [GOC:sm]	10	5.84 e ⁻⁵	1.51 e ⁻²
GOBP_NEURONAL_ACTION_POTENTIAL_PROPAGATION [9]	The propagation of an action potential along an axon, away from the soma.	2	6.32 e ⁻⁵	1.58 e ⁻²

GOBP_NEUROGENESIS [1669]	Generation of cells within the nervous system. [GO_REF:0000021, GOC:cls, GOC:curators, GOC:dgh, GOC:dph, GOC:jid]	10	6.65 e ⁻⁵	1.61 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_CELLULAR_CR_COMPONENT_ORGANIZATION [1052]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of a process	8	7.63 e ⁻⁵	1.8 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_SYNAPSE_ASSEMBLY [63]	Any process that activates, maintains or increases the frequency, rate or extent	3	8.56 e ⁻⁵	1.95 e ⁻²
GOBP_CELLULAR_RESPONSE_TO_ENDOGENOUS_SIGNAL_STIMULUS [1394]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell (in terms of	9	9.17 e ⁻⁵	2.03 e ⁻²
GOBP_LIPID_METABOLIC_PROCESS [1415]	The chemical reactions and pathways involving lipids, compounds soluble in an organic solvent but not, or sparingly, in an aqueous solvent. Includes fatty acids; neutral fats, other fatty-acid esters, and soaps; long-chain (fatty) alcohols and waxes; sphingoids and other long-chain bases; glycolipids, phospholipids and sphingolipids; and carotenes, polyprenols, sterols, terpenes and other isoprenoids. [GOC:ma]	9	1.03 e ⁻⁴	2.19 e ⁻²

GOBP_INOSITOL_LIPID_MEDIATED_SIGNALING [182]	<p>The series of molecular signals in which a cell uses an inositol-containing lipid to convert a signal into a response. Inositol lipids include the phosphoinositides (phosphatidylinositol and its phosphorylated derivatives), ceramides containing inositol, and inositol glycolipids. [GOC:bf, GOC:ceb, PMID:16088939]</p>	4	1.07 e ⁻⁴	2.19 e ⁻²
GOBP_VASCULATURE_DEVELOPMENT [819]	<p>The process whose specific outcome is the progression of the vasculature over time, from its formation to the mature structure. The vasculature is an interconnected tubular multi-tissue structure that contains fluid that is actively transported around the organism. [GOC:dph, UBERON:0002409]</p>	7	1.09 e ⁻⁴	2.19 e ⁻²

GOBP_NEURON_DEVELOPMENT [1113]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a neuron over time, from initial commitment of the cell to a specific fate, to the fully functional differentiated cell. [GOC:dph]	8	1.13 e ⁻⁴	2.19 e ⁻²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_CELL_POPULATION_PROLIFERATION [1779]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of cell	10	1.13 e ⁻⁴	2.19 e ⁻²
GOBP_PROTEOLYSIS [1795]	The hydrolysis of proteins into smaller polypeptides and/or amino acids by cleavage of their peptide bonds. [GOC:bf, GOC:mah]	10	1.21 e ⁻⁴	2.3 e ⁻²
GOBP_GLANDULAR_EPITHELIAL_CELL_DIFFERENTIATION [73]	The process in which a relatively unspecialized cell acquires specialized	3	1.33 e ⁻⁴	2.45 e ⁻²
GOBP_NEURAL_RETINA_DEVELOPMENT [79]	The progression of the neural retina over time from its initial formation to the mature structure. The neural retina is the part of the retina that contains neurons and photoreceptor cells. [GOC:ascb_2009, GOC:dph, GOC:tb]	3	1.68 e ⁻⁴	3.03 e ⁻²

GOBP_TYROSINE_METABOLIC_PROCESS [15]	The chemical reactions and pathways involving tyrosine, an aromatic amino acid, 2-amino-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)propanoic acid. [GOC:go_curators]	2	1.83 e ⁻⁴	3.16 e ⁻²
GOBP_TAXIS [623]	The directed movement of a motile cell or organism in response to an external stimulus. [GOC:jl, ISBN:0192801023]	6	1.85 e ⁻⁴	3.16 e ⁻²
GOBP_TRANSMEMBRANE_RECEPTOR_PROTEIN_SE _SERINE_THREONINE_KINASE_SIGNALING_PATHWAY [395]	The series of molecular signals initiated by an extracellular ligand binding to a receptor on the surface of the target cell Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of the growth of all or part of an organism so that it occurs at its proper speed, either globally or in a specific part of the organism's development. [GOC:ems, GOC:mah]	5	1.89 e ⁻⁴	3.16 e ⁻²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_GROWTH [627]	The process whose specific outcome is the progression of a sensory system over time from its formation to the mature structure.	6	1.91 e ⁻⁴	3.16 e ⁻²
GOBP_SENSORY_SYSTEM_DEVELOPMENT [398]	[GOC:dgh]	5	1.96 e ⁻⁴	3.17 e ⁻²

			The process whose specific outcome is the progression of an epithelium over time, from its formation to the mature structure. An epithelium is a tissue that covers the internal or external surfaces of an anatomical structure. [GOC:dph, GOC:mtg_lung]	8	2.01×10^{-4}	3.18×10^{-2}
		GOBP_EPITHELIUM_DEVELOPMENT [1211]				
		GOBP_AROMATIC_AMINO_ACID_FAMILY_CATABOLIC_PROCESS [16]	The chemical reactions and pathways resulting in the breakdown of aromatic	2	2.09×10^{-4}	3.25×10^{-2}
24	90	REACTOME_SYNTHESIS_OF_BILE_ACIDS_AND_BILE_SALTS_VIA_24-HYDROXYCHOLESTEROL [14]	Synthesis of bile acids and bile salts via 24-hydroxycholesterol Catalysis of the reaction: an alcohol + NADP+ = an aldehyde or a ketone + NADPH + H+. [GOC:ai]	3	3.65×10^{-6}	1.11×10^{-2}
		GOMF_ALDO_KETO_REDUCTASE_NADP_ACTIVITY [31]		3	4.39×10^{-5}	2.79×10^{-2}
		GOMF_MONOCARBOXYLIC_ACID_BINDING [89]	Binding to a monocarboxylic acid, any organic acid containing one carboxyl (COOH) group or anion (COO-). [GOC:mah]	4	4.59×10^{-5}	2.79×10^{-2}
		GOMF_KETOSTEROID_MONOOXYGENASE_ACTIVITY [5]	Catalysis of the reaction: O2 + NADPH + progesterone = H2O +	2	4.74×10^{-5}	2.79×10^{-2}

25	39						
		GOMF_GLUCURONOSYLTRANSFERASE_ACTIVITY [35]	Catalysis of the reaction: UDP-glucuronate + acceptor = UDP + acceptor beta-D-glucuronoside. [RHEA:21032]	3	5.09×10^{-6}	8.98×10^{-3}	
		GOMF_EXTRACELLULAR_MATRIX_STRUCTURAL_C L_CONSTITUENT [173]	The action of a molecule that contributes to the structural integrity of the	4	2.24×10^{-5}	1.98×10^{-2}	
			The modification of an organic chemical by the conjugation of glucuronic acid. The substances resulting from glucuronidation are known as glucuronosides (or glucuronides) and are often much more water- soluble than the non- glucuronic acid-containing precursor. [GOC:BHF]				
		GOBP_CELLULAR_GLUCURONIDATION [21]		3	1.04×10^{-6}	7.9×10^{-3}	

GOBP_URONIC_ACID_METABOLIC_PROCESS [26]	<p>The chemical reactions and pathways involving uronic acid, any monocarboxylic acid formally derived by oxidizing to a carboxyl group the terminal hydroxymethylene group of either an aldose with four or more carbon atoms in the molecule, or of any glycoside derived from such an aldose.</p> <p>[ISBN:0198506732]</p>	3	2.04 e^{-6}	7.9 e^{-3}
GOBP_XENOBIOTIC_METABOLIC_PROCESS [118]	<p>The chemical reactions and pathways involving a xenobiotic compound, a compound foreign to the organism exposed to it. It may be synthesized by another organism (like ampicilin) or it can be a synthetic chemical.</p> <p>[GOC:cab2, GOC:krc]</p>	4	4.95 e^{-6}	1.19 e^{-2}
GOBP_ESTROGEN_METABOLIC_PROCESS [39]	<p>The chemical reactions and pathways involving estrogens, C18 steroid hormones that can stimulate the development of female sexual characteristics. Also found in plants.</p> <p>[ISBN:0198506732]</p>	3	7.09 e^{-6}	1.19 e^{-2}

GOBP_REGULATION_OF_WOUND_HEALING [137]	Any process that modulates the rate, frequency, or extent of the series of events that restore integrity to a damaged tissue, following an injury. [GOC:BHF, GOC:dph]	4	8.95 e ⁻⁶	1.19 e ⁻²
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_HORMONE_LEVELS [520]	Any process that modulates the levels of hormone within an organism or a tissue. A hormone is any substance formed in very small amounts in one specialized organ or group of cells and carried (sometimes in the bloodstream) to another organ or group of cells in the same organism, upon which it has a specific regulatory action. [GOC:BHF, GOC:dph, GOC:tb]	6	9.23 e ⁻⁶	1.19 e ⁻²

GOBP_XENOBIOTIC_GLUCURONIDATION [7]	The modification of a xenobiotic substance by the conjugation of glucuronic acid. The resultant glucuronosides are often much more water-soluble than the xenobiotic precursor, enabling efficient excretion. [GOC:BHF, PMID:20056724]	2	1.84×10^{-5}	1.85×10^{-2}
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_COAGULATION [54]	Any process that stops, prevents, or reduces the frequency, rate or extent	3	1.91×10^{-5}	1.85×10^{-2}
GOBP_REGULATION_OF_RESPONSE_TO_WOUNDING [172]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of response	4	2.19×10^{-5}	1.86×10^{-2}
GOBP_MONOCARBOXYLIC_ACID_METABOLIC_PROCESS [616]	The chemical reactions and pathways involving monocarboxylic acids, any	6	2.4×10^{-5}	1.86×10^{-2}
GOBP_CELLULAR_RESPONSE_TO_XENOBIOTIC_STIMULUS [183]	Any process that results in a change in state or activity of a cell (in terms of	4	2.79×10^{-5}	1.97×10^{-2}
GOBP_ORGANIC_ACID_METABOLIC_PROCESS [966]	The chemical reactions and pathways involving organic acids, any acidic compound containing carbon in covalent linkage. [ISBN:0198506732]	7	3.13×10^{-5}	2.03×10^{-2}

GOBP_REGULATION_OF_COAGULATION [75]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of coagulation, the process in which a fluid solution, or part of it, changes into a solid or semisolid mass. [GOC:ai]	3	5.12 e ⁻⁵	3.06 e ⁻²
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_WOUND_HEALING [78]	Any process that decreases the rate, frequency, or extent of the series of	3	5.76 e ⁻⁵	3.19 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_HETEROTYPIC_CELL_CELL_ADHESION [15]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate, or extent of	2	9.18 e ⁻⁵	4.75 e ⁻²
GOBP_NEGATIVE_REGULATION_OF_RESPONSE_TO_WOUNDING [94]	Any process that stops, prevents or reduces the frequency, rate or extent	3	1 e ⁻⁴	4.87 e ⁻²
KEGG_DRUG_METABOLISM_OTHER_ENZYMES [51]	Drug metabolism - other enzymes	4	1.69 e ⁻⁷	5.15 e ⁻⁴
KEGG_RETINOL_METABOLISM [64]	Retinol metabolism	4	4.26 e ⁻⁷	6.49 e ⁻⁴
KEGG_DRUG_METABOLISM_CYTOCHROME_P450 [72]	Drug metabolism - cytochrome P450	4	6.85 e ⁻⁷	6.96 e ⁻⁴
KEGG_ASCORBATE_AND_ALDARATE_METABOLISM [25]	Ascorbate and aldarate metabolism	3	1.8 e ⁻⁶	9.17 e ⁻⁴
REACTOME_GLUCURONIDATION [25]	Glucuronidation	3	1.8 e ⁻⁶	9.17 e ⁻⁴
WP_GLUCURONIDATION [26]	Glucuronidation	3	2.04 e ⁻⁶	9.17 e ⁻⁴
REACTOME_BIOLOGICAL_OXIDATIONS [220]	Biological oxidations	5	2.11 e ⁻⁶	9.17 e ⁻⁴
KEGG_PENTOSE_AND_GLUCURONATE_INTERCONVERSIONS [28]	Pentose and glucuronate interconversions	3	2.56 e ⁻⁶	9.76 e ⁻⁴
KEGG_PORPHYRIN_AND_CHLOROPHYLL_METABOLISM [41]	Porphyrin and chlorophyll metabolism	3	8.26 e ⁻⁶	2.8 e ⁻³

REACTOME_ASPIRIN_ADME [44]	Aspirin ADME	3	1.02×10^{-5}	3.12×10^{-3}
KEGG_STARCH_AND_SUCROSE_METABOLISM [52]	Starch and sucrose metabolism	3	1.7×10^{-5}	4.69×10^{-3}
WP_COVID19_THROMBOSIS_AND_ANTICOAGULATION [7]	COVID-19, thrombosis and anticoagulation	2	1.84×10^{-5}	4.69×10^{-3}
KEGG_STEROID_HORMONE_BIOSYNTHESIS [55]	Steroid hormone biosynthesis	3	2.02×10^{-5}	4.73×10^{-3}
WP_FOLATE_METABOLISM [69]	Folate metabolism	3	3.99×10^{-5}	8.46×10^{-3}
KEGG_METABOLISM_OF_XENOBIOTICS_BY_CYTOCHROME_P450 [70]	Metabolism of xenobiotics by cytochrome P450	3	4.16×10^{-5}	8.46×10^{-3}
NABA_MATRISOME [1026]	Ensemble of genes encoding extracellular matrix and extracellular matrix-associated proteins	7	4.59×10^{-5}	8.75×10^{-3}
BIOCARTA_FIBRINOLYSIS_PATHWAY [12]	Fibrinolysis Pathway	2	5.78×10^{-5}	1.04×10^{-2}
BIOCARTA_EXTRINSIC_PATHWAY [13]	Extrinsic Prothrombin Activation Pathway	2	6.83×10^{-5}	1.16×10^{-2}
REACTOME_GRB2_SOS_PROVIDES_LINKAGE_TO_TO_MAPK_SIGNALING_FOR_INTEGRINS [15]	GRB2:SOS provides linkage to MAPK signaling for Integrins	2	9.18×10^{-5}	1.4×10^{-2}
REACTOME_P130CAS_LINKAGE_TO_MAPK_SIGNALING_FOR_INTEGRINS [15]	p130Cas linkage to MAPK signaling for integrins	2	9.18×10^{-5}	1.4×10^{-2}
REACTOME_DRUG_ADME [98]	Drug ADME	3	1.14×10^{-4}	1.65×10^{-2}
REACTOME_IRAK4_DEFICIENCY_TLR2_4 [18]	IRAK4 deficiency (TLR2/4)	2	1.34×10^{-4}	1.79×10^{-2}

NABA_CORE_MATRISOME [275]	Ensemble of genes encoding core extracellular matrix including ECM glycoproteins, collagens and proteoglycans	4	1.35 e ⁻⁴	1.79 e ⁻²
REACTOME_PHASE_II_CONJUGATION_OF_COMPOUNDS [109]	Phase II - Conjugation of compounds	3	1.56 e ⁻⁴	1.98 e ⁻²
BIOCARTA_AMI_PATHWAY [20]	Acute Myocardial Infarction	2	1.66 e ⁻⁴	2.02 e ⁻²
REACTOME_REGULATION_OF_TLR_BY_ENDOGENOUS_LIGAND [21]	Regulation of TLR by endogenous ligand	2	1.83 e ⁻⁴	2.15 e ⁻²
REACTOME_COMMON_PATHWAY_OF_FIBRIN_CLOT_FORMATION [22]	Common Pathway of Fibrin Clot Formation	2	2.01 e ⁻⁴	2.19 e ⁻²
WP_BLOOD_CLOTTING_CASCADE [22]	Blood clotting cascade	2	2.01 e ⁻⁴	2.19 e ⁻²
BIOCARTA_INTRINSIC_PATHWAY [23]	Intrinsic Prothrombin Activation Pathway	2	2.2 e ⁻⁴	2.31 e ⁻²
REACTOME_REGULATION_OF_INSULIN_LIKE_GROWTH_FACTOR_IGF_TRANSPORT_AND_UPTAKE_BY_INSULIN_LIKE_GROWTH_FACTOR_BINDING_PROTEINS_IGFBPS [124]	Regulation of Insulin-like Growth Factor (IGF) transport and uptake by Insulin-like Growth Factor Binding Proteins (IGFBPs)	3	2.28 e ⁻⁴	2.31 e ⁻²
REACTOME_INTEGRIN_SIGNALING [27]	Integrin signaling	2	3.05 e ⁻⁴	3 e ⁻²
PID_INTEGRIN2_PATHWAY [29]	Beta2 integrin cell surface interactions	2	3.52 e ⁻⁴	3.35 e ⁻²
PID_EPHRINB_REV_PATHWAY [30]	Ephrin B reverse signaling	2	3.77 e ⁻⁴	3.48 e ⁻²
REACTOME_DISEASES_OF_IMMUNE_SYSTEM [31]	Diseases of Immune System	2	4.03 e ⁻⁴	3.61 e ⁻²

		NABA_PROTEOGLYCANS [35]	Genes encoding proteoglycans	2	5.14 e ⁻⁴	4.48 e ⁻²
26	201	REACTOME_EUKARYOTIC_TRANSLATION_ELONGATION [94]	Eukaryotic Translation Elongation	17	4.12 e ⁻²²	9.53 e ⁻¹⁹
		REACTOME_SELENOAMINO_ACID_METABOLISM [118]	Selenoamino acid metabolism	18	6.25 e ⁻²²	9.53 e ⁻¹⁹
		REACTOME_RESPONSE_OF_EIF2AK4_GCIN2_TO_AO_AMINO_ACID_DEFICIENCY [102]	Response of EIF2AK4 (GCIN2) to amino acid deficiency	17	1.81 e ⁻²¹	1.84 e ⁻¹⁸
		KEGG_RIBOSOME [88]	Ribosome	16	6.41 e ⁻²¹	3.91 e ⁻¹⁸
		WP_CYTOPLASMIC_RIBOSOMAL_PROTEINS [88]	Cytoplasmic ribosomal proteins	16	6.41 e ⁻²¹	3.91 e ⁻¹⁸
		REACTOME_SRP_DEPENDENT_COTRANSLATIONAL_NAL_PROTEIN_TARGETING_TO_MEMBRANE [113]	SRP-dependent cotranslational protein targeting to membrane	17	1.14 e ⁻²⁰	5.8 e ⁻¹⁸
		REACTOME_NONSENSE_MEDIATED_DECAY_NMD [116]	Nonsense-Mediated Decay (NMD)	17	1.82 e ⁻²⁰	7.94 e ⁻¹⁸
		REACTOME_RRNA_PROCESSING [205]	rRNA processing	20	3 e ⁻²⁰	1.13 e ⁻¹⁷
		REACTOME_EUKARYOTIC_TRANSLATION_INITIATION [120]	Eukaryotic Translation Initiation	17	3.33 e ⁻²⁰	1.13 e ⁻¹⁷
		REACTOME_TRANSLATION [295]	Translation	22	1.29 e ⁻¹⁹	3.93 e ⁻¹⁷
		REACTOME_CELLULAR_RESPONSE_TO_STARVATION [157]	Cellular response to starvation	17	3.67 e ⁻¹⁸	9.32 e ⁻¹⁶
		REACTOME_INFLUENZA_INFECTION [157]	Influenza Infection	17	3.67 e ⁻¹⁸	9.32 e ⁻¹⁶
		REACTOME_REGULATION_OF_EXPRESSION_OF_SLF_SLITS_AND_ROBOS [172]	Regulation of expression of SLITs and ROBOs	17	1.76 e ⁻¹⁷	4.13 e ⁻¹⁵
		REACTOME_SIGNALING_BY_ROBO_RECEPTORS [218]	Signaling by ROBO receptors	17	9.71 e ⁻¹⁶	2.11 e ⁻¹³

REACTOME_SARS_COV_2_MODULATES_HOST_TRANSLATION_MACHINERY [51]	SARS-CoV-2 modulates host translation machinery	11	1.19×10^{-15}	2.42×10^{-13}
REACTOME_METABOLISM_OF_RNA [674]	Metabolism of RNA	25	5.51×10^{-15}	1.05×10^{-12}
REACTOME_METABOLISM_OF_AMINO_ACIDS_AND_DERIVATIVES [373]	Metabolism of amino acids and derivatives	19	4.56×10^{-14}	8.18×10^{-12}
REACTOME_CELLULAR_RESPONSES_TO_STIMULI [812]	Cellular responses to stimuli	23	1.75×10^{-11}	2.97×10^{-9}
REACTOME_INFECTIOUS_DISEASE [1077]	Infectious disease	25	1.48×10^{-10}	2.37×10^{-8}
REACTOME_NERVOUS_SYSTEM_DEVELOPMENT [580]	Nervous system development	18	7.38×10^{-10}	1.12×10^{-7}
REACTOME_SARS_COV_2_HOST_INTERACTIONS [204]	SARS-CoV-2-host interactions	11	6.33×10^{-9}	9.2×10^{-7}
REACTOME_ACTIVATION_OF_THE_MRNA_UPON_BINDING_OF_THE_CAP_BINDING_COMPLEX_AND_EIFs_AND_SUBSEQUENT_BINDING_TO_43S [60]	Activation of the mRNA upon binding of the cap-binding complex and eIFs, and subsequent binding to 43S	7	1.9×10^{-8}	2.63×10^{-6}
REACTOME_SARS_COV_2_INFECTION [289]	SARS-CoV-2 Infection	11	2.21×10^{-7}	2.93×10^{-5}
BIOCARTA_SM_PATHWAY [14]	Spliceosomal Assembly	4	5.39×10^{-7}	6.85×10^{-5}
REACTOME_DEVELOPMENTAL_BIOLOGY [1151]	Developmental Biology	20	1.15×10^{-6}	1.41×10^{-4}
REACTOME_SARS_COV_INFECTIONS [432]	SARS-CoV Infections	11	1.07×10^{-5}	1.25×10^{-3}
REACTOME_RESPIRATORY_ELECTRON_TRANSPORT_ATP_SYNTHESIS_BY_CHEMIOSMOTIC_COUPLING_AND_HEAT_PRODUCTION_BY_UNCOUPLING_PROTEINS [127]	Respiratory electron transport, ATP synthesis by chemiosmotic coupling, and heat production by uncoupling proteins.	6	4.06×10^{-5}	4.59×10^{-3}

REACTOME_MRNA_SPLICING_MINOR_PATHWAY [50]	mRNA Splicing - Minor Pathway	4	1.08 e ⁻⁴	1.18 e ⁻²
REACTOME_SNRNP_ASSEMBLY [54]	snRNP Assembly	4	1.46 e ⁻⁴	1.54 e ⁻²
REACTOME_RESPIRATORY_ELECTRON_TRANSPORT [103]	Respiratory electron transport	5	1.6 e ⁻⁴	1.62 e ⁻²
WP_MITOCHONDRIAL_COMPLEX_I_ASSEMBLY_MODEL_OXPHOS_SYSTEM [56]	Mitochondrial complex I assembly model OXPHOS system	4	1.68 e ⁻⁴	1.66 e ⁻²
REACTOME_INTERLEUKIN_12_FAMILY_SIGNALING [57]	Interleukin-12 family signaling	4	1.8 e ⁻⁴	1.72 e ⁻²
REACTOME_THE_CITRIC_ACID_TCA_CYCLE_AND AND_RESPIRATORY_ELECTRON_TRANSPORT [178]	The citric acid (TCA) cycle and respiratory electron transport	6	2.59 e ⁻⁴	2.4 e ⁻²
KEGG_OXIDATIVE_PHOSPHORYLATION [132]	Oxidative phosphorylation The chemical reactions and pathways resulting in the formation of a protein in the cytoplasm. This is a ribosome-mediated process in which the information in messenger RNA (mRNA) is used to specify the sequence of amino acids in the protein.	5	5.03 e ⁻⁴	4.51 e ⁻²
GOBP_CYTOPLASMIC_TRANSLATION [161]	[GOC:hjd]	17	5.66 e ⁻¹⁸	4.39 e ⁻¹⁴

GOBP_AMIDE_BIOSYNTHETIC_PROCESS [932]	<p>The chemical reactions and pathways resulting in the formation of an amide, any derivative of an oxoacid in which an acidic hydroxy group has been replaced by an amino or substituted amino group.</p> <p>[GOC:curators]</p>	26	1.07 e^{-12}	4.15 e^{-9}
GOBP_CELLULAR_AMIDE_METABOLIC_PROCESS [1245]	<p>The chemical reactions and pathways involving an amide, any derivative of an oxoacid in which an acidic hydroxy group has been replaced by an amino or substituted amino group, as carried out by individual cells. [GOC:curators]</p>	29	3.98 e^{-12}	1.03 e^{-8}

GOBP_PEPTIDE_BIOSYNTHETIC_PROCESS [801]	The chemical reactions and pathways resulting in the formation of peptides, compounds of 2 or more (but usually less than 100) amino acids where the alpha carboxyl group of one is bound to the alpha amino group of another. This may include the translation of a precursor protein and its subsequent processing into a functional peptide. [GOC:dph, GOC:jl]	23	1.34 e ⁻¹¹	2.59 e ⁻⁸
GOBP_PEPTIDE_METABOLIC_PROCESS [967]	The chemical reactions and pathways involving peptides, compounds of two or more amino acids where the alpha carboxyl group of one is bound to the alpha amino group of another. [GOC:go_curators]	24	9.26 e ⁻¹¹	1.44 e ⁻⁷
GOBP_ORGANONITROGEN_COMPOUND_BIOSYNTHETIC_PROCESS [1821]	The chemical reactions and pathways resulting in the formation of	31	1.59 e ⁻⁹	2.06 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_RIBONUCLEOPROTEIN_COMPLEX_BIOGENESIS [487]	A cellular process that results in the biosynthesis of constituent	16	3.01 e ⁻⁹	3.34 e ⁻⁶
GOBP_7_METHYLGUANOSINE_CAP_HYPERMETHYLATION [8]	Hypermethylation of the 7-(mono)methylguanosine (m(7)G) cap structure at	4	3.86 e ⁻⁸	3.74 e ⁻⁵

GOBP_CELLULAR_MACROMOLECULE_BIOSYNTHETIC_PROCESS [1234]	The chemical reactions and pathways resulting in the formation of a	23	4.96×10^{-8}	4.28×10^{-5}
GOBP_PROTEIN_CONTAINING_COMPLEX_ORGANIZATION [1841]	Any process in which macromolecules aggregate, disaggregate, or	27	3.98×10^{-7}	3.09×10^{-4}
GOBP_RIBOSOME_BIOGENESIS [310]	A cellular process that results in the biosynthesis of constituent macromolecules, assembly, and arrangement of constituent parts of ribosome subunits; includes transport to the sites of protein synthesis. [GOC:ma, PMID:26404467, Wikipedia:Ribosome_biogenesis]	11	4.43×10^{-7}	3.13×10^{-4}
GOBP_RESPIRATORY_ELECTRON_TRANSPORT_CHAIN [122]	A process in which a series of electron carriers operate together to transfer	7	2.54×10^{-6}	1.52×10^{-3}

GOBP_RNA_CAPPING [20]	<p>The sequence of enzymatic reactions by which a cap structure is added to the 5' end of nascent RNA polymerase transcripts. Examples of RNA capping include 7-methyl-G caps found on all RNA polymerase II transcripts and nucleotide-containing cofactor caps, such as NAD(H) or FAD, found on bacterial transcripts.</p> <p>[GOC:bf, GOC:krc, GOC:mah, PMID:18775984, PMID:27383794, PMID:29681497, PMID:30353673]</p>	4	2.55×10^{-6}	1.52×10^{-3}
GOBP_ELECTRON_TRANSPORT_CHAIN [176]	<p>A process in which a series of electron carriers operate together to transfer electrons from donors to any of several different terminal electron acceptors.</p> <p>[GOC:mtg_electron_transport]</p>	8	2.78×10^{-6}	1.54×10^{-3}

GOBP_CELLULAR_RESPIRATION [240]	The enzymatic release of energy from inorganic and organic compounds (especially carbohydrates and fats) which either requires oxygen (aerobic respiration) or does not (anaerobic respiration). [GOC:das, ISBN:0140513590, ISBN:0198506732]	9	3.22 e ⁻⁶	1.56 e ⁻³
GOBP_RIBONUCLEOPROTEIN_COMPLEX_SUBUNIT NIT_ORGANIZATION [240]	Any process in which macromolecules aggregate, disaggregate, or	9	3.22 e ⁻⁶	1.56 e ⁻³
GOBP_U2_TYPE_PRESPLICEOSOME_ASSEMBLY [24]	The aggregation, arrangement and bonding together of a set of components to form an U2-type prespliceosome. [GO_REF:0000079, GOC:TermGenie, PMID:12374752]	4	5.51 e ⁻⁶	2.52 e ⁻³
GOBP_ENERGY_DERIVATION_BY_OXIDATION_OF _OF_ORGANIC_COMPOUNDS [333]	The chemical reactions and pathways by which a cell derives energy from	10	6.55 e ⁻⁶	2.82 e ⁻³
GOBP_GENERATION_OF_PRECURSOR_METABOLIT LITES_AND_ENERGY [505]	The chemical reactions and pathways resulting in the formation of precursor	12	8.49 e ⁻⁶	3.39 e ⁻³

GOBP_OXIDATIVE_PHOSPHORYLATION [147]	The phosphorylation of ADP to ATP that accompanies the oxidation of a metabolite through the operation of the respiratory chain. Oxidation of compounds establishes a proton gradient across the membrane, providing the energy for ATP synthesis. [ISBN:0198506732, ISBN:0471331309]	7	8.72 e^{-6}	3.39 e^{-3}
GOBP_MITOCHONDRIAL_RESPIRATORY_CHAIN_CN_COMPLEX_ASSEMBLY [99]	The aggregation, arrangement and bonding together of a set of	6	9.86 e^{-6}	3.65 e^{-3}
GOBP_ATP_SYNTHESIS_COUPLED_ELECTRON_TRANSPORT [101]	The transfer of electrons through a series of electron donors and	6	1.11 e^{-5}	3.9 e^{-3}

GOBP_MITOCHONDRION_ORGANIZATION [542]	<p>A process that is carried out at the cellular level which results in the assembly, arrangement of constituent parts, or disassembly of a mitochondrion; includes mitochondrial morphogenesis and distribution, and replication of the mitochondrial genome as well as synthesis of new mitochondrial components. [GOC:dph, GOC:jl, GOC:mah, GOC:sgd_curators, PMID:9786946]</p>	12	1.71 e^{-5}	5.77 e^{-3}
GOBP_RIBOSOMAL_SMALL_SUBUNIT_BIOGENESIS [78]	<p>A cellular process that results in the biosynthesis of constituent</p> <p>The enzymatic release of energy from inorganic and organic compounds (especially carbohydrates and fats) which requires oxygen as the terminal electron acceptor.</p>	5	4.25 e^{-5}	1.37 e^{-2}
GOBP_AEROBIC_RESPIRATION [194]	<p>[GOC:das, GOC:jl, ISBN:0140513590]</p>	7	5.19 e^{-5}	1.61 e^{-2}

GOBP_SPLICEOSOMAL_COMPLEX_ASSEMBLY [93]	The aggregation, arrangement and bonding together of a spliceosomal complex, a ribonucleoprotein apparatus that catalyzes nuclear mRNA splicing via transesterification reactions. [PMID:9476892]	5	9.85 e ⁻⁵	2.94 e ⁻²
GOBP_RIBOSOMAL_SMALL_SUBUNIT_ASSEMBLY [19]	The aggregation, arrangement and bonding together of constituent RNAs and proteins to form the small ribosomal subunit. [GOC:jl]	3	1.06 e ⁻⁴	3.05 e ⁻²
GOBP_POSITIVE_REGULATION_OF_ANION_TRANSPORT [51]	Any process that activates or increases the frequency, rate or extent of anion	4	1.17 e ⁻⁴	3.13 e ⁻²
GOBP_SPLICEOSOMAL_SNRNP_ASSEMBLY [51]	The aggregation, arrangement and bonding together of one or more snRNA and multiple protein components to form a ribonucleoprotein complex that is involved in formation of the spliceosome. [GOC:krc, GOC:mah, ISBN:0879695897]	4	1.17 e ⁻⁴	3.13 e ⁻²
GOMF_STRUCTURAL_CONSTITUENT_OF_RIBOSOM	The action of a molecule that contributes to the			

SOME [169]	structural integrity of the The action of a molecule that contributes to the structural integrity of a complex or its assembly within or outside a cell.	19	1.77 e ⁻²⁰	3.12 e ⁻¹⁷
GOMF_STRUCTUREAL_MOLECULE_ACTIVITY [808]	[GOC:mah, GOC:vw]	27	5.22 e ⁻¹⁵	4.6 e ⁻¹²
GOMF_RNA_BINDING [1961]	Binding to an RNA molecule or a portion thereof. [GOC:jl, GOC:mah]	38	3.49 e ⁻¹³	2.05 e ⁻¹⁰
GOMF_RRNA_BINDING [67]	Binding to a ribosomal RNA. [GOC:jl]	6	1 e ⁻⁶	4.41 e ⁻⁴

27	101				
	GOBP_CIRCADIAN_RHYTHM [210]	Any biological process in an organism that recurs with a regularity of approximately 24 hours. [GOC:bf, GOC:go_curators]	6	1.42 e ⁻⁵	4.6 e ⁻²
	GOBP_CELL_RECOGNITION [224]	The process in which a cell in an organism interprets its surroundings. [GOC:go_curators]	6	2.04 e ⁻⁵	4.6 e ⁻²
	GOBP_MEMBRANE_INVAGINATION [136]	The infolding of a membrane. [GOC:tb]	5	2.28 e ⁻⁵	4.6 e ⁻²

GOBP_NEURON_PROJECTION_GUIDANCE [237]	The process in which the migration of a neuron projection is directed to a specific target site in response to a combination of attractive and repulsive cues. [GOC:BHF, GOC:rl, PMID:22790009]	6	2.8×10^{-5}	4.6×10^{-2}
GOBP_CIRCADIAN_REGULATION_OF_GENE_EXPRESSION [71]	Any process that modulates the frequency, rate or extent of gene	4	2.96×10^{-5}	4.6×10^{-2}
WP_CIRCADIAN_RHYTHM_GENES [201]	Circadian rhythm genes	6	1.11×10^{-5}	3.37×10^{-2}

28

30

none